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Editors:

Mehdi Ghommem, Aych Benjeddou, Jinsong Leng, Abdessattar Abdelkefi

Editorial

This e-book contains the edited proceedings of SMN2024, the *Eighth International Conference on Smart Materials & Nanotechnology in Engineering*, held on November 25–28, 2024, at the American University of Sharjah, Sharjah, United Arab Emirates. The conference continues the successful tradition of previous editions held in Harbin (China, 2007), Weihai (China, 2009), Shenzhen (China, 2011), Gold Coast (Australia, 2013), Vancouver (Canada, 2015), Madrid (Spain, 2017), and Harbin (China, 2019).

SMN2024 served as a platform connecting dynamic advancements in smart materials and nanotechnology for engineering applications. These fields, covering a range of domains such as aerospace, automotive, mechanical and civil engineering, robotics, and biomedicine, emphasize the integration of active, multifunctional materials and nanotechnology. With the rapid growth of hybrid technologies, the combination of nanomaterials and smart materials remains a frontier of innovation. SMN2024 included contributions across traditional and emerging areas, highlighting the multidisciplinary nature of the field. This edition's structure featured 5 plenary lectures, 2 keynote lectures, mini-symposia, special sessions, and general tracks, distributed over 15 parallel technical sessions and showcasing both traditional and emerging topics in smart materials and nanotechnology. SMN 2024 featured 77 speakers. Notably, 32% of the speakers were PhD or Master's students, highlighting the event's commitment to promoting emerging researchers and fostering academic growth. The conference attracted an audience of over 100 participants, representing a global community from 15 different countries, further emphasizing its international reach and collaborative spirit.

From the 80 scheduled contributions: 5 plenary lectures, 2 keynote lectures, 65 oral and 8 poster presentations, 16 papers (abstract and full paper submission option) were accepted, after peer-review and revision, for inclusion in the present proceedings. This represents 20% of the programmed presentations.

We express our gratitude to the contributing authors, session organizers, and the international scientific committee for their invaluable efforts. Special thanks go to the sponsors and supporting institutions for their generous support, ensuring the success of this conference. We hope these proceedings serve as a valuable resource for researchers and practitioners worldwide, further advancing the field of smart materials and nanotechnology in engineering.

Mehdi Ghommem, Aych Benjeddou, Jinsong Leng, Abdessattar Abdelkefi (*Editors*)

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THERMAL PERFORMANCE OF KRESLING ORIGAMI STRUCTURES AS DEPLOYABLE HEAT FINS

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Abstract. This paper investigates the thermal performance of Kresling origami structures as deployable heat fins for enhanced thermal management. Origami-inspired designs offer unique advantages in heat dissipation due to their shape-transforming capabilities, enabling adaptive heat transfer solutions. The study focuses on both numerical and experimental analysis of Kresling origami fins, with the objective of understanding their conductive and convective heat transfer characteristics. Experimental measurements are conducted in a controlled wind tunnel environment enclosing a heated body with deployable origami fins. Further, a transient three-dimensional numerical model is developed based on the conservation principles of mass, momentum, and energy to simulate the heat transfer behavior. The results demonstrate that the use of Kresling origami fins significantly improves cooling performance, reducing the temperature of the heated body by up to 35.1% and 14.1% compared to a finless systems and traditionally finned system, respectively. Overall, the study demonstrates that Kresling origami offers promising potential as a deployable and efficient thermal management solution, especially in systems requiring adaptability and compactness.

Keywords: Kresling Origami; Heat fins; Thermal characterization; Deployable fins.

1 INTRODUCTION

Thermal management devices are critical for controlling heat flow in various systems, ensuring that components operate within safe temperature limits [1]. They play a key role in electronics, aerospace, and energy systems by dissipating heat, preventing overheating, and improving efficiency [2]. These devices can include heat fins, cooling fans, and phase change materials to manage heat transfer [3].

Deployable heat fins have gained attention in thermal management systems due to the increasing need for adaptable cooling solutions in compact and dynamic environments [4]. Traditional fixed fins often face limitations in applications requiring variable heat dissipation, such as electronics, aerospace, and renewable energy systems. Deployable fins, which can adjust their geometry in response to changing thermal loads, offer a more efficient approach by dynamically optimizing heat transfer. These fins can expand or retract based on operational demands, enhancing or minimizing heat dissipation on demand [5, 6].

In recent years, origami-inspired designs have emerged as promising candidates for advanced thermal management solutions acting as deployable fins [7]. Origami structures offer unique advantages, including high flexibility, scalability, and compactness, making them particularly suited for dynamic thermal control applications [8, 9]. Their ability to undergo complex geometric transformations allows for optimized and controlled heat dissipation, providing efficient pathways for thermal management.

Several studies have examined the thermal characteristics of various origami patterns, particularly Miura-Ori patterns (see Fig. 1(a)), for their ability to control heat transfer through conduction, convection, and radiation mechanisms. For instance, Rehmeier et al. [7] characterized an extendable multi-layer insulation employing an origami pattern for spacecraft applications. The origami folds decreased heat conductance by 42% while increasing radiative heat by 236%. Similarly, Mulford et al. [10] studied the ability of Miura-Ori patterns to control radiative heat in dynamic environments. Subsequently, Iverson et al. [11] further compared the apparent radiative absorptivity of the Miura-Ori, V-groove, and hinged V-groove surfaces and determined the dominant geometrical parameters. More recently, Ahmed et al. [12] incorporated natural convection analysis to radiative heat transfer with respect to the Miura-Ori and W-fold origami. The overall heat transfer coefficient were experimentally controlled by changing the compression length of the geometry. In specific, compressing the Miura-Ori and W-fold origami decreased the heat transfer coefficient by up to 25.3% and 45.9%, respectively.

Figure 1: a) Miura-Ori origami pattern mostly employed in origami-inspired thermal management systems, and b) Kresling origami pattern proposed in this study.

While these studies have largely focused on origami designs that expand or contract perpendicular to surfaces, our work aims to explore the potential of spatially efficient origami patterns that deform parallel to the surface. In this context, we investigate the thermal management capabilities of the Kresling origami pattern, shown in Fig. 1(b). Specifically, we aim to understand the heat transfer mechanisms of deployable fin structures made of conductive metals and shaped as a truss-based Kresling pattern.

To evaluate the thermal performance of Kresling origami, we developed an experimental setup and a computational model. Experimentally, the Kresling origami was subjected to controlled heating and forced convection in a wind tunnel, in order to assess its heat transfer capabilities. Additionally, we constructed a high-fidelity computational model to simulate the experimental conditions and gain deeper insights into the mechanisms governing heat dissipation in this complex structure.

The paper is structured as follows. In Section 2, we describe the experimental setup, detailing

Figure 2: Truss based Kresling origami used in this study. (a) Expanded configuration, and (b) contracted configuration.

the design of the origami, and the configuration used to evaluate the thermal performance of the structure. Section 3 presents the development of the computational model, including governing equations, boundary conditions, and numerical approach. Section 4 discusses model validation and heat transfer characteristics of Kresling origami. Finally, Section 5 offers conclusions and outlines potential directions for future work.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The Kresling origami fins structure are generally made of aluminum and brass due to their high thermal conductivity light weight. The structure consists of two (top and bottom) hexagonal aluminum plates (fins) connected through rigid bars (i.e. linkages), as shown in Fig. 2. The ends of each linkage rest on one ball socket joint, which is, in turn, attached to the aluminum plates. Spring joints are added at the center of the outer linkages to allow deployment of the structure upon applying a load (axial or torsional) at the end plates. The design parameters of the structure are carefully chosen such that it can maintain two stable configurations: a fully expanded and a fully contracted position, as shown in Fig. 2[13].

The Kresling structure is integrated to an experiment setup to investigate its thermal management capabilities as depicted in Fig. 3. The system consists of a heater with a constant heat flux, housed within an aluminum cylindrical enclosure. The origami structure is positioned such that the aluminum plates can slide along the surface of the enclosure as the Kresling structure is deployed into one of its stable configurations. The heater, centrally located to promote uniform thermal distribution, is controlled via a variable step-down transformer to regulate the heat flux. Temperature measurements are recorded using thermistors placed at key locations on the surface of the enclosure to capture relevant thermal variations. The experiments are conducted in an open-ended suction-type wind tunnel with a cross-sectional area of 0.5 m x 0.65 m and a test section length of 1 m. To ensure uniform airflow, a honeycomb structure is installed at the inlet. Air velocity measurements are obtained using a hot-wire anemometer. This configuration of controlled heating and forced convection enables a systematic

Figure 3: a) Experimental setup inside the wind tunnel and b) schematic illustration.

evaluation of the heat management of the origami structure under varying thermal conditions.

3 COMPUTATIONAL MODEL

A three dimensional mathematical model is developed to investigate the thermal performance of a Kresling origami structure. The governing equations and boundary conditions are set following the experimental setup discussed in the previous section. The computational domain consists of both solid and fluid media, as illustrated in Fig. 4. The entire computational domain is shown in Fig. 4(a). The solid domain includes the origami linkages, the support plates, the aluminum enclosure, and the heater as displayed in Fig. 4(b). The fluid domain comprises air which passes through these solid structures.

Figure 4: (a) Entire computational domain replicating the experimental setup, and (b) illustration of solid structure inside the computational domain.

3.1 Solid domain

Heat conduction in the solid domain is governed by the transient energy equation:

$$\rho_s c_{p,s} \frac{\partial T_s}{\partial t} = \nabla \cdot (k_s \nabla T_s) + Q_s \quad (1)$$

where ρ_s , $c_{p,s}$, and k_s denote the density, specific heat capacity, and thermal conductivity of the solid, respectively. T_s is the temperature in the solid domain, and Q_s represents the heat source term.

3.2 Fluid domain

The air in the fluid domain is modeled using the conservation equations of mass, momentum, and energy, as follows.

$$\frac{\partial \rho_a}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho_a \mathbf{v}_a) = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$\rho_a \frac{\partial \mathbf{v}_a}{\partial t} + \rho_a (\mathbf{v}_a \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{v}_a = -\nabla p_a + \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau} \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{v} is the velocity vector, p is the pressure, $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ is the stress tensor due to viscous forces, and subscript a denotes the material properties of air such that.

$$\rho_a c_{p,a} \left(\frac{\partial T_a}{\partial t} + \mathbf{v}_a \cdot \nabla T_a \right) = \nabla \cdot (k_a \nabla T_a) \quad (4)$$

where T_a is the air temperature.

Since the Reynolds number is greater than 10^4 , indicating a turbulent flow, we used the Transition SST (Shear Stress Transport) turbulence model [14].

3.3 Boundary conditions

The model incorporates several boundary conditions to accurately model the airflow and thermal interactions in the system. These boundary conditions are applied as follows:

At the inlet, an air velocity of 8 m/s is imposed along with a specified temperature of 25.5°C. The velocity and temperature boundary conditions are given by:

$$v_{\text{inlet}} = 8 \text{ m/s}, \quad T_{\text{inlet}} = 25.5^\circ\text{C}, \quad (5)$$

where v_{inlet} is the velocity magnitude normal to the inlet boundary, and T_{inlet} is the specified inlet temperature to the wind tunnel.

The boundary conditions at the outlet are given as:

$$p_{\text{outlet}} = 0, \quad \nabla T \cdot \mathbf{n}|_{\text{outlet}} = 0, \quad (6)$$

where p_{outlet} is the gauge pressure and \mathbf{n} is a normal vector to a boundary.

At the interface where the solid structures interact with the airflow, no-slip conditions are enforced. This is expressed as:

$$\mathbf{v}_a = 0. \quad (7)$$

Additionally, to ensure heat continuity, thermal coupling between the solid and the air is set as:

$$T_s = T_a, \quad k_s \frac{\partial T_s}{\partial n} = k_a \frac{\partial T_a}{\partial n} \quad (8)$$

At the far boundary, the fluid is assumed to move with the same velocity as the inlet velocity, and a zero temperature gradient normal to the boundary is imposed to prevent artificial heat accumulation or loss. These conditions are described by:

$$\mathbf{v}_{\text{far}} = \mathbf{v}_{\text{inlet}}, \quad \left. \frac{\partial T}{\partial n} \right|_{\text{far}} = 0 \quad (9)$$

where \mathbf{v}_{far} is the velocity vector at the far boundary and $\left. \frac{\partial T}{\partial n} \right|_{\text{far}}$ is the normal temperature gradient.

3.4 Numerical methods

The computational domain and mesh were generated using ANSYS Workbench 18.1. A detailed geometry was constructed to capture the complex structure of the origami-based system, which includes both solid and fluid domains. The mesh was refined in critical regions, particularly within the narrow air gaps between origami members, to ensure accurate resolution of temperature and velocity gradients.

Model computation of the governing equations, along with the boundary and initial conditions, was performed using ANSYS Fluent. The fluid domain, composed of more than 1×10^7 cells, allowed for a fine resolution of the buoyancy-driven air flow. A mesh independence study was conducted by varying the total number of cells.

The transient simulations were run for a sufficient number of time steps to capture the steady-state behavior of the system, ensuring the convergence of both thermal and fluid flow fields. The time step was gradually increased from 0.1 s to 6 s to maintain solution stability during the initial stages of the simulation, allowing the model to adapt to the transient behavior of the system. The residuals for convergence were set at 1×10^{-4} for all variables, except for the energy equation, where a stricter convergence criterion of 1×10^{-8} was applied to ensure accurate temperature

4 RESULTS

Before analyzing the thermal management performance, it is essential to validate that our computational model accurately reproduces the experimental results. Following this validation, we proceed to analyze the thermal response of the Kresling origami in both expanded and contracted configurations.

4.1 Model validation

The computational model was validated against the experiments for two cases; namely a bare enclosure and an origami in the fully expanded configurations. In both the experiments and the computation, the velocity is set to 8 m/s, and the initial room temperature is set to 313 K. A constant heat flux of 16 Watts is maintained at the center of the enclosure. The temperature field in experimental measurements and numerical model were allowed to develop until reaching a steady state. Fig. 5 shows the time history of the temperature difference between the enclosure and inlet temperature, ΔT , against the experimental observations. It can be clearly seen that the two cases demonstrate a strong

agreement between the computational results and the experimental data. Nevertheless, the results of the base case with no fin is less accurate, possibly due to the noise heat of the structural support in the experiment. Introducing origami structure may have increased the heat transfer rate from the enclosure container; consequently, the effect of noise heat becomes lower, and the mathematical results match within less than 5% of experimental measurements.

Figure 5: Model validation against experimental measurements with respect to the temperature difference between the container and inlet temperature, ΔT , for two cases: a) only heater without fins and b) adding support plates with expanded origami members.

4.2 Discussion and analysis

The validated computational model is now employed to understand the thermal characteristics of the Kresling origami as a deployable fin over a heated body. The cooling ability of origami fins is a critical design criteria to justify its application in thermal management systems. Accordingly, the temperature of the heated body is monitored with respect to the inlet temperature for four different cases: 1) mere enclosure, 2) top and bottom support plates without origami linkages, 3) enclosure covered by expanded Kresling origami configuration, and finally 4) enclosure covered by contracted Kresling origami configuration. Thermal performance of all cases are compared at transient and steady states in Fig. 6.

The transient period where the temperature regime is developing is shorter in the presence of fins due to their faster heat transfer rate. In specific, the steady-state temperature is reached within around 15 minutes in the finned scenarios as compared to around 25 minutes with no fins. Thus, introducing fins can speed up the thermal performance by up to 40%. Nonetheless, adding origami members in contracted or expanded states does not seem to affect the duration of the transient period. At steady state, the inclusion of fins significantly reduces the temperature of the heated body, with performance varying based on the fin configuration. Traditional fins without origami members lower the temperature by 24.6%. When the origami linkages are in the expanded configuration, the temperature decreases further by 29.3%. The best cooling performance occurs with the origami members in the contracted configuration, reducing the temperature by 35.1%. Compared to the traditionally finned system, the contracted configuration offers a 14.1% improvement over the expanded configuration. This enhanced cooling is due to the closer proximity of the origami members to the heated body in the contracted state, which increases convective heat transfer, as well as direct contact at the middle of the origami members thereby enhancing heat conduction.

Figure 6: Cooling performance of the heated body in various cases, where ΔT is the difference between the container surface temperature and air inlet temperature.

The contribution of combined conductive and convective heat transfer rate due to origami members can be further investigated. Since heat radiation is insignificant in this study, the total heat transfer rate away from the heated body can be expressed as

$$\dot{Q}_{total} = \dot{Q}_{conduction} + \dot{Q}_{convection} \quad (10)$$

The combined conductive and convective heat transfer from the support plates reduces the temperature of the heated body by 24.6%, as previously discussed. The additional cooling resulting from the origami linkages is primarily due to the enhanced convective heat transfer across these members. In the expanded configuration, convective heat transfer contributes to an additional 4.8% reduction in temperature. Notably, this percentage doubles to approximately 10.5% in the contracted configuration.

Overall, Kresling origami structures have shown excellent heat extraction capabilities. Compared to conventional fins, these origami configurations improve thermal performance by enhancing convective and conductive heat transfer mechanisms. Although this study focuses on the thermal behavior of Kresling origami, it is important to highlight their deployability. This characteristic makes them a promising solution for thermal management. For example, these Kresling structure can be operated passively or actively for thermal management of batteries, solar panels, and other electronic devices. Future work will focus on real-time analysis of thermal management applications.

5 CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates the significant potential of Kresling origami structures as deployable heat fins for advanced thermal management. Both experimental and numerical methods were conducted. The experiment comprises a wind-tunnel which houses origami members over a heated element. The numerical model was derived based on the conservation principles of mass, momentum, and energy, and then validated within 5% against experimental measurements. The model was then employed to analyze the thermal performance of these origami structures under varying configurations. The following findings are observed:

- Incorporating Kresling origami fins greatly enhances cooling efficiency, lowering the temperature

of the heated body by up to 35.1% compared to a finless system, and by 14.1% when compared to conventionally finned systems.

- Combined convective and conductive heat transfer rate attributed to contracted origami configuration is almost double that of expanded origami configurations.

In conclusion, the research demonstrates that Kresling origami structures can provide adaptable and efficient thermal management by leveraging their reconfigurable geometry. Future research could focus on refining the geometry for specific thermal applications, as well as investigating potential control mechanisms for real-time adjustments based on heat load conditions.

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PIEZOELECTRIC ENERGY HARVESTING FOR LEADLESS PACEMAKERS: THE INVESTIGATION OF PATIENTS' ECGS

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Abstract. This paper investigates the performance of a novel heart piezoelectric energy harvester. Heart-simulating experiments were based on the electrocardiogram (ECG) signals from different patients. The shape of the ECG signal as the heart motion simulation was investigated for the energy harvester performance. Amplitude-normalized ECG signals of five patients were used as input for a vibration shaker while the electrical performance was recorded. The output results, voltage, the number of energy pulses generated, and the width of the generated energy pulses were calculated. Results showed that this novel energy harvester developed 11.40 ± 0.85 V voltage, 26.4 pulses of energy in each heartbeat, and an average pulse width of 0.11 ± 0.03 ms. The results showed that the output performance of different patients is still influential. The study contributes to broadly testing piezoelectric energy harvesters for leadless pacemakers.

Keywords: Piezoelectric, Energy Harvesting, Heart, Leadless Pacemakers, ECG.

1 INTRODUCTION

Self-powered biomedical devices have the potential to revolutionise the field of medicine. The development of miniaturised, self-sustained devices would be a significant achievement, as conventional batteries are bulky, mechanically rigid, and require frequent replacements with complicated procedures or surgery. By eliminating the need for replacement surgeries due to battery depletion, self-powered implants would be more robust and multifunctional for intracardiac implants. Intracardiac leadless pacemakers (ICLP) have emerged as an alternative, reducing some of the risks of complications associated with their predecessors [1]–[3]. However, they also have a limited battery life [4]–[6], which can cause significant issues. Powering pacemakers using heartbeats has drawn some attention previously. A zigzag structure was proposed [7]; however, the dimensions are too large for intracardiac implantation. A cantilevered beam was also proposed for leadless pacemakers [8], but due to the limited length and the low frequency of heartbeats, this design faces significant challenges.

Despite the unsatisfactory power generation of current state-of-the-art energy harvesting concepts, designing, and fabricating novel self-powering ICLPs is vital for cardiovascular treatment. Such a development would significantly impact millions of patients worldwide, reducing the risks of revision surgery-related infections and device endocarditis.

Piezoelectric materials generate an electric potential when mechanically deformed. Since the human body constantly produces enormous amounts of kinetic energy, harvesting this energy through piezoelectricity could revolutionise the medical field. For instance, the heart's 1 W mechanical power [9] can power a leadless pacemaker. Piezoelectric energy harvesting can be achieved by connecting the body's mechanical motion to the piezoelectric material through periodic movements such as blood flow [10], tissue contraction [11], and cardiac/lung motions [12], [13]. However, the practical purpose of piezoelectric energy harvesting is mainly restrained by low energy output performance [14]. The body's kinetic motion is low-frequency [15]–[18], which poses significant challenges to energy conversion efficiency. Therefore, a kinetic body energy harvesting mechanism with substantial efficiency improvement is needed.

This work further investigates a new approach to harvesting body energy inspired by the patent authors have published [19]. The presented novel energy harvester has been reported as a contact-based multi-directional energy generator with a specific design for heart energy harvesting [19]. The understudy energy harvester is robust and can generate sufficient power for the heart's pacing. However, this energy harvester needs extensive validation through experimental tests, long-term tests, and various heart motions from different patients. This study presents a collection of patients' heart motions and studies the piezoelectric energy harvester (PEH) performance under these patients' motions. Piezoelectric outputs are compared at different heart signals by statistical analysis. This study contributes to the validation of a new energy harvester for leadless pacemakers. The developed energy harvester is novel for leadless pacemakers; therefore, this study will pave the way for the application of a new practical energy harvester.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

This section presents the information about the leadless pacemaker, dimensions and operational information as well as the experimental setup of the novel energy harvester [20].

2.1 Leadless pacemaker piezoelectric energy harvesting

The MicraTM (Medtronic, Minneapolis, MN, USA) is a leadless pacemaker, see Figure 1a, with approximately 50% volume occupied by the battery. The leadless pacemaker MicraTM uses 1.3-2.1 μA and 1.5-2.5 V typically, about 6 μW power [21].

The energy harvester comprises two piezoelectric cubes with an inner moving ball to create the contact force in heartbeat motion; see Figure 1b. The performance of this energy harvester in pig model and laboratory heart simulation has been demonstrated [20]. More detailed information about the energy harvester can be found in [20]. The volume of the energy harvester is set to be within the range of MicraTM's battery. The self-powering leadless pacemaker idea is to replace the MicraTM's battery with this energy harvester with a smaller rechargeable battery. The built sample has an AC-to-DC converter since the piezoelectric outputs are AC voltage.

Figure 1: (a) Micra™ (Medtronic, Minneapolis, MN, USA), (b) the proposed energy harvester, which can be embedded in a leadless pacemaker, and (c) an experimental setup for simulating heart motion.

2.2 Experimental heart simulation vibration

Figure 1c shows the experimental setup for the test. A vibration shaker (LDS V201 from Bruel and Kjaer, Virum, Denmark) simulated the kinetic heart motion on the leadless pacemaker PEH. The heart motion was simulated using an (electrocardiogram) ECG heart signal generated by a signal generator, which controlled a compatible amplifier (LPA 100 from Bruel and Kjaer, Virum, Denmark) to power the shaker. The input heart signal had a controlled amplitude.

The kinetic motion shape and amplitude of the human heart provide valuable data for evaluating energy harvester performance. However, obtaining precise data on the heart's motion type and amplitude is challenging. The heart is a complex organ with both electrical and mechanical indices. The ECG, a standard diagnostic tool, measures the electrical activity of the heart. The mechanical kinetic motion of the heart, which refers to the movement of the heart muscles, can provide valuable information about heart function. Electrical and dynamic heart motions exhibit similarities and characteristics that contribute to a comprehensive analysis of heart activities. While ECG signals are well-documented in the literature, the database for heart dynamic motion is limited.

ECG open datasets are widely [22]–[24] ECG signals from five normal-sinus-rhythm patients were obtained from the MIT-BIH Arrhythmia database [23], [24]. Table 1 presents the patients' information and the code to refer to them. The ECG signals have heart rates and different amplitudes, see Figure 2. Each ECG has different segments. Each signal was normalized to its maximum value to obtain the unbiased ECG signals. Figure 2b shows the normalized ECG signals in a 10-second window. The heart rate and heart motion shape are uncontrolled and original from the patients' recordings. Nevertheless, the similarity of all ECG signals is the shock pattern in the ECG signal, demonstrating the sudden motion of the heart in a short period.

The heart acceleration was previously measured in an animal pig model by the authors [25]. These acceleration signals were used to set the amplitude of the ECG signal, ensuring that a comparable acceleration is

applied to the energy harvester. The ECG signals in Figure 2b were fed into the shaker with a controlled amplitude, resulting in a maximum shaker acceleration of approximately 3.5 m/s^2 , similar to [15]. The piezoelectric voltage was then measured over a long period, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Patient information [23], [24]

Patient's code	Gender	Age	Heart Rate ^a (bpm)	Number of ECG parts	Voltage recording time
100	Male	69	79	8	24 minutes
103	Male	NA	141	5	15 minutes
116	Male	68	78	8	24 minutes
209	Male	62	95	9	27 minutes
213	Male	61	111	12	36 minutes

^a Calculated from the Fast Fourier Transform of the ECG signal.

Figure 2: The ECG signals of five patients, (a) the original signals and (b) normalized amplitude signals in a 10-second window

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Figure 3 shows the open-circuit voltage from the excitation signal of patient #100, along with a zoomed-in view. For simplicity, the voltage output is shown in Figure 3 from the four first four segments of the ECG segments. The zoomed-in view highlights the multiple energy pulses generated in each heartbeat. The plot displays four distinct signal parts with varying voltage amplitudes over time. The peak open-circuit voltage amplitude ranges between 10-12 V. The zoomed-in view reveals multiple power pulse generations.

Figure 3: The piezoelectric voltage output from excitation signals of patient #100 and the zoomed-in view of the voltage.

Furthermore, Figure 4 shows the voltage output for the patients #103, #116, #209, and #213. The plot limits of the recorded voltage plot in Figure 3 and Figure 4 were reduced for the demonstration easiness. Comparing the voltage output from these five patients' output voltage, there were scatters in the voltage output peak between different patients. These scatters also could be found within different segments of one patient ECG. Nonetheless, the scatter was not substantial.

Figure 4: The piezoelectric voltage outputs from patients #103, #116, #209, and #213 excitation signals.

Due to pulse power generation, the average of peak voltages is also reported. The average peak voltage generated for different patients is plotted in Figure 5. The voltage of each patient during the ECG segments shows discrepancies. The energy generation from the patient can be time-variable. The statistical analysis for each patient indicates a 5.0% to 14.6% variation in voltage peaks. As the average voltage for the five patients,

the voltage output average is 11.4 V, and the scatter is 7.5% of the average value.

Figure 5: The maximum piezoelectric voltage results for the five studied ECGs are (a) the pulse maximum voltage at different ECG segments, (b) the peak voltages among patients, and (c) the overall peak voltage for all patients.

The number of energy pulses for each patient is individually shown in Figure 6. On average, each heartbeat led to the generation of approximately 26 pulses. The variation in the number of pulses is 18.6%, higher than the voltage peak values. The number of pulses is more affected by the randomness of the contact force. Therefore, it is expected that the number of pulses varies more substantially. The minimum number of pulses was eight for patient #213.

The pulse width of energy pulses is another critical parameter studied for different patients' ECG signals. See Figure 7. The average pulse width is 0.10 ms for the most vital generated pulse in each heartbeat, with a variation of 33.3%. The different patients substantially affect the pulse width but have a minimum pulse width of 0.07 ms.

Figure 6: The number of piezoelectric energy pulses in each heartbeat for the five studied ECGs, (a) the pulse numbers at different ECG segments, (b) the pulse numbers among patients, and (c) the overall pulse numbers for all patients.

Figure 7: The piezoelectric energy pulse width for the five studied ECGs, (a) the energy pulse width at different ECG segments, (b) the energy pulse width among patients, and (c) the overall energy pulse width for all patients.

The previously reported values were open-circuit voltages. A resistive load test is carried out to estimate the power. Figure 8 shows the electrical performance of the energy harvester in one heartbeat. The voltage and current are separately measured. Power is the product of voltage and current. Multiple pulses of energy are

produced in one heartbeat during 0.1 seconds, as seen in **Figure 8**. The power output has ten distinct pulses, with a maximum of $389 \mu\text{W}$. This power output is considerably higher than the $6 \mu\text{W}$ requirement for Micra™.

Figure 8: The piezoelectric energy harvester's voltage, current, and power output with a resistance load connection ($8.3 \text{ k}\Omega$).

4 CONCLUSIONS

This paper presented the energy generation performance of the heart's kinetic motion for the self-powering of leadless pacemakers. The investigated prospects included the kinetic motion simulation of five patients from ECG signals. The authors recently published a patent on high-efficiency piezoelectric harvesters, demonstrating excellent performance. The performance of this energy harvester has been investigated using different shapes of ECG signals from patients. While variations in output performance were inevitable due to the time-variable nature of heart kinetic motion and randomness, the generated energy from the heart's kinetic motion was satisfactory. For these five patients, over 10 V of voltage, 24 pulses of energy, and a pulse width of 0.1 ms were estimated. Our team is exploring a more comprehensive range of testing and exciting aspects of this innovative idea in self-powering medical devices.

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AEROELASTIC BEHAVIOR OF A PIEZOELECTRIC ENERGY HARVESTING FLAG UNDER WIND EXCITATION

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Abstract. This study aims to advance the understanding of alternative energy sources by exploring flag-based flutter energy harvesters. A smart piezoelectric flag equipped with an MFC patch on a steel substrate is designed and subjected to experimental aeroelastic and energy harvesting analyses under various inflow conditions. The research reveals that under streamlined flow, flutter occurs at higher flow speeds, but can be induced at lower speeds if subcriticality is effectively triggered, thus potentially enhancing energy harvesting at reduced flow speeds. Conversely, under vortex-induced excitation, the flag demonstrates limited energy harvesting potential at smaller gap distances from the upstream bluff body. However, larger gap distances facilitate energy capture at lower flow speeds. The study examines the impact of bluff body diameter on the performance of the piezoelectric flags using cylinder A (2 cm diameter) and cylinder B (3 cm diameter). Results indicate that while cylinder A results in reduced energy harvesting efficiency, cylinder B significantly enhances it. Overall, this study identifies the optimal conditions for maximizing energy harvesting from aeroelastic flutter, considering the combined effects of flag positioning, flow characteristics, bluff body shape, and wind speed. To the best of our knowledge, a hand in hand analysis of these parameters has not been explored in the hitherto literature.

Keywords: Piezoelectric energy harvesting; Subcritical bifurcations; Flutter; MFC; Wind tunnel tests.

1 INTRODUCTION

The growing demand for clean and sustainable energy has led to increased interest in alternative energy solutions [1, 2, 3, 4]. Aeroelastic instabilities, arising from nonlinear fluid-structure interactions, have shown promise as a viable method for energy harvesting [2, 5]. For optimal performance in urban environments, these energy harvesters must capitalize on the in-field aerodynamic conditions to manifest sustained oscillations even at low wind speeds. Therefore, the design of aeroelastic energy harvesters requires a careful balance between lightweight, flexible structures and the durability

necessary to maintain limit cycle oscillations (LCOs) over prolonged periods, ensuring efficient energy harvesting.

Lightweight aeroelastic structures, such as flags [3, 6, 4] or leaf stalks [7, 1, 8], are often used in energy harvester designs. These harvesters are typically examined under either streamlined airflow or vortex-induced flow, the latter occurring when placed downstream of a bluff body that disrupts the airflow. The performance of the harvesters depends upon several factors, including the shape of the flag [1], inflow characteristics, alignment with the flow direction [9], and the distance from the bluff body in vortex-induced inflow conditions [4]. Triangular shapes often exhibit greater instability and power output compared to other shapes [1]. In scenarios involving the vortex-induced inflow, gap distance (G) between the flag and the bluff body is a critical parameter, which not only governs the flag’s aeroelastic behaviour, but also affects the vortex formation mechanism [10]. It is also observed that the shape of the bluff body can have a significant impact on the power output from the harvester [11, 4]. Therefore, efficient energy harvesting from flag flutter in various inflow conditions is a complex multiphysics problem that requires a comprehensive understanding of how multiple parameters interact and influence aeroelastic behaviour as well as the energy harvesting efficiency. This motivates a detailed analysis of energy harvesting performance for a highly flexible piezoelectric flag under varying system parameters. To that end, we propose a smart flag design capable of sustaining oscillations under both streamlined and vortex-induced flows. Aeroelastic and energy harvesting analyses are subsequently conducted on a steel piezoelectric flag equipped with a triangular appendage, subjected to these flow conditions. We investigate various parameters, including bluff body shape, gap distance, and flow speed regimes, to identify effective design conditions for energy harvesting. The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 describes the experimental methodology, Section 3 presents the results and discussion, and Section 4 concludes the study.

2 EXPERIMENTAL METHODOLOGY

The energy harvesting experiments are carried out in the test section (dimensions $0.75 \text{ m} \times 0.9 \text{ m} \times 1.8 \text{ m}$) of a low-speed wind tunnel at the Aeronautics Laboratory, American University of Sharjah. The suction side of the wind tunnel features a honeycomb mesh, ensuring streamlined flow with the turbulence intensity below 1%. A photograph of test section is shown in Fig. 1(a), with data acquisition in Fig. 1(b). The experimental setup includes a triangular steel flag mounted on a metallic platform (Fig. 1(c)). The flag design features a flexible steel beam supporting a triangular flag, with hinges at its free ends. For vortex-induced motion experiments, two different cylindrical bluff bodies with diameters of 2 cm and 3 cm are used upstream of the flag, referred to as cylinder A and cylinder B, respectively, for brevity. Natural frequencies are determined through eigenvalue analysis using *COMSOL Multiphysics*. For the flag beam, the natural frequencies are found to be 3.23 Hz for the first bending mode and 15.96 Hz for the first torsional mode. The properties of different structures used in the experiments are detailed in Table 1.

During the onset of flutter, the triangular flag remains rigid and oscillates about the hinges while the beam undergoes bending deformation. A laser displacement sensor (*Baumer OM70-11112065*) connected to an oscilloscope measures the flag’s bending deflection (y) at the beam’s center (see Fig. 1). Torsional deflections are negligible and not recorded. The energy from the flag flutter is harvested using a MFC patch (*M8528-P2* with d31 effect) with a net active area of $85 \times 28 \text{ mm}^2$, attached at the base of the flag beam. The voltage output from this piezoelectric flag, for all the

Figure 1: Experimental setup: (a) photograph of the test section with piezoelectric flag behind bluff body, (b) data acquisition, and (c) schematic of the experimental setup.

Table 1: Specifications of the structures employed in the experiments.

Shape	Dimensions (width or base / height / thickness)
Beam	2 cm / 20 cm / 0.3 mm
Triangular flag	8 cm / 8 cm / 0.3 mm
Cylindrical bluff body A	2 cm (dia.) / 22 cm / 1 mm
Cylindrical bluff body B	3 cm (dia.) / 22 cm / 1 mm

experiments, are obtained across a load resistance of $R = 0.2 \text{ M}\Omega$ and recorded in a PicoScope (see Fig. 1(b)). The average power output from the piezoelectric flag is calculated as $P_{avg} = V_{rms}^2/R$, where V_{rms} is the root mean square voltage. Flow speed (U) is measured using a Vernier anemometer connected to a data acquisition system. All the experiments are performed within the range $U = 0 - 9.0 \text{ m/s}$.

Measurements at two points near the flag, using simultaneous anemometers, show a flow speed difference within $\pm 0.3 \text{ m/s}$ across a range of 0 to 12.0 m/s, indicating high measurement accuracy. To evaluate the uncertainty in aeroelastic response analysis, five flag flutter tests are performed for a gap distance $G = 3d$ behind the 3 cm diameter cylindrical bluff body. The bending, flutter frequency and voltage output responses from these trials are shown in Fig. 2. The mean, standard deviation and coefficient of variance of the test data is listed in Table 2. Overall, the analysis demonstrates the

Table 2: Uncertainty analysis of the test data (Std - Standard deviation, CoV - Coefficient of variance).

Response	Mean	Std	CoV
Voltage	2.44 V	0.11 V	4.34%
Bending amplitude	15.02 mm	1.16 mm	7.69%
Flutter speed	7.7 m/s	0.08 m/s	1.04%
Flutter frequency	3.524 Hz	0.03 Hz	0.83%

Figure 2: Uncertainty quantification of test data: (a) Bending amplitude, (b) Voltage, and (c) Flutter frequency, obtained from five trials

robustness of the data measurement.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Energy harvesting under streamlined flow is analyzed first, by exposing the piezoelectric flag directly to the inflow from the suction side. The experiment is conducted in a forward sweep, increasing the flow speed up to 9.0 m/s, followed by a backward sweep. This method aims to identify any hysteresis in the system response, which indicates subcritical behavior. During the forward sweep (see Fig. 3(a)), flutter onset occurs at approximately $U = 8.7$ m/s, LCOs at a frequency of 3.81 Hz. The average power output from the piezoelectric flag at this speed is $78.41 \mu\text{W}$, remaining nearly constant as the flow speed increases to 9.0 m/s. In the backward sweep (see Fig. 3(b)), LCOs are observed at lower speeds, suggesting potential for energy harvesting at reduced speeds if subcritical conditions are present. The maximum average power output of $86.94 \mu\text{W}$ is recorded at $U = 8.4$ m/s. At $U = 6.2$ m/s, the power output is less than half of the maximum value. LCOs persist down to $U = 5.0$ m/s, but power output is very low below $U = 6.1$ m/s.

Next, the experiments are performed under vortex-induced motion by placing the piezoelectric flag behind either of the cylinders (A or B), at various G values. The flag does not exhibit flutter even at the maximum tested flow speeds ($U = 9.0$ m/s), when very closely placed behind either of the bluff body ($G = 0.5d$). In this case, very small amplitude random oscillations are observed in the flag below 2 mm amplitudes and can not be utilized for the energy harvesting. Even for a higher gap value $G = 3d$, the flag exhibits flutter only under the wake of cylinder B, that too only at $U = 9.0$ m/s. The V_{rms} obtained for this case is 4.16 V, accounting for a $86.32 \mu\text{W}$ power output. At $G = 6d$, flutter is recorded for both the cases. Using cylinder A, the flag undergoes flutter near $U = 8.4$ m/s with a power output of $26.45 \mu\text{W}$. While for cylinder B, the flutter is observed near $U = 7.0$ m/s with a power output of $28.58 \mu\text{W}$ - indicating a similar energy output at almost 20% lesser flow speeds.

Experiments are further continued for increasing the gap between the flag and bluff body. For $G = 9d$, flutter speed is reduced for both the cylinders, enabling the energy harvesting to be possible at lower speeds. For cylinder A, flutter speed is observed near $U = 8.0$ m/s with a $35.11 \mu\text{W}$ power output. For cylinder B, the flutter speed is much lower, close to $U = 6.8$ m/s. The energy output

Figure 3: Responses of piezoelectric flag under streamlined flow (WBB - without bluff body).

is $46.18 \mu W$ - means approximately 31% higher power can be extracted at 18% lower flow speed by replacing the cylinder A with B. For the farthest location of the flag behind the bluff body, *i.e.* $G = 12d$, flutter speed of the flag is reduced close to $U = 7.5$ m/s for cylinder A and $U = 6.2$ m/s for cylinder B. The power output near flutter speed is observed as $25.20 \mu W$ and $10.62 \mu W$, for cylinder A and cylinder B, respectively.

A comparison of the aeroelastic (bending) responses and output voltage responses from the piezoelectric flag for all the test cases at $U = 9.0$ m/s is shown in Fig. 4. The maximum bending deflection (y_{max}) for the case without bluff body (WBB) upstream of flag, *i.e.*, under streamlined inflow conditions, is 23.09 mm with a V_{rms} of 3.97 V (Fig. 4(a)). Under the vortex-induced motion from cylinder A, the y_{max} ranges between 13.86 - 19.61 mm across various gap distances, with the V_{rms} ranging between 3.42 - 3.79 V (Fig. 4(b)-(d)). Hence, for any G value, energy harvesting could not be enhanced using the cylinder A. Nonetheless, the flutter can be achieved at a lower flow velocity, shifting from $U = 8.7$ m/s in the WBB forward sweep case to $U = 7.5$ m/s at $G = 12d$ with cylinder A. The y_{max} and V_{rms} responses are significantly higher when the cylinder A is replaced with the cylinder B (Fig. 4(e)-(h)). In this case, the y_{max} ranges between 18.15 - 24.18 mm and V_{rms} ranges between 3.85 - 5.06 V. Here the maximum V_{rms} of 5.06 V is observed among all test cases at $G = 9d$ corresponding to highest y_{max} (24.18 mm) as well (Fig. 4(g)). Its also worth mentioning that, the flutter speeds are reduced up to $U = 6.2$ m/s (at $G = 12d$) using the cylinder B.

Figure 4: Comparison of aeroelastic responses and voltage output for different experimental configurations at $U = 9.0$ m/s (WBB - without bluff body).

Figure 5 provides a comparative analysis of the power output across different energy harvester configurations, as well as various flow speeds and gap distances. It is evident that the highest power output is achieved with cylinder B within the velocity range of $U = 7.7 - 9.0$ m/s. This is followed by the power output from the backward sweep in the streamlined flow case. However, the energy harvesting potential in the backward sweep scenario remains uncertain, as it is subject to the triggering of subcriticality. In contrast, cylinder A consistently demonstrates a lower power output, particularly at gap distances between $G = 6d$ and $G = 9d$, highlighting its comparatively lower efficiency relative to cylinder B and streamlined flow. A summary of the operational flow speed ranges for various test configurations, along with the corresponding maximum average power extracted from these configurations within their respective operational ranges, is presented in Table 3.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, we investigated the effect of different flow conditions, bluff body shapes and relative position of flag and bluff body on the energy harvesting performance of a piezoelectric flag. The salient findings from the study can be summarized as follows:

- Under streamlined flow conditions, the system exhibited subcritical bifurcation behavior. By appropriately triggering this subcriticality, the system has the potential to harvest significant energy at reduced flow speeds regimes.

Figure 5: Power output with different configurations of energy harvesting system (WBB - without bluff body).

Table 3: Operational range and maximum power for different configurations tested.

Configuration	Operational Range		Maximum Average Power	
	Forward	Backward	Forward	Backward
WBB	8.7 - 9.0 m/s	6.1 - 9.0 m/s	78.8 μW	86.94 μW
	Cylinder A	Cylinder B	Cylinder A	Cylinder B
$G = 3d$	-	9.0 m/s	-	86.53 μW
$G = 6d$	8.4 - 9.0 m/s	7.0 - 9.0 m/s	58.48 μW	75.66 μW
$G = 9d$	8.0 - 9.0 m/s	6.8 - 9.0 m/s	71.82 μW	128.02 μW
$G = 12d$	7.5 - 9.0 m/s	6.2 - 9.0 m/s	59.17 μW	74.11 μW

- Energy harvesting using an upstream bluff body to induce vortex motion was found more effective at larger gap values between the piezoelectric flag and the cylinder. Reducing the gap below a certain threshold stabilizes the flag, likely due to feedback effects that alter the wake structure [10].
- Placing cylinder A (2 cm diameter) upstream of the piezoelectric flag reduced the flutter speed compared to the forward sweep under streamlined flow, but resulted in a lower overall power output.
- Cylinder B (3 cm diameter), on the other hand, enhanced the performance of the piezoelectric flag, yielding the highest power output in specific regimes, across all test cases.

Overall, the study presented various configurations aimed at enhancing the energy harvesting from aeroelastic flutter of a piezoelectric flag. The findings highlight the potential for maximizing energy capture, particularly at lower flow speeds. The proposed energy harvesting system can be effectively

integrated in urban settings such as building rooftops, roadside installations, drones, or coastal areas, operating effectively across a range of inflow conditions. Note that, the current analysis is limited to a specific piezoelectric circuit configuration and could be expanded to explore alternative piezoelectric materials and load resistances. Future research could also investigate different bluff body geometries, flag designs, and flow conditions to strategically enhance the energy harvester designs for real-world applications.

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GLOBAL SENSITIVITY AND UNCERTAINTY ANALYSIS OF ASYMMETRIC BISTABLE ENERGY HARVESTERS

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Abstract. This study investigates the performance of asymmetric bistable energy harvesters with nonlinear piezoelectric coupling, focusing on the impact of parametric variability on system reliability. Global sensitivity analysis using Sobol indices identifies critical parameters influencing harvested power, providing insights for the robust design of nonlinear harvesters. To address uncertainties in system parameters, we employ a probabilistic framework incorporating Polynomial Chaos Expansion (PCE) and probabilistic maps. This approach, leveraging the maximum entropy principle, models and propagates uncertainties to visualize their effects on power output. Results show that excitation frequency, amplitude, asymmetric terms, and piezoelectric coupling properties are critical factors, with their importance varying across dynamic stability regimes. Our findings highlight the need to account for joint parameter variability to enhance energy harvesting system efficiency and reliability.

Keywords: Energy harvesting; Nonlinear dynamics; Asymmetric system; Sensitivity analysis; Sobol' indices; Uncertainty quantification

1 INTRODUCTION

Energy harvesting from environmental vibrations has gained significant attention as a means to power autonomous devices. Among the various energy harvesting mechanisms, bistable systems have shown enhanced performance due to their ability to exploit nonlinearities, thereby increasing energy capture across a broad frequency range [1, 2, 3]. However, such systems are highly sensitive to parametric uncertainties and geometric imperfections, which can affect their performance and reliability [4].

This study focuses on the global sensitivity analysis (GSA) and uncertainty quantification (UQ) of an asymmetric bistable energy harvester with nonlinear piezoelectric coupling [5, 6]. The sensitivity analysis approach employs Sobol indices, computed via Polynomial Chaos Expansion (PCE), to quantify the influence of each parameter on the harvested power, providing a basis for optimizing harvester design under uncertainty.

But while GSA provides valuable insights, it does not explain how these parameters affect power harvesting under uncertainty. To address this gap, this paper integrates a parametric probabilistic approach [7] to model and quantify these impacts, providing a more comprehensive understanding of how uncertainties affect the system response.

2 MATHEMATICAL MODELING

The asymmetric bistable energy harvester under consideration, Figure 1, is modeled by the following set of nonlinear differential equations:

$$\ddot{x} + 2\xi\dot{x} - \frac{1}{2}x(1-x^2) - (1 + \beta|x|)\chi v = f \cos(\Omega t) + p \sin \phi, \quad (1)$$

$$\dot{v} + \lambda v + (1 + \beta|x|)\kappa \dot{x} = 0, \quad (2)$$

where x denotes the beam tip displacement, v is the voltage across the resistive circuit, ξ represents the damping ratio, χ and κ are piezoelectric coupling coefficients, λ is a time constant, f is the excitation amplitude, Ω is the excitation frequency, ϕ is the bias angle, and β characterizes the nonlinear piezoelectric coupling.

Figure 1: Asymmetric bistable energy harvester with nonlinear piezoelectric coupling.

The quantity of interest (QoI) is the mean output power, given by

$$P = \frac{1}{T} \int_{t_0}^{t_0+T} \lambda v(t)^2 dt. \quad (3)$$

To model the parametric uncertainties, we employ a probabilistic approach based on the maximum entropy principle, which ensures the least biased estimation for the probability distributions given the limited information available. Since the only known information for the random variables (such as excitation frequency, amplitude, and material properties) is their range of possible values (support), the maximum entropy principle yields uniform distributions for each parameter. These distributions are assumed to be independent and identically distributed (i.i.d.) due to the lack of any known correlations between the parameters.

The propagation of uncertainties through the system is performed using a Monte Carlo simulation [8], which is efficiently approximated by a PCE surrogate model. The PCE provides an accurate and computationally efficient way to estimate the system’s response to random variations in parameters, enabling a comprehensive analysis of the effects of uncertainty on power output.

Sobol indices are employed for global sensitivity analysis to quantify the contribution of each input parameter to the variance of the model output. Rather than using a direct Monte Carlo simulation, which can be computationally expensive, we compute these indices more efficiently through PCE. PCE expresses the model output as a series of orthogonal polynomials in terms of the input random variables, with each polynomial term having an associated coefficient that indicates its contribution to the output. The Sobol indices are then directly derived from these PCE coefficients. The first-order Sobol index, which measures the variance contribution of a single parameter, is calculated by summing the squared PCE coefficients related to that parameter. Higher-order Sobol indices, which account for the interactions between multiple parameters, are similarly obtained by summing the squared coefficients corresponding to the polynomial terms involving those parameters. This method significantly reduces computational costs by leveraging the PCE surrogate model, which provides an accurate approximation of the original model, facilitating efficient variance decomposition and sensitivity analysis.

All the simulations reported here were done with the package STONEHENGE - Suite for Nonlinear Analysis of Energy Harvesting Systems [9], which has modules for UQ and GSA.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The model parameters analyzed include the damping ratio ($\xi = 0.01$), the electrical coupling constant ($\kappa = 0.5$), the time constant reciprocal ($\lambda = 0.05$), the nonlinear coupling coefficient ($\beta = 1$), the quadratic nonlinearity coefficient ($\delta = 0.15$), and the excitation frequency ($\Omega = 0.8$). The bias angle (ϕ) was set to 10° , while the excitation amplitude (f) is varied to explore different types of dynamic oscillations such as intrawell, interwell, and chaotic motions. The adopted initial condition is $(x_0, \dot{x}_0, v_0) = (1, 0, 0)$.

3.1 Key sensitivity findings

Figure 2 illustrates the variation of Sobol indices with respect to the amplitude of excitation for an asymmetric bistable energy harvester model with nonlinear piezoelectric coupling. The Sobol indices indicate the contribution of each input parameter to the variance in harvested power, providing insight into how different parameters affect power output across various excitation amplitudes.

The results reveal that for configurations with high excitation amplitudes, the electrical coupling parameter (κ) predominantly influences power output, particularly in regimes characterized by interwell motion. The excitation frequency (Ω) and amplitude (f) are critical in enhancing power in intrawell and chaotic motion regimes, respectively. Furthermore, for low and medium amplitudes of excitation, the bias angle (ϕ) significantly impact system behavior. These findings underscore the importance of considering parameter interactions to optimize energy harvesting performance. For a deeper analysis of bistable energy harvesting systems with Sobol indices, the reader is referred to [5].

Figure 2: Variation of the Sobol indices with respect to the amplitude of excitation for the asymmetric bistable energy harvester model with nonlinear piezoelectric coupling. The Sobol indices quantify the contribution of each input parameter to the variance in the harvested power, illustrating how different parameters influence power output across various excitation amplitudes.

3.2 Impact of uncertainty quantification

To further explore the influence of parametric variability, we integrated uncertainty quantification methodologies, including the PCE surrogate model, to construct probabilistic maps. These maps, shown in Figure 3, illustrate the conditional probability of increasing the nominal mean power by 50% when each parameter is increased by 10%, plotted against the excitation amplitude for the asymmetric energy harvester model with nonlinear piezoelectric coupling. The maps reveal that the excitation parameters (Ω and f) and the piezoelectric coupling terms (κ and β) are the most sensitive, with significant variability in harvested power across different stability regimes.

The analysis confirms that excitation frequency and amplitude are pivotal in enhancing power in intrawell and chaotic motion regimes, respectively. Meanwhile, piezoelectric coupling parameters play a crucial role in interwell motions. These results demonstrate the importance of understanding parametric uncertainties to achieve robust and optimized designs for nonlinear energy harvesters. For a more comprehensive examination of the uncertainty quantification, the reader is invited to consult [6].

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study provides a robust framework for understanding the effects of uncertainties in bistable energy harvesting systems with nonlinear piezoelectric coupling and geometric asymmetries. The results emphasize the critical role of excitation frequency, amplitude, and piezoelectric properties in determining power output under varying dynamic conditions. These insights can guide the design and optimization of more reliable and efficient energy harvesters [10]. Future research could extend this approach to explore other forms of nonlinearities or consider multi-physics couplings to further enhance the robustness and performance of energy harvesting devices.

Figure 3: Conditional probability of increasing the nominal mean power by 50% as each parameter is increased by 10%, plotted against the excitation amplitude for the asymmetric energy harvester model with nonlinear piezoelectric coupling. The graph highlights the relative importance of each parameter in improving energy harvesting performance under different excitation conditions.

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NUMERICAL EVALUATION OF SHEAR STRENGTH ENHANCEMENT IN RC BEAMS INCORPORATING VARIOUS WEB OPENING CONFIGURATIONS AND PRE-STRESSED FE-SMA BAR SIZES

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Abstract. Web openings in reinforced concrete (RC) beams are commonly required to accommodate utility ducts, pipes, and other service installations, optimizing space utilization and reducing construction costs. However, these openings can severely compromise the structural integrity of beams, mainly by lowering their shear strength, thus necessitating innovative reinforcement techniques to maintain their load-bearing capacity. This study presents a numerical investigation to enhance the shear strength of RC beams with various web opening shapes by integrating pre-stressed Fe-SMA (Iron-based Shape Memory Alloy) bars. The analysis focuses on two key parameters: the shape of the web openings and the diameter of the Fe-SMA bars. Finite element modeling was used to simulate RC beams with rectangular, circular, and diamond-shaped openings, and the impact of different Fe-SMA bar sizes on shear capacity was systematically evaluated. The results demonstrated that the incorporation of pre-stressed Fe-SMA bars significantly enhances the shear strength of RC beams, with the extent of improvement closely tied to both the geometry of the openings and the bar diameter. Under four-point loading, beams with diamond and circular openings exhibited fewer diagonal cracks and greater shear strength than those with square openings, especially when reinforced with larger Fe-SMA bars. Compared to the control beam (without opening), beams with diamond-shaped openings strengthened with 32 mm Fe-SMA bars showed the closest performance with only a 2% reduction in load capacity. In contrast, circular and square-shaped openings resulted in load reductions of 9.4% and 25.6%, respectively. These findings suggest that optimizing both the size of Fe-SMA bars and the shape of web openings is an effective strategy for enhancing the structural performance of RC beams with web openings.

Keywords: RC beams; FE-SMA; Web opening; Pre-stressed; Numerical; Shear strength.

1 INTRODUCTION

Web openings in reinforced concrete (RC) beams are commonly adopted to permit the passage of electrical and mechanical utilities such as pipes and ducts. The presence of web openings in beams eliminates the need for dropped ceilings, which results in an overall decrease in the building's weight and height [1]. This leads to a more efficient and cost-effective design. However, web openings cause significant losses in beams' flexural and shear capacities because they disrupt the flow of stresses, causing stress concentrations around openings. The influence of openings in the flexural and shear zones on beams has been investigated in numerous studies [2], [3]. Web openings in the shear zones can have various sizes and shapes depending on their purpose of use [4]. Shear forces cause diagonal tensile stresses in the shear zone of RC beams [5]. These forces are resisted by concrete struts acting in compression and shear reinforcement acting in tension [6]. Introducing openings in the shear zone reduces the amount of concrete, which results in insufficient strength to resist shear forces. Openings result in high stress concentrations around openings, with the opening shape and size influencing the amount of stress

concentration [7]. Stress concentrations around openings cause significant reductions in the ultimate strength, shear capacity, and rigidity of beams [8].

Studies reported that openings in the shear zone diminish the load-carrying capacity of RC beams more than openings in the flexure zone [9]–[12]. Introducing openings near the supports changes the beam behavior from shear-controlled to flexure-controlled due to insufficient material in the diagonal compression strut [13]. This leads to premature failures, such as web compression failure. Alsheikh et al. [11] investigated the influence of opening locations on the load-carrying capacity of beams. Results showed that circular openings located at the midspan reduce the load-carrying capacity by 5%, while openings near the supports cause a significant reduction of around 25%. Another study by Jasim et al. [14] found that openings near the supports reduce the ultimate load capacity and torque by 45% and 43.8%, compared to openings located in the midspan. Openings in near supports interrupt the interaction between moment and shear, substantially reducing the load-carrying capacity. The closer the openings to supports, the higher the impact on moment and shear [15], [16].

The structural behavior of beams with openings is influenced by the shear span-to-depth ratio, opening size and location, and tension reinforcement ratio [9]. Beams can preserve their elastic and plastic deformations if the opening size is small. Ame et al. [17] reported that circular openings with a diameter less than 40% of the beam effective depth do not significantly influence ultimate load capacity or first cracking. Another study by Mwonga et al. [7] examined the influence of square opening sizes on the behavior of beams. Results showed square openings exceeding 25% of the overall beam depth cause significant deflections and cracking. This indicates that square openings cause higher stress concentrations than circular openings, especially at the corners.

Reinforcing beam openings is necessary to prevent premature failures. Many researchers explored various materials and techniques to strengthen openings. Fiber-reinforced polymers (FRP) and shape memory alloys (SMA) are commonly used to strengthen openings due to their remarkable characteristics. Rahim et al. [18] investigated the effectiveness of carbon fiber-reinforced polymer (CFRP) sheets in strengthening beam openings in the shear zone. Results showed that the thickness of CFRP sheets needed to strengthen openings mainly depends on the beam-to-depth ratio. The effective number of CFRP layers for deep beams having opening diameters of 150 mm and 200 mm was found to be two and three, respectively [18]. Elkafrawy et al. [19] examined the effectiveness of iron shape memory alloys (Fe-SMA) in reinforcing beam openings in the shear zone. Fe-SMA bars around openings allowed openings to regain their shear capacity and behave similarly to beams without openings. This is due to the ability of Fe-SMA to recover strains upon heating and unloading [20]. Pre-stressing Fe-SMA is considered an effective method for enhancing the overall behavior of beams with openings. This method can reduce stress concentration and fracture localization. Prestressing Fe-SMA bars by 30% and 60% enhanced beams' load capacity, with 100 mm x 150 mm openings by 12% and 9%, respectively [19].

Although numerous studies have explored the behavior of beams with openings, limited research has focused explicitly on strengthening these openings with Fe-SMA bars. This gap highlights the need for further investigation into the potential benefits of Fe-SMA bars for enhancing the structural performance of such beams. Thus, this study uses ABAQUS simulations to numerically evaluate the performance of beams with various opening shapes, including square, circular, and diamond. Under a four-point loading scheme, the behavior of beams with these opening shapes will be assessed and compared to solid beams, thoroughly examining the effectiveness of Fe-SMA bar reinforcement in strengthening the web openings.

2 FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

2.1 Material constitutive models

Three-dimensional (3D) finite element (FE) models of RC beams with different shaped openings and strengthened using Fe-SMA bars of various diameters are modeled using ABAQUS. The Fe-SMA bars are characterized by an elastic modulus of 133 GPa and a Poisson's ratio of 0.3. This FE analysis aims to thoroughly understand the structural performance of the studied RC beams under load without the need for experimental tests. The modeling of the Fe-SMA bars in ABAQUS is performed based on the simulation parameters outlined in earlier research [20]. Generally, the behavior of concrete in structural elements is represented in ABAQUS through various models. The smeared cracking model assumes consistent concrete behavior without considering cracks at high loads, while the brittle cracking model examines cracks under low strains. On the other hand, the concrete damaged plasticity (CDP) model combines aspects of both smeared and brittle cracking models to provide a comprehensive representation of concrete behavior and damage under tension and compression [21]. This allows

the CDP model to account for material plasticity and crack propagation. As a result, this study utilized the CDP model for concrete in RC beams. The constitutive models employed have been thoroughly detailed in the author's prior research [19].

2.2 Element types

This study employed a 20 mm element mesh size to get accurate results while minimizing computational time. The behavior of steel and Fe-SMA reinforcement bars is represented by a 2-node linear 3D truss element. For optimal bonding, the embedded rebar is surrounded by concrete [20], [22] represented by an 8-node linear brick solid element with reduced integration. This approach creates a balance between accuracy and computational efficiency through reduced integrations.

2.2 Specimens configuration

The study investigates RC beams 450 mm deep and 200 mm wide, with a shear span of 1000 mm and a loaded length of 2800 mm, under four-point loading. Figure 1 displays the beams' geometry and reinforcement details. Figure 1a illustrates the control beam without openings, whose structural behavior is compared to beams with openings. RC beams with three different web opening shapes: circular, square, and diamond, are presented in Figures 1b, 1c, and 1d, respectively. Figure 2 depicts the cross-sectional of the beam. All openings are 200 mm × 200 mm, but the diameter of the Fe-SMA reinforcing bars varies among the samples. Table 1 presents the test specimen details.

Figure 1: Specimen geometry with different web opening shapes: (a) B-Control; (b) B-Circle-2T18; (c) B-Square-2T18; (d) B-Diamond-2T18.

Figure 2: Cross-sectional view of the beam.

Table 1: Specimen Details

Group	Opening shape	Beam ID	Opening dimensions	Reinforcement	
				Type	Diameter (mm)
Control	-	B-Control	-	-	-
Group I	Circle	B-Circle-10	200 × 200	Fe-SMA	10
		B-Circle-18			18
		B-Circle-32			32
Group II	Square	B-Square-10			10
		B-Square-18			18
		B-Square-32			32
Group III	Diamond	B-Diamond-10	10		
		B-Diamond-18	18		
		B-Diamond-32	32		

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Modeling verification

For reliable results, the FEM model is verified through experimental work. This verification is essential to ensure that the model accurately replicates the behavior of RC beams under four-point loading. The verification has been done by comparing the results obtained from the FEM analysis with the experimental data published by Shahverdi et al. [22]. Although there are minor inconsistencies between the load vs. deflection curves derived from the experimental data with those produced from the FEM analysis, there is still a strong correlation between the results. The variations are due to limitations and assumptions in numerical modeling. The validation results have been previously presented in the authors' earlier work [23].

3.2 Cracking pattern

The opening shape and the size of the Fe-SMA reinforcing bars primarily influence the cracking pattern of beams with openings. As shown in Figure 3, beams with circular, square, and diamond-shaped openings exhibit different crack propagation behaviors. In the control beam (B-Control), which has no openings, cracking is concentrated near the center, with the maximum damage occurring at the midspan. In contrast, beams with openings display distinct cracking patterns based on the shape of the opening and the size of the reinforcing bars. Circular and diamond-shaped openings experience fewer diagonal cracks than square openings, regardless of the reinforcement size. This is because circular and diamond openings distribute stress more evenly due to their geometric properties. In contrast, square openings create stress concentrations at their sharp corners, which weakens the beam and leads to premature failure.

The size of the Fe-SMA bars also significantly impacts stress concentration around the openings. Beams with larger reinforcement bar diameters, such as B-Circle-32, B-Square-32, and B-Diamond-32, demonstrate reduced cracking and stress distribution closely resembling the control beam, indicating that the larger bars provide better reinforcement. This reduces the adverse effects of openings by spreading the stress more evenly across the beam. Conversely, beams with smaller reinforcement diameters, like B-Circle-10, B-Square-10, and B-Diamond-10, show higher stress concentrations and more pronounced cracking around the openings, especially in areas close to the edges. This underscores the necessity of using adequate reinforcement in beams with openings to avoid stress accumulation, which can compromise the structural integrity. Therefore, increasing the reinforcement bar diameter effectively enhances the beam's capacity to manage stress around critical areas like openings, improving overall structural performance.

Figure 3: Cracking patterns of beams.

3.3 Effect of opening shape

The load-deflection behavior of reinforced concrete beams with various web opening shapes, as depicted in Figure 4, demonstrates a clear impact of opening geometry on both the load-carrying capacity and deflection characteristics throughout the loading stages. These stages consist of an initial elastic phase, a cracking phase, a peak load point, and a post-peak softening phase. During the elastic phase, all beams, including those with openings, behave similarly to the control beam until initial cracking begins. The cracking phase is marked by the development of both flexural and shear cracks, during which beams with larger reinforcement bars, especially in the diamond-shaped openings, maintain better performance. Diamond openings demonstrate the highest shear capacity at the peak load, closely followed by circular openings, while square openings lag behind. In the post-peak softening phase, beams with diamond and circular openings display more gradual reductions in stiffness, reflecting better crack control and ductility, whereas square openings exhibit rapid stiffness loss.

The control beam without openings (B-Control) sets the highest benchmark with a peak load of 540 kN. Beams with diamond-shaped openings exhibit the highest load-carrying capacity among the beams with openings. For instance, the beam reinforced with 32 mm Fe-SMA bars (B-Diamond-32) achieved a peak load of 529 kN, which is only 2% lower than the control beam. Notably, the diamond-shaped opening outperforms other shapes, surpassing the circular-shaped beam (B-Circle-32), which reached a maximum load of 489 kN, about 8.2% lower than B-Diamond-32 and 9.4% lower than the control. Diamond openings also gradually soften after the peak, indicating better stiffness retention and crack control than other shapes. The most pronounced negative effect is seen in beams with square-shaped openings. For example, the beam with 32 mm Fe-SMA bars (B-Square-32) only achieved a peak load of 402 kN, marking a 25.6% reduction from the control and a 24.0% reduction compared to the B-Diamond-32 beam. This significant drop in capacity is accompanied by a steeper decline in stiffness after the peak load, indicating poorer crack resistance and overall reduced structural integrity.

Beams with openings experienced lower energy absorption capacities than the control beam. This is due to the accumulation of stresses around the openings, which reduces the beam's strength and energy absorption capacity [24]-[28]. Nevertheless, among beams with openings, the superior performance of the diamond-shaped openings can be attributed to their geometry, which allows for better stress distribution and crack control around the openings. This reduces stress concentration compared to square openings, which are more susceptible to sharp corners where cracks can initiate. Circular openings also perform well, but their curved edges, while smooth, seem to concentrate less shear resistance compared to diamond shapes. The square-shaped openings' sharp corners cause more pronounced stress concentrations and reduced load-bearing performance, which justifies their lower overall capacity and stiffness.

Figure 4: Effect of opening shape on the load-deflection response for beams with different Fe-SMA bar sizes.

3.4 Effect of Fe-SMA bar size

The load-deflection behavior shown in Figure 5 illustrates the impact of different Fe-SMA bar sizes on beams with varying opening shapes, specifically circular, square, and diamond-shaped openings. The overall trend indicates that increasing the Fe-SMA bar diameter enhances the load-carrying capacity and stiffness retention of the beams, though the extent of improvement varies based on the shape of the opening. For beams with circular-shaped openings (Figure 5a), the increase in Fe-SMA bar size significantly improves ultimate load. The beam reinforced with 32 mm bars (B-Circle-32) achieves a peak load of 489 kN, while those reinforced with 18 mm (B-Circle-18) and 10 mm (B-Circle-10) Fe-SMA bars reach peak loads of 484 kN and 432 kN, respectively. This shows that increasing the bar size from 10 mm to 32 mm leads to a 13.2% improvement in ultimate load. The larger bars also lead to better post-peak stiffness retention, as evidenced by the more gradual reduction in load after the peak, compared to the more drastic drop in smaller bars.

Similarly, the ultimate load increases with Fe-SMA bar size for beams with square-shaped openings (Figure 5b). The beam with 32 mm bars (B-Square-32) reaches a peak load of 402 kN, followed by 397 kN for the 18 mm bars (B-Square-18) and 349 kN for the 10 mm bars (B-Square-10). The increase from 10 mm to 32 mm bars results in a 15.2% improvement in ultimate load. However, even with the increase in bar size, square openings result in the lowest load-carrying capacity among the shapes, indicating that square openings concentrate stress more unfavorably compared to circular or diamond shapes. Moreover, the post-peak stiffness loss is more pronounced for square openings, particularly for the smaller bars, indicating that square openings are more sensitive to bar size reductions in terms of stiffness and ductility.

Beams with diamond-shaped openings (Figure 5c) demonstrate the highest ultimate load values. The beam reinforced with 32 mm bars (B-Diamond-2T32) achieves a peak load of 529 kN, very close to the control beam's 540 kN. The 18 mm (B-Diamond-2T18) and 10 mm (B-Diamond-2T10) versions achieve 526 kN and 468 kN, respectively. The improvement in load capacity from 10 mm to 32 mm bars is around 13%. Diamond-shaped

openings exhibit superior structural performance compared to circular and square openings, likely due to more efficient stress distribution and crack control around the opening. Additionally, the post-peak stiffness retention is superior in beams with larger bars, with diamond-shaped openings showing the least drastic reduction in stiffness compared to circular and square openings. Increasing the Fe-SMA bar size in all cases enhances the beams' load-bearing capacity by distributing the stress more effectively and controlling crack propagation. Larger bars (32 mm) demonstrate superior performance by allowing the beams to sustain higher loads before significant deflection occurs, leading to improved stiffness and ductility in the post-peak phase. Smaller bars (10 mm), while still enhancing the structural integrity of the beams, result in lower load capacities and a sharper decline in stiffness after peak loading, particularly in beams with square openings.

Figure 5: Effect of Fe-SMA bar size on the load-deflection response for beams with different opening shapes.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Openings in beams can significantly compromise their structural integrity and reduce their service life by concentrating stresses and promoting crack development. Reinforcing these openings with Fe-SMA bars is an effective technique that mitigates these adverse effects. This study examined the behavior of beams with various web-opening shapes in the shear zone by analyzing load-deflection relationships. A comparison was made between strengthened and unstrengthened beams with the following key conclusions:

- Beams with diamond and circular openings exhibited fewer diagonal cracks compared to beams with square openings. This is attributed to their geometric configurations, which allow for more even stress distribution, reducing stress concentrations that would otherwise accelerate crack formation in beams with square openings.
- Reinforcing beam openings with Fe-SMA bars significantly minimized stress localization and delayed crack development around the openings. This improvement is due to the unique properties of Fe-SMA bars, including the shape memory effect and superelasticity, which help to redistribute forces more effectively around the openings.
- Larger Fe-SMA bar diameters effectively prevented the early initiation of cracks around the openings. Increasing the bar diameter from 10 mm to 32 mm enhanced the load-carrying capacity of beams across all

opening shapes. For instance, beams with diamond-shaped openings reinforced with 18 mm and 32 mm Fe-SMA bars supported ultimate loads of 526 kN and 529 kN, respectively, which is comparable to the 540 kN capacity of the solid beam (without openings).

- Strengthening openings with 32 mm Fe-SMA bars resulted in the least reduction in ultimate load capacity for beams with diamond openings, showing only a 2% decrease compared to the control beam. In contrast, strengthening beams with square openings also increased their capacity. Still, it resulted in the most significant reduction, approximately 25.5%, in ultimate load capacity compared to beams with diamond and circular openings.

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MICROSTRUCTURE, PHASE TRANSFORMATION AND MECHANICAL PROPERTY OF NiMnGa/Sn COMPOSITES

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Abstract. This paper proposes to prepare NiMnGa/Sn composites by compositing NiMnGa particles and Sn powder. The microstructure, martensitic transformation and mechanical properties of the bulk alloy, ball-milled powders and composites were systematically investigated. The results show that the milled NiMnGa particles are mainly flaky in shape, and the alloy transforms from ordered to disordered structure after ball milling. The martensitic transformation of milled NiMnGa particles disappeared and it is recovered by post-annealing. The annealed NiMnGa particles and Sn powder were mixed and sintered to make NiMnGa particles /Sn composites. The composites exhibit a different NiMnGa particle distribution morphology for the axial direction and radial direction of the sample. The interfacial reaction between the NiMnGa particles and Sn matrix is observed. The martensitic transformation of the 30% and 40% composites has been observed, but the transformation temperatures for the composites are higher than that of the annealed NiMnGa particles, which should be related to the interfacial reaction that changes the composition of the NiMnGa particles. Most of the composites are not fractured during compressive test irrespective of the particles distribution and show a large plasticity, the mechanical strength of the composites increases with increasing the NiMnGa particle content.

Keywords: NiMnGa, Composite materials, Microstructure, Martensitic transformation, Mechanical properties

1 INTRODUCTION

Energy transducers commonly have two basic modes of operation, one in which an active material vibrates under an applied excitation to produce sound waves, and the other in which the active material converts the received vibrations into electromagnetic signals[1]. Typical transducer materials include piezoelectric ceramics, magnetostrictive materials, and their composite materials[2-5]. NiMnGa alloy is a magnetic shape memory alloy (FSMA) with large magnetic-field induced strain (MFIS) and high response frequency[6,7], which demonstrates great potential for applications in the domain of sensor and transducers[8]. However, NiMnGa alloy belongs to intermetallic compounds, and the brittleness is large that is not conducive to application[9]. Preparing porous alloys or particles and then compositing them with ductile matrix to form composites is an effective way to enhance the mechanical properties of NiMnGa alloys[10-12]. The two main types of common matrices are polymers and metals. However, the ageing of polymers leads to the deterioration of the mechanical properties of composites, which limits their application to a certain extent. Moreover, the interfacial bonding between the polymer matrix and NiMnGa particles is weak, which is not beneficial for stress transfer under mechanical loading. Metal matrix, on the other hand, can be a good solution to the above problems. Metal matrix composites have better interfacial bonding strength and higher mechanical strength, and show more stable physicochemical characteristics under specific conditions. The preparation of NiMnGa composites using Mg, Cu, and Al metals as the matrix has been reported, and the composites exhibit higher strength and ductility compared to a single metal matrix or NiMnGa alloy, indicating that compositing NiMnGa alloys with ductile metal matrix is an effective way to improve its property[11,13-15].

Metal Sn has large plasticity and ductility, but poor strength, the compositing of NiMnGa particles and Sn may be an effective way to solve the brittleness of NiMnGa alloy and improve the strength of Sn matrix at the same time. In this article, NiMnGa alloy particles were firstly prepared by ball milling method, and then the NiMnGa/Sn composites were prepared by powder metallurgy method. The microstructure, phase transformation, and mechanical properties of the composites were systematically investigated.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

Ni_{40.8}Mn_{38.1}Ga_{21.1} ferromagnetic shape memory alloy ingot was prepared by arc-melting of high purity elements of Ni, Mn and Ga under an argon atmosphere. The alloy was melted by rotating the melt 6 times, and the magnetic stirring was applied after the 2nd rotation to ensure homogeneity of the alloy composition. Then the as-cast ingot was homogenized in argon atmosphere at 1123 K for 9 h followed by water-quenching. The NiMnGa alloy powder was prepared by ball milling and post annealing at 1023 K for 2 h. The ball milling was performed using a QM-3A ball mill with hardened steel balls and ball-to-powder ratio was 8:1, ball milling time was 15 min, 25 min and 35 min. Alcohol was added as ball milling medium to reduce the occurrence of cold-welding, and cool the ball milling tank to avoid overheating. Using QM-3A ball mill to mix the annealed 35 min-milled NiMnGa alloy powder and Sn powder for 20 min without milling balls, and the NiMnGa powder weight ratio was chosen as 20%, 30% and 40%. The mixed powder was transferred into the mould and then cold-pressed, and finally the pressed samples were sintered at 428K for 1h under an argon atmosphere to obtain NiMnGa/Sn composites. Figure 1 shows the schematic diagram of the preparation of NiMnGa/Sn composites.

The microstructure of the samples was characterized using a FEI Apreo-C scanning electron microscope (SEM) equipped with an energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) analyzer. Phase constitution was identified by X-ray diffraction (XRD) using a Panalytical X-pert PRO diffractometer with Cu K_α radiation at room temperature. Martensitic transformation of the samples was investigated using a Pekin-Elmer Diamond differential scanning calorimeter (DSC). The compression tests were carried out using an Instron universal testing machine (Model 3365) at a deformation speed of 0.5 mm/min. The size of the compression testing samples was ~Φ3 mm × 6 mm.

Figure 1: Schematic diagram of the preparation of NiMnGa/Sn composites.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Microstructure

Figure 2 shows SEM images of NiMnGa particles prepared by different ball milling time. Figure 2 (a), (b) and (c) corresponds to ball milling time of 15 min, 25 min and 35 min, respectively. It can be seen that all the NiMnGa particles are flaky in shape, and the size of particles seems to be decreased gradually as the milling time increases. The 35 min ball milled NiMnGa particles have many fine particles and show a wider size distribution.

Figure 2: SEM images of NiMnGa powder with different ball milling time, (a) 15 min, (b) 25min, and (c) 35min

The XRD patterns of Figure 3 show that the structural evolution from NiMnGa ingots to powder with the milling time. At room temperature, the diffraction peaks of NiMnGa alloy can be mainly indexed as body-centered tetragonal structure martensite phase (peaks corresponding to the black dashed line), indicating that the bulk NiMnGa alloy is a single martensite phase at room temperature. After 15 min ball milling, the structure of the powder turns into a disordered cubic structure (peaks corresponding to the yellow dashed line). With the increase of ball milling time, the diffraction peaks of the disordered cubic phase structure seem to be enhanced gradually. And for the XRD pattern of the 35 min sample, only the diffraction peaks of the disordered cubic structure exist which agrees with the results of cryo-milling Ni_{49.4}Mn_{30.3}Ga_{20.3} powders[16]. This indicates that the structure of the alloy was destroyed during the ball milling process, and evolved from ordered to disordered. Correspondingly the martensitic transformation should be also affected, which was verified in the subsequent DSC analysis, and the phase transformation did not occur in the ball milled powder during both heating and cooling cycles.

Figure 3: Room-temperature XRD patterns of NiMnGa bulk alloy and powders with different ball milling time.

To recover the ordered structure and martensitic transformation of ball-milled NiMnGa particles, the milled particles are annealed at 1023 K for 1 h. Then the annealed 35 min-milled particles were composited with Sn powder. The SEM micrographs of the annealed NiMnGa particle and the Sn powder have been shown in Figure 4(a) and (b), respectively. It can be seen that the Sn powder exhibits irregularly spherical or dumbbell shape that is different from the flaky NiMnGa particles, which should be beneficial for the densification of the composites under compression with different shape raw powders. Figure 4(c), (e) and (g) shows SEM images of the composites taken at the axial direction of the sample, Figure 4(d), (f) and (h) shows SEM images of the composites taken at the radial direction of the sample, and Figure 4(i) shows the schematic diagram of different directions. It can be seen that the darker black phase is the NiMnGa alloy particles and the lighter grey phase should be the Sn matrix.

From the SEM image of 20% composite, it can be found that along the axial direction the NiMnGa alloy particles are widely dispersed in the light grey Sn matrix. Along the radial direction, the large-size NiMnGa alloy particles present a sheet-like structure, uniformly distributed in the matrix. This special particle morphology is not only related to the shape of the original ball-milled particles, but also may be related to the cold-pressing effect on the sample, in which the alloy particles are redistributed due to the applied compression stress during the cold-pressing process. As the NiMnGa particle content increases, the particle dispersion uniformity decreases. The distribution of particles is relatively homogeneous in the composites with 20% particle content, whereas in the composites with 40% particle content the local agglomeration of NiMnGa particles occurs.

Figure 4: SEM images of (a) NiMnGa particles, (b) Sn powder, (c) 20% composite axial, (d) 20% composite radial, (e) 30% composite axial, (f) 30% composite radial, (g) 40% composite axial, (h) 40% composite radial, (i) schematic diagrams of different directions.

The EDS test results on the surface of 40% composite are given in Figure 5(a), clearly indicating the distribution of NiMnGa particles and Sn matrix in the sample, which is consistent with the above analysis result in Figure 4. Figure 5(b) further shows the line-scan EDS results across the interface of the NiMnGa particle and Sn matrix. The high magnification SEM image shows that the interface between the NiMnGa particles and Sn matrix under the combined effect of cold pressing and sintering is relatively tight, and the irregular surface of the particles is conducive to the mechanical bonding between the matrix and the particles, but some irregularly shaped holes at the interface are also observed. The line-scan EDS result shows a wide Ni, Mn, Ga and Sn elements distribution on the interface, indicating a slight chemical reaction at the interface happens. For Sn alloys, elemental diffusion may lead to the formation of Kirkendall holes, and the irregular microporosity near the interface may be the Kirkendall holes caused by elemental diffusion [17]. Therefore, the holes at the interfacial area could be related to the Kirkendall effect due to the mutual elemental diffusion. In addition, the holes away from the interface show a more regular round shape, which may be related to the introduced gas pores during the cold-compression process.

Figure 6 shows the XRD patterns of NiMnGa/Sn composites with different particle contents. The black squares, blue circles and green triangles labelled on the pattern correspond to the diffraction peaks of NiMnGa particles, NiSn compound and Sn, respectively. It can be seen that, with the increase of NiMnGa content, the intensity of NiMnGa diffraction peaks gradually increases. The diffraction peaks at $\sim 28^\circ$ and $\sim 73^\circ$ are the diffraction peaks of NiSn, indicating the existence of new compound that should be caused by the interfacial reaction between Sn matrix and NiMnGa particles, which are in agreement with the EDS result shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: (a) EDS result of elemental distribution of NiMnGa/Sn composites, (b) line-scan EDS result of elemental distribution at the interface.

Figure 6: Room-temperature XRD patterns of the annealed NiMnGa powder and NiMnGa/Sn composite.

3.2 Phase transformation

Figure 7: The DSC curves of (a) annealed NiMnGa particles, (b) 20% composite, (c) 30% composite and (d) 40% composite.

Figure 7 shows the DSC curves of annealed NiMnGa particles and NiMnGa/Sn composites. It can be seen that the annealed NiMnGa particles exhibit a clear martensitic transformation during heating/cooling process. However, the composite with 20% particle content has no significant phase transformation peaks observed, which should result from the low content of NiMnGa particles. With further content increase of NiMnGa particles, phase transformation peaks are observed in 30% and 40% of the composites. The A_s and M_f of annealed NiMnGa particles are 100.1 °C and 86.9 °C, respectively. The A_s and M_f temperatures of the composite with 30% NiMnGa content are 144.8 °C and 117.4 °C, and those of 40% NiMnGa content are 159.1 °C and 130.1 °C, respectively. It can be seen that the phase transformation temperature of the composite is higher than that of the annealed NiMnGa particles, and with the increase of NiMnGa particle content, the phase transformation temperature of the composites also increases. The change in phase transformation temperature may be related to the interfacial reaction between the matrix and the particles, which altered the composition of the NiMnGa particles to some extent.

3.3 Mechanical properties of composites

In order to investigate the effect of NiMnGa particle distribution and content on the mechanical properties of the composites, different specimens were cut along the axial and radial directions of the composite samples for compression experiments. Figure 8(a) shows the stress-strain curve along the axial compression. It can be seen that, except for the NiMnGa/Sn composites with 40% particle content, all the composites show significant plastic deformation behavior, and are not completely fractured when the compressive strain reaches 80%. Figure 8(b) shows the compressive stress-strain curve of the specimen cut along the radial direction. It can be seen that the deformation stage is basically similar to the axial specimen, all the samples are not completely fractured and the samples are compressed to a thin sheet finally. Besides, different from compressive curve along axial direction, the stress-strain curve along the radial compression shows a minor fluctuation during loading, which could be correlated to the different NiMnGa particles distribution in different directions shown in Figure 4. Overall, the compressive strength of composites increases with

increasing the NiMnGa particle content, which mainly result from the reinforcing effect of the NiMnGa particles.

Figure 8: Compressive stress-strain curves of composite materials, (a) axial compression, (b) radial compression

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, we have successfully prepared NiMnGa/Sn composites by ball milling and sintering method. NiMnGa particles prepared by ball milling are flaky-shape. After ball milling, the ordered structure of the alloy is destroyed and the martensitic transformation correspondingly disappears. The martensitic transformation of the NiMnGa particles is retrieved after post-annealing. The NiMnGa alloy particles are widely dispersed in the Sn matrix, and exhibit a different distribution morphology at axial and radial direction of the samples. The interfacial bonding between the NiMnGa particles and the Sn matrix is relatively tight mainly correlated to the interfacial reaction. In the composite with 20% NiMnGa particles, the martensitic transformation is not observed due to the low content of NiMnGa particles. The 30% and 40% composites exhibit martensitic transformation but with higher transformation temperatures than that of the original annealed NiMnGa particles. With the increase of NiMnGa particle content, the compressive strength of the composite increases. Most of the composites demonstrate a large plasticity without completely fracturing during compression.

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FINITE ELEMENT EVALUATION OF FULL 3D EFFECTIVE PROPERTIES OF d_{31} PIEZOELECTRIC MACRO-FIBRE COMPOSITES

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Abstract. Piezoelectric Macro-Fibre Composites (MFC) transducers have become very popular since they combine the conformability of epoxy-matrix composites and the electromechanical energy density of piezoceramic materials. Since they are heterogeneous and made of several different materials (piezoceramic fibres, epoxy matrix, electrode and protective layers), a methodology is required to relate their effective properties with the individual properties of its components. This work presents the evaluation of all necessary effective properties for a full 3D finite element analysis. For the evaluation of the remaining effective piezoelectric coefficients, new local problems were added to those presented in the literature. The results are compared to those available in the literature and provided by the manufacturer. A discussion on the full 3D effective properties and their application for full 3D finite element analysis of smart structures with bonded MFCs is also presented.

Keywords: Macro-Fibre Composites, Finite element homogenization, 3D piezoelectric effective properties

1 INTRODUCTION

Piezoelectric Macro-Fibre Composites (MFC) transducers have become very popular since they combine the conformability of epoxy-matrix composites and the electromechanical energy density of piezoceramic materials [1]. Since they are heterogeneous and made of several different materials (piezoceramic fibres, epoxy matrix, electrode and protective layers), a methodology is required to relate their effective properties with the individual properties of its components [2]. Previous studies [3, 4] have shown that the effective properties depend not only on the active layer (piezoceramic fibres and epoxy matrix) but also on electrode and protective layers.

In particular, in [4], the effective elastic, piezoelectric and dielectric properties of a d_{31} MFC, accounting for the effect of electrode and protective layers, were evaluated through finite element (FE) homogenization. An analysis of the effect of the fibre volume fraction, electric boundary conditions (BC) and electric field dependence of soft piezoceramic fibres dielectric and piezoelectric properties on the main effective properties was also presented. Nevertheless, some effective properties, such as the piezoelectric coefficients e_{15} and e_{24} and the dielectric coefficients ϵ_{11}^S and ϵ_{22}^S , that may be important for completing the full 3D matrices required for FE simulations of the homogenized patches were not presented in [4].

Hence, this work presents the evaluation of all necessary effective properties for a full 3D FE analysis. For the evaluation of the remaining effective piezoelectric coefficients, new local problems were added to those presented in [4]. Also, some small adjustments are performed to the FE model to provide coherent results, considering that new evaluations are carried out. In particular, the FE mesh was refined, compared to that considered in [4]. The results are compared to those available in the literature and provided by the manufacturer. A discussion on the full 3D effective properties and their application for full 3D FE analysis of smart structures with bonded MFCs will be also presented.

2 FULL 3D CONSTITUTIVE EQUATIONS FOR d_{31} MFC

Let us consider a d_{31} MFC made of an active layer, composed of piezoceramic macro-fibres embedded in an Epoxy matrix, which is then fully covered by electrode and protective layers, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of a d_{31} MFC.

Figure 2: Representative volume element (RVE) of a d_{31} MFC.

All piezoelectric fibres are considered to be poled in x_3 (through-thickness) direction. A preferential or dominant x_3 direction is imposed for the electric field through an electrode layer fully covering top (x_3^+) and bottom (x_3^-) surfaces. Thus, for the intended d_{31} operation mode, it can then be assumed that in-plane electric fields vanish (that is, $E_1 = E_2 = 0$). On the other hand, in order to also evaluate the effective piezoelectric and dielectric properties under other electric BC (that is, with $E_1 \neq 0$ or $E_2 \neq 0$), complete 3D matrix properties are considered, such that

$$\begin{pmatrix} T_1 \\ T_2 \\ T_3 \\ T_4 \\ T_5 \\ T_6 \\ D_1 \\ D_2 \\ D_3 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} c_{11}^E & c_{12}^E & c_{13}^E & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -e_{31} \\ c_{12}^E & c_{22}^E & c_{23}^E & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -e_{32} \\ c_{13}^E & c_{23}^E & c_{33}^E & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -e_{33} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & c_{44}^E & 0 & 0 & 0 & -e_{24} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & c_{55}^E & 0 & -e_{15} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & c_{66}^E & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \hline 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & e_{15} & 0 & \epsilon_{11}^S & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & e_{24} & 0 & 0 & 0 & \epsilon_{22}^S & 0 \\ e_{31} & e_{32} & e_{33} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \epsilon_{33}^S \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} S_1 \\ S_2 \\ S_3 \\ S_4 \\ S_5 \\ S_6 \\ E_1 \\ E_2 \\ E_3 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (1)$$

where T_p and S_q , with $p, q = 1, \dots, 6$, stand for the six components of mechanical stress and strain vectors in Kelvin-Voigt notation. D_j and E_j denote the electric displacements and fields in direction x_j ($j = 1, 2, 3$). In the so-called e -form of the linear piezoelectric constitutive equations (1), c_{pq}^E , e_{jp} and ϵ_{jj}^S denote the short-circuit (SC) elastic stiffness (at constant electric fields), stress piezoelectric and blocked electric permittivity (at constant mechanical strains) coefficients. For the so-called d -form constitutive equations, s_{pq}^E , d_{jp} and ϵ_{jj}^T stand for the SC elastic compliance (at constant electric fields), strain piezoelectric and free electric permittivity (at constant mechanical stresses) coefficients.

In the d_{31} operation (transverse response) mode, the dominant electromechanical coupling (in the longitudinal direction) is between the electric field and displacement in x_3 (through-thickness) direction, E_3 and D_3 , and x_1 (fibre longitudinal direction) normal stress and strain, T_1 and S_1 . Thus, the evaluation of the piezoelectric e_{31}/d_{31} , elastic c_{11}^E/s_{11}^E and dielectric $\epsilon_{33}^S/\epsilon_{33}^T$ coefficients is necessary to qualify these composite transducers as sensors and actuators. Nevertheless, due to the anisotropy of the resulting MFC piezoelectric composite effective behavior, it is important to analyze properties related to through-width deformation, which are e_{32} , d_{32} , c_{22}^E , c_{12}^E . Besides, in order to provide complete 3D effective properties matrices for the d_{31} MFC and, hence, be able to use them in 3D FE modeling and simulation, the remaining properties, related to the in-plane electrical excitation, e_{15} , e_{24} , $\epsilon_{11}^S/\epsilon_{11}^T$ and $\epsilon_{22}^S/\epsilon_{22}^T$ need also to be evaluated.

3 EVALUATION OF d_{31} MFC FULL 3D EFFECTIVE ELECTROMECHANICAL PROPERTIES

The evaluation of the effective coefficients that are important to a d_{31} MFC, as discussed in the previous section, is done in this work using the so-called average quantity-based FE homogenization technique proposed in [3]. It is based on the evaluation of the average stresses, strains, electric fields and electric displacements in a FE model of a Representative Volume Element (RVE) of the MFC when subjected to properly chosen mechanical and electrical boundary and periodicity conditions. With these averaged quantities and using the constitutive equations of an equivalent orthotropic piezoelectric material, described in the previous section, the effective elastic, piezoelectric and dielectric coefficients of the MFC are evaluated. It is important to account for symmetric or periodic mechanical and electrical BC in directions x_1 and x_2 , since the RVE is obtained from a through-thickness cut of the real MFC.

The active layer RVE is built with one longitudinal section of the piezoceramic macro-fibre (through-thickness poled and electroded) between two Epoxy inserts. Both upper and lower surfaces of the active layer are covered by a thin electrode layer, composed of two Copper and one Epoxy layers representing a section of the fingered electrode layer. Finally, electrode layers are covered by a homogeneous Kapton protective layer. The RVE boundaries are denoted X_1^- , X_1^+ , X_2^- , X_2^+ , X_3^- and X_3^+ (Figure 2). To obtain a more realistic analysis, electric potential BC are imposed at the electrodes on surfaces Γ_e^- and Γ_e^+ , which represent the areas covered by Copper electrodes and piezoceramic fibre electrodes (at top and bottom surfaces of the piezoceramic fibres).

Average strains and electric fields can be imposed to the RVE using displacements and voltage BC, as

$$u_i^{X_j^+} - u_i^{X_j^-} = \bar{S}_{ij}(x_j^{X_j^+} - x_j^{X_j^-}), \quad i, j = 1, 2, 3, \quad (2)$$

$$\phi^{X_\alpha^+} - \phi^{X_\alpha^-} = -\bar{E}_\alpha(x_\alpha^{X_\alpha^+} - x_\alpha^{X_\alpha^-}), \quad \alpha = 1, 2, \quad \phi^{\Gamma_e^+} - \phi^{\Gamma_e^-} = -\bar{E}_3(x_3^{\Gamma_e^+} - x_3^{\Gamma_e^-}). \quad (3)$$

The resulting average strains, stresses, electric fields and electric displacements could be defined by the following integrals over the RVE volume

$$\bar{S}_q = \frac{1}{V} \int_V S_q dV, \quad \bar{T}_p = \frac{1}{V} \int_V T_p dV, \quad p, q = 1, \dots, 6, \quad (4)$$

$$\bar{E}_k = \frac{1}{V} \int_V E_k dV, \quad \bar{D}_i = \frac{1}{V} \int_V D_i dV, \quad i, k = 1, 2, 3. \quad (5)$$

Since the RVE is discretized in a number of finite elements, these integrals can only be approximated by a sum over averaged element values multiplied by the respective element volume divided by total volume of the RVE, such that

$$\bar{S}_q = \frac{\sum_{e=1}^N S_q^{(e)} V^{(e)}}{\sum_{e=1}^N V^{(e)}}, \quad \bar{T}_p = \frac{\sum_{e=1}^N T_p^{(e)} V^{(e)}}{\sum_{e=1}^N V^{(e)}}, \quad p, q = 1, \dots, 6, \quad (6)$$

$$\bar{E}_k = \frac{\sum_{e=1}^N E_k^{(e)} V^{(e)}}{\sum_{e=1}^N V^{(e)}}, \quad \bar{D}_i = \frac{\sum_{e=1}^N D_i^{(e)} V^{(e)}}{\sum_{e=1}^N V^{(e)}}, \quad i, k = 1, 2, 3. \quad (7)$$

where $V^{(e)}$ is the element e volume. $S_q^{(e)}$, $T_p^{(e)}$, $E_k^{(e)}$ and $D_i^{(e)}$ are the average strains, stresses, electric fields and electric displacements evaluated at element e . N is the number of finite elements used to discretize the RVE.

The elastic coefficients related to normal strains and stresses c_{pq}^E , $p, q = 1, 2, 3$ were evaluated using three local problems for which a normal strain S_q ($q = 1, 2, 3$) is imposed, through relative normal displacements $u_q^{X_q^+} - u_q^{X_q^-}$. Also, in order to obtain $\bar{S}_j = 0$ for $j \neq q$, the normal displacements u_j for each pair of nodes at opposing surfaces X_j^- and X_j^+ are forced to be equal (symmetrically coupled degrees of freedom). Then, starting from the e -form constitutive equations (1), the effective SC elastic coefficients can be evaluated using

$$c_{pq}^E = \bar{T}_p / \bar{S}_q, \quad p, q = 1, 2, 3, \quad (8)$$

in which the average stresses \bar{T}_p and strains \bar{S}_q are evaluated using (6).

The stress piezoelectric coefficients e_{31} , e_{32} and e_{33} can be also obtained from the local problems used to evaluate c_{1j}^E , c_{2j}^E and c_{3j}^E , respectively, that is where normal stress states in directions x_1 , x_2 and x_3 are approximated. From the e -form constitutive equations (1), e_{31} , e_{32} and e_{33} can be obtained through evaluation of the average electric displacement D_3 such that

$$e_{31} = \bar{D}_3 / \bar{S}_1, \quad e_{32} = \bar{D}_3 / \bar{S}_2, \quad e_{33} = \bar{D}_3 / \bar{S}_3, \quad (9)$$

where the average normal strains \bar{S}_1 , \bar{S}_2 and \bar{S}_3 and electric displacement \bar{D}_3 are evaluated using the FE approximations of (6) and (7).

The evaluation of the SC elastic coefficients related to shear strains and stresses c_{pp}^E , $p = 4, 5, 6$, is performed using other three local problems for which shear strains S_{ik} ($S_{23} = S_4/2$, $S_{13} = S_5/2$ and $S_{12} = S_6/2$) are applied to approximate a pure shear stress state in the planes $x_2 - x_3$, $x_1 - x_3$ and $x_1 - x_2$ by imposing relative shear displacements $u_i^{X_k^+} - u_i^{X_k^-}$ at surfaces X_k^+ / X_k^- and $u_k^{X_i^+} - u_k^{X_i^-}$ at surfaces X_i^+ / X_i^- . In addition, normal displacements at the boundary surfaces parallel to each shear plane of interest are symmetrically coupled to ensure zero strains perpendicular to the shear plane. Then, the evaluation of the effective shear elastic coefficients is performed in terms of the average shear stresses \bar{T}_p and strains \bar{S}_p using

$$c_{pp}^E = \bar{T}_p / \bar{S}_p, \quad p = 4, 5, 6. \quad (10)$$

A SC electric BC is ensured in both previous cases, (8) and (10), setting the voltage degrees of freedom (dof) in the electrodes at surfaces Γ_e^- and Γ_e^+ to zero. Table 1 indicates symmetric BC for the electric potential along directions x_1 and x_2 for the X_1^- / X_1^+ and X_2^- / X_2^+ RVE surfaces.

The stress piezoelectric coefficients e_{24} and e_{15} can be also obtained from the local problems used to evaluate the SC elastic coefficients related to shear strains and stresses c_{pp}^E , $p = 4, 5, 6$. Indeed, from the e -form constitutive equations (1), e_{24} and e_{15} can be obtained through evaluation of the average electric displacement D_2 and D_1 , respectively, such that

$$e_{24} = \bar{D}_2 / \bar{S}_4, \quad (11)$$

$$e_{15} = \bar{D}_1 / \bar{S}_5. \quad (12)$$

For the evaluation of the blocked dielectric coefficient e_{33}^S , another local problem is set up for which an electric voltage $\phi^{\Gamma_e^+} = h_p$ (in value) is applied to the electrode at surface Γ_e^+ while the voltage at the opposite

Table 1: Boundary conditions (displacement/electric potential) and relations used to evaluate the full 3D effective material properties of a d_{31} piezoelectric MFC.

Problem	X_1^-/X_1^+	X_2^-/X_2^+	X_3^-/X_3^+	Γ_e^-/Γ_e^+	Relation
1	$u_1^{i+} - u_1^{i-} = q$ $\phi^{i+} - \phi^{i-} = 0$	$u_2^{i+} - u_2^{i-} = 0$ $\phi^{i+} - \phi^{i-} = 0$	$u_3^{i+} - u_3^{i-} = 0$ -	- $\phi^{i+} = 0; \phi^{i-} = 0$	$c_{1j}^E = \bar{T}_j/\bar{S}_1$ (8) $e_{31} = \bar{D}_3/\bar{S}_1$ (9)
2	$u_1^{i+} - u_1^{i-} = 0$ $\phi^{i+} - \phi^{i-} = 0$	$u_2^{i+} - u_2^{i-} = q$ $\phi^{i+} - \phi^{i-} = 0$	$u_3^{i+} - u_3^{i-} = 0$ -	- $\phi^{i+} = 0; \phi^{i-} = 0$	$c_{2j}^E = \bar{T}_j/\bar{S}_2$ (8) $e_{32} = \bar{D}_3/\bar{S}_2$ (9)
3	$u_1^{i+} - u_1^{i-} = 0$ $\phi^{i+} - \phi^{i-} = 0$	$u_2^{i+} - u_2^{i-} = 0$ $\phi^{i+} - \phi^{i-} = 0$	$u_3^{i+} - u_3^{i-} = q$ -	- $\phi^{i+} = 0; \phi^{i-} = 0$	$c_{3j}^E = \bar{T}_j/\bar{S}_3$ (8) $e_{33} = \bar{D}_3/\bar{S}_3$ (9)
4	$u_1^{i+} - u_1^{i-} = 0$ $\phi^{i+} - \phi^{i-} = 0$	$u_2^{i+} - u_2^{i-} = q$ $\phi^{i+} - \phi^{i-} = 0$	$u_3^{i+} - u_3^{i-} = q$ -	- $\phi^{i+} = 0; \phi^{i-} = 0$	$c_{44}^E = \bar{T}_4/\bar{S}_4$ (10) $e_{24} = \bar{D}_2/\bar{S}_4$ (11)
5	$u_3^{i+} - u_3^{i-} = q$ $\phi^{i+} - \phi^{i-} = 0$	$u_2^{i+} - u_2^{i-} = 0$ $\phi^{i+} - \phi^{i-} = 0$	$u_1^{i+} - u_1^{i-} = q$ -	- $\phi^{i+} = 0; \phi^{i-} = 0$	$c_{55}^E = \bar{T}_5/\bar{S}_5$ (10) $e_{15} = \bar{D}_1/\bar{S}_5$ (12)
6	$u_2^{i+} - u_2^{i-} = q$ $\phi^{i+} - \phi^{i-} = 0$	$u_1^{i+} - u_1^{i-} = q$ $\phi^{i+} - \phi^{i-} = 0$	$u_3^{i+} - u_3^{i-} = 0$ -	- $\phi^{i+} = 0; \phi^{i-} = 0$	$c_{66}^E = \bar{T}_6/\bar{S}_6$ (10)
7	$u_1^{i+} - u_1^{i-} = 0$ $\phi^{i+} - \phi^{i-} = 0$	$u_2^{i+} - u_2^{i-} = 0$ $\phi^{i+} - \phi^{i-} = 0$	$u_3^{i+} - u_3^{i-} = 0$ -	- $\phi^{i+} = q; \phi^{i-} = 0$	$\epsilon_{33}^S = \bar{D}_3/\bar{E}_3$ (13)
8	- $\phi^{i+} - \phi^{i-} = 0$	- $\phi^{i+} - \phi^{i-} = 0$	- -	- $\phi^{i+} = q; \phi^{i-} = 0$	$\epsilon_{33}^T = \bar{D}_3/\bar{E}_3$ (14)
9	$u_3^{i+} - u_3^{i-} = 0$ $\phi^{i+} = q; \phi^{i-} = 0$	- $\phi^{i+} - \phi^{i-} = 0$	$u_1^{i+} - u_1^{i-} = 0$ $\phi^{i+} - \phi^{i-} = 0$	- -	$\epsilon_{11}^S = \bar{D}_1/\bar{E}_1$ (15)
10	- $\phi^{i+} = q; \phi^{i-} = 0$	- $\phi^{i+} - \phi^{i-} = 0$	- $\phi^{i+} - \phi^{i-} = 0$	- -	$\epsilon_{11}^T = \bar{D}_1/\bar{E}_1$ (17)
11	- $\phi^{i+} - \phi^{i-} = 0$	$u_3^{i+} - u_3^{i-} = 0$ $\phi^{i+} = q; \phi^{i-} = 0$	$u_2^{i+} - u_2^{i-} = 0$ $\phi^{i+} - \phi^{i-} = 0$	- -	$\epsilon_{22}^S = \bar{D}_2/\bar{E}_2$ (16)
12	- $\phi^{i+} - \phi^{i-} = 0$	- $\phi^{i+} = q; \phi^{i-} = 0$	- $\phi^{i+} - \phi^{i-} = 0$	- -	$\epsilon_{22}^T = \bar{D}_2/\bar{E}_2$ (18)

electrode (at surface Γ_e^-) is set to zero so that a unitary electric field in the x_3 direction is generated. The blocked condition is approximated by preventing the normal strains S_1 , S_2 and S_3 through the imposition of equal normal displacements u_j ($j = 1, 2, 3$) for each pair of nodes at opposing surfaces X_j^- and X_j^+ . The dielectric coefficient is then obtained from

$$\epsilon_{33}^S = \bar{D}_3/\bar{E}_3. \quad (13)$$

It could also be interesting to evaluate the free dielectric coefficient ϵ_{33}^T . For that, a local problem is designed in which an electric voltage $\phi^{\Gamma_e^+} = h_p$ (in value) is applied to the electrode at surface Γ_e^+ while the voltage at the opposite electrode (at surface Γ_e^-) is set to zero so that a unitary electric field in the x_3 direction is generated. To approximate the free condition, no mechanical displacements BC are imposed to the RVE. The dielectric coefficient is then obtained from

$$\epsilon_{33}^T = \bar{D}_3/\bar{E}_3. \quad (14)$$

For the evaluation of the blocked dielectric coefficients ϵ_{11}^S and ϵ_{22}^S , two other local problems are set up for the imposition of in-plane electric fields in x_1 and x_2 directions, respectively. Since there are no physical electrodes in the corresponding planes x_2/x_3 and x_1/x_3 , the electric potentials are applied to the boundaries of the RVE, namely X_1^- and X_1^+ for the application of an electric field in x_1 direction and X_2^- and X_2^+ for the application of an electric field in x_2 direction. Additionally, it is assumed that the actual Copper electrode is electrically inactive but is kept in place to maintain the RVE stiffness behavior unchanged. Since the application of an electric field perpendicular to the piezoelectric fiber poling direction is expected to generate a transverse

shear strain, the blocked condition is approximated by preventing the shear strains S_4 , for the evaluation of ϵ_{22}^S with application of an electric field E_2 , or S_5 , for the evaluation of ϵ_{11}^S with application of an electric field E_1 . The dielectric coefficients are then obtained from

$$\epsilon_{11}^S = \bar{D}_1 / \bar{E}_1, \quad \text{with BC aiming at } \bar{S}_5 = 0, \quad (15)$$

and

$$\epsilon_{22}^S = \bar{D}_2 / \bar{E}_2, \quad \text{with BC aiming at } \bar{S}_4 = 0. \quad (16)$$

The free dielectric coefficients ϵ_{11}^T and ϵ_{22}^T may also be evaluated with similar local problems but without mechanical displacements BC imposed to the RVE, to approximate a free condition,

$$\epsilon_{11}^T = \bar{D}_1 / \bar{E}_1, \quad \text{with BC aiming at } \bar{T}_5 = 0, \quad (17)$$

and

$$\epsilon_{22}^T = \bar{D}_2 / \bar{E}_2, \quad \text{with BC aiming at } \bar{T}_4 = 0. \quad (18)$$

The local problems used to evaluate the full 3D material effective electromechanical properties of the piezoelectric d_{31} MFC RVE are summarized in Table 1, where u_j^{i-} and u_j^{i+} are the displacements in direction j and ϕ^{i-} and ϕ^{i+} are the electric potentials at i -th node of opposite surfaces; q is an arbitrary non-null value.

The MFC effective material static electromechanical coupling coefficients (EMCC) k_{3j}^2 may be evaluated as

$$k_{3j}^2 = \frac{d_{3j}^2}{s_{jj}^E \epsilon_{33}^T}. \quad (19)$$

4 FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS AND VALIDATION

A FE model was built in Ansys[®] to solve the local problems and evaluate the full 3D effective electromechanical properties of a 5-layered piezoelectric d_{31} MFC RVE, using a fiber volume fraction (FVF) of 0.86 for the PZT+Epoxy Active Layer. The 3D 20-Node coupled-field solid FE SOLID226 was used to mesh all volumes. It has the three displacement translations along the Cartesian coordinate system axes and the electric potential as nodal dof. A mesh of 9900 finite elements was used considering 25 divisions in x_1 direction (17 divisions for the Epoxy layer and 4 divisions for each electrode layer), 18 divisions in x_2 direction (14 divisions for the PZT fibre and 2 divisions for each Epoxy layer) and 22 divisions in x_3 direction (12 divisions for the PZT layer, 2 divisions for each electrode layer and 3 divisions for each protective layer). The dimensions considered for this RVE are $h_P = 180 \mu\text{m}$, $h_K = 40 \mu\text{m}$, and $h_C = 18 \mu\text{m}$, $L_E = 420 \mu\text{m}$, $L_C = 80 \mu\text{m}$, $w_E = 28.35 \mu\text{m}$ and $w_P = 348.3 \mu\text{m}$ [2]. The material properties for the piezoceramic material Sonox P502, taken from [2], are: $s_{11}^E = s_{22}^E = 18.5 \text{ pm}^2/\text{N}$, $s_{33}^E = 20.7 \text{ pm}^2/\text{N}$, $s_{12}^E = -6.29 \text{ pm}^2/\text{N}$, $s_{13}^E = -6.23 \text{ pm}^2/\text{N}$, $s_{44}^E = s_{55}^E = 33.2 \text{ pm}^2/\text{N}$, $s_{66}^E = 52.3 \text{ pm}^2/\text{N}$, $d_{31} = d_{32} = -185 \text{ pC}/\text{N}$, $d_{33} = 440 \text{ pC}/\text{N}$, $d_{15} = d_{24} = 560 \text{ pC}/\text{N}$, $\epsilon_{11}^T = \epsilon_{22}^T = 1950\epsilon_0$, $\epsilon_{33}^T = 1850\epsilon_0$. The material properties for the other constituents, taken from [5], are: Epoxy – $Y = 2.5 \text{ GPa}$, $\nu = 0.42$ and $\epsilon = 4.25\epsilon_0$; Kapton – $Y = 2.5 \text{ GPa}$, $\nu = 0.34$ and $\epsilon = 3.4\epsilon_0$; and Copper electrode – $Y = 110 \text{ GPa}$, $\nu = 0.34$ and $\epsilon = 5\epsilon_0$, with $\epsilon_0 = 8.854 \text{ pF}/\text{m}$.

A discussion on the local problems #1, #2, #3, #6, #7 and #8 was presented in [4]. Since similar results were obtained for these local problems, here, it is chosen to focus on the new local problems from now on.

Local problems #4 and #5, that are mainly intended to evaluate the effective shear modulus c_{44}^E and c_{55}^E , respectively, were also used to evaluate the effective stress piezoelectric coefficients e_{24} and e_{15} . Although

these coefficients are usually less important in terms of operation performance of d_{31} MFCs, they are required to complete the full 3D piezoelectric matrix necessary for 3D FE simulations. The approximation is mainly based on the evaluation of the average electric displacement in the in-plane x_2 and x_1 directions according to (11) and (12), respectively. Thus, the distributions of electric displacement and field and shear strain and stress are shown in Figures 3, for local problem #4, and 4, for local problem #5.

Figure 3: Electric displacement D_2 (a) and field E_2 (b) and shear strain S_4 (c) and stress T_4 (d) induced by shear displacements applied to the d_{31} MFC RVE (local problem #4).

Figure 4: Electric displacement D_1 (a) and field E_1 (b) and shear strain S_5 (c) and stress T_5 (d) induced by shear displacements applied to the d_{31} MFC RVE (local problem #5).

Although most of the shear strains are localized in the protective layers, in both cases, it is noticeable that non-negligible electric displacements are developed in the piezoelectric fiber. Hence, despite being smaller than the e_{3j} effective coefficients, both e_{24} and e_{15} are in the same order of magnitude, meaning that actuation/sensing using the d_{24} and d_{15} modes could be possible if actual electrodes were installed in the X_2^-/X_2^+ or X_1^-/X_1^+ faces. As generally this is not the case, these effective coefficients shall be used only to complete the full 3D piezoelectric matrix for FE simulations.

In addition, other effective coefficients required to fill the full 3D e -form properties matrix are the effective blocked dielectric coefficients ϵ_{11}^S and ϵ_{22}^S . For their evaluation, additional local problems are required since it is necessary to apply an electric field along the in-plane x_1 and x_2 directions. Thus, although there are no actual electrodes in the X_1^-/X_1^+ and X_2^-/X_2^+ faces, electric potentials were applied to these faces to generate the required electric fields. Since the application of such electric fields induces shear strains in the RVE, these strains are blocked through displacements BC. Then, the effective blocked dielectric coefficients ϵ_{11}^S and ϵ_{22}^S are evaluated in local problems #9 and #11 using the approximations to the average electric displacements and fields according to (15) and (16), respectively. The distributions of interest in these cases are the electric displacement and field and the shear strain and stress. These are shown in Figures 5, for the evaluation of ϵ_{11}^S , and 6, for the evaluation of ϵ_{22}^S . Figure 5 shows that the application of an electric field in the x_1 direction (local problem #9) induces important transverse shear strains S_5 in the piezoelectric fiber that are counterbalanced by shear strains in the protective layers so that the RVE is not sheared in its boundaries. The resulting effect

is that the effective dielectric coefficient ϵ_{11}^S is of the same order of magnitude as the through-thickness one ϵ_{33}^S as shown in Table 2. On the other hand, for the application of an electric field in the x_2 direction (local problem #11), although the global behavior of the shear strains that are induced both in the piezoelectric fiber and, in opposite sense, in the protective layer, the effect is much less important. This is due to the fact that the electric potentials are applied to the X_2^-/X_2^+ faces that are constituted by non-piezoelectric material (Epoxy, for the active layer, and Epoxy, Copper and Kapton, for the covering outer layers). This leads to an important reduction of the electric potential induced in the piezoelectric fiber faces. For this reason, the effective dielectric coefficient ϵ_{22}^S is much smaller than the other two, as shown in Table 2.

Figure 5: Electric displacement D_1 (a) and field E_1 (b) and shear strain S_5 (c) and stress T_5 (d) induced by electric potentials difference applied to the blocked d_{31} MFC RVE (local problem #9).

Figure 6: Electric displacement D_2 (a) and field E_2 (b) and shear strain S_4 (c) and stress T_4 (d) induced by electric potentials difference applied to the blocked d_{31} MFC RVE (local problem #11).

In order to validate the FE homogenization, the evaluated full 3D effective coefficients of the d_{31} MFC were compared to previous analytical and experimental results available in the literature. The results obtained here for the full 5-layered MFC were compared to data provided by the manufacturer of a commercial d_{31} MFC (Smart Material Corp.) [6], with the same nominal geometrical and material properties for its constituents considered in the present work. Results are summarized in Table 2. Notice that not all coefficients are provided by the manufacturer. Nevertheless, it can be concluded that the here 3D FE-evaluated effective electromechanical properties represent very well the actual (manufactured) d_{31} MFC. The only coefficient presenting a significant relative deviation (24%) to the data from manufacturer is the transversal elastic modulus Y_2^E , but this may be explained by the fact that the actual width of the Copper electrode finger (L_C) is not known and was only visually approximated from a microphotography presented by the original prototype developer at NASA Langley Research Center [1]. A wider Copper electrode finger would lead to a higher transversal elastic modulus Y_2^E . It could also affect the transverse piezoelectric coefficients e_{32} and d_{32} . The results obtained for the most important effective coefficients, Y_1^E , d_{31} and ϵ_{11}^T , are all below 4% of relative deviation (3.4%, 1.3% and 0.9% respectively) compared to the data provided by the Smart Material Corp. [6]. The present results were also compared to those shown in [4]. Both results were almost the same despite the fact that, in the present analysis,

the FE mesh is substantially finer than that considered in [4].

Table 2: Effective material properties of d_{31} MFC (*: values obtained post-processing data provided in the reference).

Coefficient	FE [4]	Present FE	Manufacturer [6]	Coefficient	FE [4]	Present FE	Manufacturer [6]
Y_1^E (GPa)	31.40	31.37	30.34	d_{31} (pC/N)	-172.2	-172.3	-170
Y_2^E (GPa)	19.80	19.69	15.86	d_{32} (pC/N)	-133.8	-133.2	–
Y_3^E (GPa)	9.03	9.02	–	d_{33} (pC/N)	310.0	308.9	–
G_{23}^E (GPa)	2.17	2.16	–	d_{15} (pC/N)	–	334.9	–
G_{13}^E (GPa)	2.42	2.42	–	d_{24} (pC/N)	–	219.3	–
G_{12}^E (GPa)	5.34	5.33	5.52	e_{31} (C/m ²)	-6.04	-6.03	–
ν_{12}^E	0.36	0.36	0.31	e_{32} (C/m ²)	-3.47	-3.44	–
ν_{23}^E	0.37	0.37	–	e_{33} (C/m ²)	1.48	1.48	–
ν_{13}^E	0.42	0.42	–	e_{15} (C/m ²)	–	0.81	–
$\epsilon_{11}^T/\epsilon_0$	–	1019.3	–	e_{24} (C/m ²)	–	0.47	–
$\epsilon_{22}^T/\epsilon_0$	–	24.1	–	k_{31}^2 (%)	6.7	6.7	6.4*
$\epsilon_{33}^T/\epsilon_0$	1572.1	1573.3	1558.6	k_{31}	0.26	0.26	0.25*
$\epsilon_{11}^S/\epsilon_0$	–	988.6	–				
$\epsilon_{22}^S/\epsilon_0$	–	24.1	–				
$\epsilon_{33}^S/\epsilon_0$	1179.7	1181.7	–				

5 APPLICATION OF EFFECTIVE PROPERTIES FOR THE ANALYSIS OF A BONDED d_{31} MFC

To exemplify the utility of the full 3D effective properties, the obtained values were applied for a FE analysis of a smart structure composed of a d_{31} MFC bonded to a metallic plate, using an Epoxy adhesive, with a tip mass (Figure 7). The benchmark was taken from [7] where the application of MFC transducers for energy harvesting was studied. The experimental results presented therein were also considered for verification of the present FE model and results. The results presented in [7] indicate a substantial non-linearity of the structure. The fundamental resonance frequency ranges between 30 and 31 Hz, depending on the imposed base acceleration. The voltage output (in RMS) of a resistive circuit connected to the MFC ranges between 6.5 and 10 Vs²/m.

Figure 7: Cantilever plate with adhesively bonded d_{31} MFC patch and tip mass.

A FE model was implemented in Ansys[®] following the geometrical and material properties provided in [7] and using the full 3D effective properties for the d_{31} MFC obtained in the present work. The plate is made of Aluminum with length 70 mm, width 10.6 mm, thickness 0.67 mm, Young's modulus 68.9 GPa, Poisson's ratio 0.33 and mass density 2700 kg m⁻³. The adhesive layer is made of Epoxy 3M DP-460 with length 28 mm, width 7 mm, thickness 0.1 mm, Young's modulus 2.7 GPa, Poisson's ratio 0.4 and mass density 1100 kg m⁻³.

The MFC patch is from Smart Material Co., model 2807-P2, with length and width equal to those of the adhesive layer and thickness 0.3 mm. The tip mass is composed of two Acrylic blocks with length 15 mm, width 25 mm and thickness 5 mm, which are fixed using two screws. The total mass, including the screws, is 7.3 g. To avoid modeling the screws, the total mass was uniformly distributed in the two Acrylic blocks. Non-uniform rectangular meshes of $87 \times 16 \times 2$, $38 \times 10 \times 2$, $38 \times 10 \times 2$, and $6 \times 22 \times 2$ 20-node solid finite elements were considered for the host plate, adhesive layer, MFC, and each tip mass block, respectively. A modal analysis was performed for SC and open-circuit (OC) electric BC on the MFC effective top and bottom surface electrodes. The first five natural frequencies and the corresponding effective (structural) modal EMCC, defined as $EMCC = 1 - f_{SC}^2 / f_{OC}^2$, are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: First five natural frequencies in SC and OC electric BC, and corresponding effective modal EMCC, for the plate with bonded MFC patch and tip mass.

Mode	1	2	3	4	5
f_{SC} (Hz)	29.9	171.1	364.9	372.5	1098.2
f_{OC} (Hz)	30.3	171.1	364.9	374.0	1098.9
EMCC (%)	2.18	0	0	0.79	0.12

The frequency response function (FRF) of the voltage output for an imposed base acceleration was also simulated in Ansys[®]. For that, a global damping factor of 4% was estimated from the FRF presented in [7] and used as input in Ansys[®]. The obtained peak output is 11.2 Vs²/m, a little higher than the experimental one.

6 CONCLUSIONS

This work presented the evaluation of all necessary effective properties of a d_{31} piezoelectric macro-fibre composite for a full 3D FE analysis. Compared to the existing methodology and results [4], for the evaluation of the remaining effective piezoelectric and dielectric coefficients, new local problems were added. The results are compared to those available in [4] and provided by the manufacturer [6]. An application of the effective properties for full 3D FE analysis of a cantilever Aluminum plate with a bonded MFC patch was also presented indicating good correspondence between numerical and experimental results [7].

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EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTIVE ELECTROMECHANICAL COUPLING OF A VIBRATING AIRCRAFT-TYPE HYBRID HONEYCOMB SANDWICH PANEL WITH BONDED PIEZOELECTRIC d_{31} MACRO-FIBRE COMPOSITE (MFC) PATCH

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Abstract. This work presents the *experimental evaluation* challenges of the modal effective *Electro-Mechanical Coupling Coefficient* (EMCC) of a *hybrid sandwich plate*, made of regular (hexagonal) Aluminium *honeycomb core* and woven glass fibre-reinforced polymer *composite faces*, on which is bonded a piezoelectric transverse response (d_{31}) *Macro-Fibre Composite* (MFC) large patch. The testing challenges come from the very *light weight* of the hybrid sandwich panel and the resulting difficulties to consider, without damaging it, different mechanical boundary conditions (BCs) along its lateral edges. This experimental campaign, using an *impedance analyser*, complements an earlier one that used an LCR meter. The latter provided only the EMCC of the first three electro-mechanically coupled modes under free-free (F-F) BCs, while the former reached *more accurately* eight ones for F-F and *clamped-free* (cantilever) BCs. Beside graphical form, the obtained frequency and effective EMCC results are given in tabular form, so that they can be used as reference for validating/correlating future numerical models.

Keywords: Experiment; EMCC; Vibration; Hybrid honeycomb sandwich; Piezoelectric; MFC.

1 INTRODUCTION

Hybrid honeycomb sandwiches, made of different materials for the core and faces, find popular usage as trim panels in modern aircraft structures for alleviating their weight, noise or vibration. Hybridization can be reached by combining Aluminium (Al) [1-3], paper [1, 4, 5] and Carbon (CFRP) [2, 4, 5] or Glass (GFRP) [3, 6, 7] Fibre-Reinforced Polymer woven *composite materials*. Hybrid honeycomb sandwiches are often functionalized through bonding *piezoelectric* (PE) ceramic [1, 2] or *Macro-Fibre Composite* (MFC) [4-7] patches that are used as sensors and actuators for wave propagation [1, 2], structural health monitoring [5] and active vibration control [4]. Besides, for vibration-based transduction applications, like PE shunted damping (PSD) and energy harvesting (PEH), the so-called modal effective *Electro-Mechanical Coupling Coefficient* (EMCC) is a key performance indicator [8] that can be maximized by adequately selecting the host-patch materials couple and optimally positioning the patch on the host laminated CFRP composite or hybrid (GFRP skins, Al core) honeycomb sandwich structures [6]. However, except the earlier works [6, 7], no others have been found in the open literature on the experimental evaluation of the modal effective EMCC of hybrid honeycomb sandwiches bonded with MFC patches. Therefore, this work presents for the first time *Experimental Impedance Analyser (EIA)*-based evaluation challenges of the modal effective EMCC of a *hybrid sandwich plate*, made of regular (hexagonal) *Al honeycomb core* and woven *GFRP composite faces*, on which is bonded a PE *transverse mode* (d_{31}) MFC large patch. The testing challenges come from the very *light weight* of the panel and the resulting difficulties to consider, without damaging it, *different mechanical Boundary Conditions* (BCs), like free-free (F-F) and clamped-free (C-F) lateral edges of the hybrid sandwich [3]. This new campaign complements an LCR (Inductance-L, Capacitance-C, Resistance-R) meter-based earlier one [6, 7], that provided only the EMCC of the first three *electromechanically coupled modes* (EMC), by reaching *more accurately* eight ones under F-F and C-F (*cantilever*) BCs.

In the following, first, the next section describes the experimental setup, materials and devices. Then, the third section presents the resulting experimental modal analyses (EMA) of the EIA measurements and their use for the *Short-Circuit* (SC) and *Open-Circuit* (OC) frequencies extractions and modal effective EMCC post-treatments. Next, the EIA measurements and results are compared to those of experimental LCR meter analyses for the respectively considered F-F or/and C-F BCs. The latter are popular in PSD and PEH, while the former are useful for inverse identification. Finally, conclusions and perspectives are given as a closure.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP: MATERIALS AND DEVICES

This section describes the EMA setup, its measurement devices and the aircraft-type hybrid honeycomb sandwich and surface-bonded PE d_{31} MFC patch materials used for the experimental evaluation of the modal effective EMCC of such vibrating smart structure under F-F (Figure 1a) and C-F (Figure 1b) BCs at its lateral edges. For this, the *impedance analyzer* WK 6500B from Wayne Kerr (WK), shown in Figure 1, is used to graphically display the *module* and *phase* of the *voltage-to-current ratio* of the *capacitance* of the d_{31} MFC patch, that is surface-bonded on the hybrid honeycomb sandwich under the considered two BCs. The *excitation voltage* was fixed to 1V, while the *impedance analyzer resolution* was set to 1600 points for a considered frequency range.

(a) Test setup for F-F configuration

(b) Test setup for C-F configuration

Figure 1: EIA setup for modal effective EMCC evaluation under (a) F-F and (b) C-F BCs.

As shown in Figure 1a and zoomed-in in Figure 2a, the F-F BCs were realized by posing the tested smart structure on two foam pieces, while the C-F BCs were realized by accurately (with good quality alignment) fastening one lateral edge along 1 cm, as shown in Figure 1b and zoomed-in in Figure 2b. It is worthy to mention that the influence of the smart coupon position on the foams was found negligible, as considering two different positions led to the same *resonant* (SC) and *anti-resonant* (OC) frequencies of their related MFC *capacitances*.

(a) Figure 1a zoom-in on F-F BCs

Figure 1b zoom-in on C-F BCs' clamp

Figure 2: Zoom-in of Figure 1 on realized (a) F-F BCs and (b) C-F BCs' clamp.

The optimal positioning of the MFC patch on the vibrating hybrid sandwich honeycomb is modal shape and BCs-dependent [9]. Hence, a numerical modal analysis (NMA) of the bare honeycomb sandwich coupon was conducted, using a developed *detailed* finite element (FE) approach [3], in order to locate the maxima of the *modal strain energy* (MSE) where to bond the MFC patch. The resulting optimized configuration is that in Figure 2a, where the MFC patch is located 3 cm from one lateral edge (see also Figure 1b) and *centered* along the host *width*. This *optimal* position *maximizes* the effective EMCC of the *first mode*, the target of the PSD and PEH applications.

The PE d_{31} MFC patch (M-8528-P2), from Smart Materials GmbH (Germany), has global in-plane dimensions of $103 \times 31 \text{ mm}^2$ and useful *active area* ones of $85 \times 28 \text{ mm}^2$ while its *thickness* is 0.3 mm. In order to connect it to the impedance analyzer (Figure 1), very thin wires were soldered to its net-like electrodes' dedicated soldering pads (see Figure 2a). The MFC patch was *glued* with *Cyanolit* (super glue) to one of the GFRP skins of the hybrid honeycomb sandwich, which has length x width x thickness of $183 \times 52 \times 4.6 \text{ mm}^3$. More details on the latter host structure geometrical and material properties can be found in [3]. The combined hybrid honeycomb sandwich and MFC patch have a measured mass of 13.75 g, indicating a *very light* smart structure. Considering the protecting polyamide film, electrodes, soldering pads and glue allowed to *update* the d_{31} MFC patch volume mass density to 6300 Kg/m^3 (*active area*-based value is 5440 Kg/m^3 [10]).

3 EXPERIMENTAL IMPEDANCE ANALYSES: FREQUENCIES & EFFECTIVE EMCC

This section first presents the graphical displays of the *absolute* and *phase* of the *voltage-to-current ratio* of the *capacitance* of the d_{31} MFC patch that is surface-bonded on the hybrid honeycomb sandwich under the considered two BCs (F-F and C-F). Then, the extracted SC and OC frequencies, approximating respectively the *resonant* (r) and *anti-resonant* (a) ones, are tabulated with the post-treated *experimental* (e) EMCC (K_e^2) from [11]:

$$K_e^2 (\%) = 100 \frac{f_a^2 - f_r^2}{f_a^2} \quad (1)$$

A slightly different, called *numerical* (n), EMCC expression is traditionally used in PSD applications:

$$K_n^2 (\%) = 100 \frac{f_{oc}^2 - f_{sc}^2}{f_{sc}^2} \quad (2)$$

However, above EMCC expressions were shown [11] to be related by this one:

$$K_e^2 \approx \frac{K_n^2}{K_n^2 + 1} \quad (3)$$

Nevertheless, when $K_n^2 \ll 1$, $K_e^2 \approx K_n^2$ and either of the expressions can be used for evaluating the EMCC.

3.1 Free-free configuration

The module and phase of the capacitance of the F-F hybrid honeycomb sandwich-bonded PE d_{31} MFC patch are shown in Figure 3, first, for a large (300 Hz-11 kHz) frequency range, in order to evaluate the number of modes present in this range. Then, zooms illustrate missing modes (Figure 4a) or for accurate identification (Figure 4b).

Figure 3: Capacitance module and phase spectra of F-F hybrid honeycomb sandwich-bonded PE d_{31} MFC.

(a) Zoom-in on frequency range [2-4.9] kHz

(b) Zoom-in on frequency range [7-9] kHz

Figure 4: Capacitance module and phase spectra of F-F hybrid honeycomb sandwich-bonded PE d_{31} MFC.

As in Figure 5, the phase peak corresponds to the inflexion point between resonance and anti-resonance peaks.

(a) Module and phase *global* combined display

(b) Module and phase *mode 1* combined display

Figure 5: Capacitance combined module and phase of F-F hybrid honeycomb sandwich-bonded PE d_{31} MFC.

Next, a zoom-in on each mode is displayed in order to identify its resonant (SC) and anti-resonant (OC) frequencies that correspond, respectively, to the maximum and minimum of the capacitance module or the points of inflexion of the ascending and descending branches of the phase, as illustrated in Figure 6 for the first mode.

(a) Mode 1 resonant (SC) frequency

(b) Mode 1 anti-resonant (OC) frequency

Figure 6: Identification of mode 1 (a) resonant (SC) and anti-resonant (OC) frequencies from module and phase.

The earlier procedure is applied for identifying the *eight modes*, numbered in Figure 3 and Figure 4, leading to the frequencies and effective EMCC summarized in Table 1. The latter confirms that the *highest* effective EMCC is obtained for the *first mode*, target of PSD and PEH applications. Besides, following (1) and (2) and as $f_{a,OC} > f_{r,SC}$, $K_n^2 > K_e^2$; hence, the numerical EMCC *overestimates* the experimental one. Nevertheless, the differences between them reduces as the former is approaching unity. Besides, it is worthy to recall that the impedance analyzer provides only the characteristics of the EMC modes. Hence, as the *in-plane* (x-y) *bending* and *torsion* modes are known to be electro-mechanically *uncoupled* [9, 11], the modes in Table 1 are the *transverse* (x-z) *bending* modes only. This recall is to be taken into account when using these experimental tabulated results as a reference for validating/correlating numerical (FE for example) ones. Specifically, the order of modes shown in the first column of Table 1 should be made consistent with that resulting from the numerical analysis. That is, the consistent modes order is correctly obtained only after modal shapes (deformation) visualizations.

Table 1: Frequencies (Hz) and effective EMCC (%) of F-F hybrid honeycomb sandwich-bonded d_{31} MFC.

Mode	f_r, f_{SC}	f_a, f_{OC}	K_e^2	K_n^2
1	600.00	618.07	5.76	6.11
2	1502.92	1523.39	2.67	2.74
3	2751.82	2788.52	2.61	2.69
4	4184.76	4242.32	2.70	2.77
5	6981.76	7089.31	3.01	3.10
6	7722.69	7850.82	3.24	3.35
7	7988.71	8061.02	1.79	1.82
8	8170.71	8319.28	3.54	3.67

3.2 Clamped-free configuration

Under the *same measurement conditions* as the F-F configuration, the module and phase of the capacitance of the C-F hybrid honeycomb sandwich-bonded PE d_{31} MFC patch are shown in Figure 7, first, for the a wide (global) frequency range (100 Hz-8 kHz) in order to evaluate the number of modes present in this range. It can be seen that the latter shows *six modes* that have much lower frequencies than those in Figure 3, due to the clamp presence.

Figure 7: Capacitance module and phase spectra of C-F hybrid honeycomb sandwich-bonded PE d_{31} MFC.

Then, the same zoom-in procedure is applied for accurately identifying the *six modes*, numbered in Figure 7, leading to the frequencies and effective EMCC shown in Table 2 from which similar remarks as from Table 1 can be retained, except that the *highest* EMCC (lower value) is here obtained for the *fourth mode* despite its low peak.

Table 2: Frequencies (Hz) and effective EMCC (%) of C-F hybrid honeycomb sandwich-bonded d_{31} MFC.

Mode	f_i, f_{SC}	f_a, f_{OC}	K_e^2	K_n^2
1	107.25	108.76	2.84	2.76
2	515.46	523.06	2.97	2.88
3	1368.38	1381.45	1.92	1.88
4	2713.41	2769.09	4.15	3.98
5	3194.49	3255.56	3.86	3.72
6	3582.33	3646.46	3.61	3.49

4 COMPARISON WITH EXPERIMENTAL LCR METER ANALYSES

This section aims to compare the *LCM Meter*-based measured (*mode-by-mode* and *frequency-by-frequency*) *impedance* (module and phase) figures, tabulated extracted frequencies and post-treated effective EMCC of the PE d_{31} MFC patch, surface-bonded on the hybrid honeycomb sandwich under F-F BCs that were *realized differently*, as this first experimental campaign was conducted few years earlier than the present one. Indeed, the F-F BCs were here realized by *wire suspension* of the smart hybrid honeycomb sandwich, as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: *Wire suspension*-realized F-F BCs of the smart hybrid honeycomb sandwich.

The impedance module and phase, measured by an LCR meter, are shown graphically in Figure 9 for the first EMC mode and Figure 10 for the second one. From the latter, notice the poor accuracy around the curves' peaks, due to the LCM meter low frequency resolution (large steps), that shall affect the accuracy of the extraction of the impedance *minimum* (*anti-resonant*, SC) and *maximum* (*resonant*, OC) frequencies (oppositely to the capacitance characteristics) and the EMCC post-treated from them. The corresponding results are shown in Table 3.

Figure 9: EMC mode 1 impedance module and phase of F-F hybrid honeycomb sandwich-bonded PE d_{31} MFC.

Figure 10: EMC mode 2 impedance module and phase of F-F hybrid honeycomb sandwich-bonded PE d_{31} MFC.

Table 3: Frequencies (Hz) and effective EMCC (%) of C-F hybrid honeycomb sandwich-bonded d_{31} MFC.

Mode	f_a, f_{SC}	f_r, f_{OC}	K_e^2	K_n^2
1	590.55	600	3.13	3.23
2	1495	1525	3.90	4.05

Despite the inaccuracy of extractions, the $a_{,SC}$ and $r_{,OC}$ frequencies given in Table 3 show small *relative deviations* (with those in Table 1 that are taken as *reference*, due to their extractions accuracy), particularly for EMC mode 2, of, respectively, -1.57% and -2.92% for EMC mode 1, and -0.53% and 0.11% for EMC mode 2. However, the relative deviations of the EMCC are much higher ($\sim \pm 47\%$, with ‘-’ for mode 1 and ‘+’ for mode 2) as they are proportional to the *frequency measurement resolution* and the *inverse of EMCC values* [12].

5 CONCLUSIONS AND PERSPECTIVES

Impedance analyser-based experimental evaluations of the modal effective EMCC of a vibrating *hybrid Al honeycomb-woven GFRP composite faces sandwich plate*, bonded with a PE d_{31} MFC large patch, were presented in figures and tables for F-F and C-F lateral edges of the smart panel. The extracted frequencies and post-treated effective EMCC were compared to those from earlier LCR meter-based experimental evaluations [6, 7]. The latter provided only the EMCC of the first two EMC modes under F-F BCs, while the former reached *more accurately eight modes* for F-F and C-F BCs. The present experimental campaign confirmed that the *highest* effective EMCC is that of the *fundamental mode*, the target of PSD and PEH applications, while the earlier experimental campaign showed *lower* graphical and peak (resonant/anti-resonant) frequency extraction *accuracy*, due to the low frequency resolution of the LCR meter. Nevertheless, the provided *tabulated results* of both experimental campaigns can be of valuable use as *reference* for validating/correlating future numerical models. In particular, the use of the detailed FE approach [3] gives a good perspective of the present work, as this will allow the *experimental validation* of the recently *FE-homogenized* 3D electromechanical properties of the here described PE d_{31} MFC [13].

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A NEW HAMILTONIAN SEMI-ANALYTICAL APPROACH TO VIBRATION ANALYSIS OF PIEZOELECTRIC MULTI-LAYERED PLATES

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Abstract. A new Hamiltonian semi-analytical method is established to investigate the free vibration characteristics of piezoelectric multilayered plates. By performing a Legendre Transform, the classical *Lagrangian* functional is recast into a *Hamiltonian* one, so that the resulting variational formulation can be expressed in terms of the displacements and electric potential and their transverse stresses and electric displacement dual variables. Within the framework of this Hamiltonian formalism, the in-plane of the piezoelectric multilayered plate is discretized into two-dimensional *p-type* high-order spectral finite elements while the resulting first-order one dimensional differential system is solved analytically by enforcing the interface continuity constraints. The whole piezoelectric multilayered plate's dynamic stiffness is then built, from which its circular frequencies are computed with the help of the Wittrick-Williams algorithm. A detailed discussion is provided on the implementation aspects, followed by some numerical examples to assess the robustness, accuracy and effectiveness of the proposed method. The obtained results are verified by comparison with published ones based on conventional approaches.

Keywords: Hamiltonian; Semi-analytic; Spectral finite element; Vibration; Piezoelectric; Multilayer; Plate.

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, a wide range of industries including automotive, aerospace and marine have focused on smart structures by devoting many research efforts to harvest electrical power from ambient vibrations using new materials such as electromagnetic, electro-elastic or piezoelectric [1]. Among the class of smart materials, piezoelectric ones are often used due to their ease of manufacturing and high-power density. Laminated composite plates constitute one of the most important components in a number of systems such as aerospace vehicles or civil engineering structures due to their lightweight, high strength and high efficiency of load-carrying characteristic. Piezoelectric composite plates are the most representative smart structures that have received an increasing attention. It is generally acknowledged that the coupling characteristics caused by the structural anisotropy of composite piezoelectric laminated plates make it difficult to model these multi-physics systems from mathematical as well as computational points of view [2]. Therefore, there is still a need to explore and develop new robust and high performance numerical models to accurately predict the dynamic response of such smart structures.

Therefore, hereafter, a *semi-analytical* numerical model for the *vibration* analysis of *piezoelectric* laminated *composite* plates is developed based on the *Hamiltonian partial-mixed* variational formulation (VF) that was recently proposed for the free vibrations analysis of elastic multilayered composite plates [3]. The advantage of semi-analytical approaches lies mainly in its dimension reduction characteristic, which allows overcoming the time and memory costs in traditional numerical approaches such as the *finite element method* (FEM). This is done by turning the plate's partial differential equations into a numerically discretized weak form in the in-plane coordinates while maintaining their analytically solved strong form in the thickness one so that the *interface continuity constraints* (ICC) are satisfied exactly. To deal with complex geometry and boundary conditions (BC), the *spectral* FEM is used for the numerical discretization, thereby increasing the computational efficiency of the here proposed approach. However, in free vibration analysis, the equations become transcendental once the ICC are considered. Here, to tackle this issue, the Wittrick-Williams (W-W) algorithm [4] is implemented.

2 NEW HAMILTONIAN SEMI-ANALYTICAL APPROACH TO VIBRATION ANALYSIS

2.1 Local and Variational Partial-Mixed Formulations

Consider a 3D linear piezoelectric body that occupies a simply connected domain Ω to which a Cartesian global coordinates system (O, x, y, z) is attached. It is bounded by a sufficiently regular boundary surface $\Gamma = \partial\Omega$, with outward unit vector $\underline{\mathbf{n}}$, and is subjected to known surface traction vector $\underline{\mathbf{F}}$ on Γ_F and surface electric charge scalar Q on Γ_Q , with Γ_F and Γ_Q being parts of the boundary Γ . The latter can also support imposed electric potential scalar $\tilde{\varphi}$ on Γ_φ , so that $\Gamma_\varphi \cap \Gamma_Q = \emptyset$ and $\Gamma_\varphi \cup \Gamma_Q = \Gamma$, and mechanical displacement vector $\underline{\tilde{\mathbf{u}}}$ on Γ_u so that $\Gamma_u \cap \Gamma_F = \emptyset$ and $\Gamma_u \cup \Gamma_F = \Gamma$. The electromechanical equations that describe the corresponding dynamic *local* problem are the:

- Cauchy's and Gauss' equations of motion:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Div} \underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} &= \rho \underline{\ddot{\mathbf{u}}} \\ \text{Div} \underline{\mathbf{D}} &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad \text{in } \Omega \quad (1)$$

Where, $\underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}$, $\underline{\mathbf{D}}$ are the linear Cauchy stress tensor and electrical displacement (induction) vector, while Div represents the divergence operator, $\underline{\ddot{\mathbf{u}}}$ the acceleration vector and ρ the mass density.

- Mechanical strains-displacements and electric fields-potential relations:

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} &= \frac{1}{2} (\text{Grad} \underline{\mathbf{u}} + \text{Grad}^T \underline{\mathbf{u}}) \\ \underline{\mathbf{E}} &= -\text{Grad} \varphi \end{aligned} \quad \text{in } \Omega \quad (2)$$

With, $\underline{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}$, $\underline{\mathbf{E}}$ being the linear Lagrange strain tensor and electric field vector, while $\underline{\mathbf{u}}$ and φ are the mechanical displacements vector and electric potential scalar. Besides, Grad denotes the gradient operator.

- Converse and direct piezoelectric constitutive equations (*e-form* type):

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} &= \underline{\underline{\mathbf{C}}}^E \underline{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} - \underline{\underline{\mathbf{e}}}^T \underline{\mathbf{E}} \\ \underline{\mathbf{D}} &= \underline{\underline{\mathbf{e}}} \underline{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} + \underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}}^S \underline{\mathbf{E}} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Where, $\underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}$, $\underline{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}$ are the engineering (Voigt notations) stress and strain vectors, while $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{C}}}^E$, $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{e}}}$ and $\underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}}^S$ are the elastic stiffness (at constant electric field), stress piezoelectric and dielectric (at constant strains) matrices.

- Dirichlet (essential) BC:

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{\mathbf{u}} &= \underline{\tilde{\mathbf{u}}} & \text{on } \Gamma_u \\ \varphi &= \tilde{\varphi} & \text{on } \Gamma_\varphi \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

- Neumann (natural) BC:

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}} \underline{\mathbf{n}} &= \underline{\mathbf{F}} & \text{on } \Gamma_F \\ \underline{\underline{\mathbf{D}}}^T \underline{\mathbf{n}} &= -Q & \text{on } \Gamma_Q \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Where, $\underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}}$ denotes the matrix representing the stress tensor.

In order to formulate the reference problem in a generalized way, the following *generalized* displacement $\underline{\mathbf{U}}$, strain $\underline{\mathbf{S}}$, stress $\underline{\mathbf{T}}$ and load $\underline{\mathbf{G}}$ vectors are introduced:

$$\underline{\mathbf{U}} = \begin{Bmatrix} \underline{\mathbf{u}} \\ \varphi \end{Bmatrix}; \quad \underline{\mathbf{S}} = \begin{Bmatrix} \underline{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} \\ -\underline{\mathbf{E}} \end{Bmatrix}; \quad \underline{\mathbf{T}} = \begin{Bmatrix} \underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} \\ \underline{\mathbf{D}} \end{Bmatrix}; \quad \underline{\mathbf{G}} = \begin{Bmatrix} \underline{\mathbf{F}} \\ -Q \end{Bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

As a consequence, the piezoelectric constitutive equations (3) rewrite as this *generalized* Hook's elastic law-like matrix form:

$$\underline{\mathbf{T}} = \underline{\underline{\mathbf{C}}} \underline{\mathbf{S}} \quad (7)$$

With, $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{C}}}$ being the *generalized* constitutive behavior matrix [5]. Moreover, the Dirichlet and Neumann BC are restated as:

$$\begin{aligned}\underline{\mathbf{U}} &= \underline{\tilde{\mathbf{U}}} & \text{on } \Gamma_U &= \Gamma_u \cup \Gamma_\varphi \\ \underline{\mathbf{T}} \underline{\mathbf{n}} &= \underline{\mathbf{G}} & \text{on } \Gamma_G &= \Gamma_F \cup \Gamma_Q\end{aligned}\quad (8)$$

Here, the *generalized* stress tensor 4th order matrix $\underline{\mathbf{T}}$ is such that $\underline{\mathbf{T}}^T = [\underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} \quad \underline{\mathbf{D}}]$.

In the case of a piezoelectric layered body with adjoining laminae *perfectly bonded together* and *without internal electrodes*, the generalized displacement vector $\underline{\mathbf{U}} = \{u_x \quad u_y \quad u_z \quad \varphi\}^T$ and transverse surface traction vector $\underline{\mathbf{T}}_z = \{\sigma_{xz} \quad \sigma_{yz} \quad \sigma_{zz} \quad D_z\}^T$ must be *continuous* through the laminate interfaces so that these ICC hold:

$$[\underline{\mathbf{U}}] = \underline{\mathbf{0}} \quad ; \quad [\underline{\mathbf{T}}_z] = \underline{\mathbf{0}} \quad (9)$$

With, $[*]$ denoting the jump in the value of the enclosed quantity across an interface.

The generalized strains vector is split into thickness (z), $\underline{\mathbf{S}}_z = \{\gamma_{xz} \quad \gamma_{yz} \quad \varepsilon_{zz} \quad -E_z\}^T$, and in-plane (p), $\underline{\mathbf{S}}_p = \{\varepsilon_{xx} \quad \varepsilon_{yy} \quad \gamma_{xy} \quad -E_x \quad -E_y\}^T$, contributions as:

$$\underline{\mathbf{S}}_z = \underline{\dot{\mathbf{U}}} + \underline{\mathbf{D}}_1 \underline{\mathbf{U}} \quad ; \quad \underline{\mathbf{S}}_p = \underline{\mathbf{D}}_2 \underline{\mathbf{U}} \quad (10)$$

Where,

$$\underline{\dot{\mathbf{U}}} = \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{U}}}{\partial z} \quad ; \quad \underline{\mathbf{D}}_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & \partial_x & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \partial_y & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad ; \quad \underline{\mathbf{D}}_2 = \begin{bmatrix} \partial_x & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \partial_y & 0 & 0 \\ \partial_y & \partial_x & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \partial_x \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \partial_y \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

Consequently, the *generalized* piezoelectric constitutive equation (7) can be bloc-decomposed as:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \underline{\mathbf{T}}_p \\ \underline{\mathbf{T}}_z \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{pp} & \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{pz} \\ \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{pz}^T & \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{zz} \end{Bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \underline{\mathbf{S}}_p \\ \underline{\mathbf{S}}_z \end{Bmatrix} \quad (12)$$

With, $\underline{\mathbf{T}}_p = \{\sigma_{xx} \quad \sigma_{yy} \quad \sigma_{xy} \quad D_x \quad D_y\}^T$ standing for the *in-plane* (p) generalized stress vector.

In the context of the *harmonic* vibration analysis, the time *variable* in (1) is transformed into a radial frequency ω so that the *Lagrange functional* associated to above local equations (1)-(12) can be written as:

$$\mathcal{L}(\underline{\mathbf{U}}, \underline{\dot{\mathbf{U}}}) = \int_{\Omega} L(\underline{\mathbf{U}}, \underline{\dot{\mathbf{U}}}) \, d\Omega - \int_{\Gamma_G} \underline{\mathbf{U}}^T \underline{\mathbf{G}} \, d\Gamma \quad (13)$$

Where, the Lagrangian density is:

$$\begin{aligned}L(\underline{\mathbf{U}}, \underline{\dot{\mathbf{U}}}) &= \frac{1}{2} \underline{\mathbf{S}}^T \underline{\mathbf{C}} \underline{\mathbf{S}} - \frac{1}{2} \rho \omega^2 \underline{\mathbf{U}}^T \underline{\mathbf{U}} \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \left[\underline{\mathbf{S}}_p^T \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{pp} \underline{\mathbf{S}}_p + 2 \underline{\mathbf{S}}_p^T \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{pz} \underline{\mathbf{S}}_z + \underline{\mathbf{S}}_z^T \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{zz} \underline{\mathbf{S}}_z \right] - \frac{1}{2} \rho \omega^2 \underline{\mathbf{U}}^T \underline{\mathbf{U}}\end{aligned}\quad (14)$$

Or, after substituting the decomposition (10):

$$\begin{aligned}L(\underline{\mathbf{U}}, \underline{\dot{\mathbf{U}}}) &= \frac{1}{2} \underline{\mathbf{U}}^T \underline{\mathbf{D}}_2^T \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{pp} \underline{\mathbf{D}}_2 \underline{\mathbf{U}} + \underline{\mathbf{U}}^T \underline{\mathbf{D}}_2^T \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{pz} \underline{\mathbf{D}}_1 \underline{\mathbf{U}} + \frac{1}{2} \underline{\mathbf{U}}^T \underline{\mathbf{D}}_1^T \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{zz} \underline{\mathbf{D}}_1 \underline{\mathbf{U}} + \underline{\mathbf{U}}^T \underline{\mathbf{D}}_2^T \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{pz} \underline{\dot{\mathbf{U}}} + \underline{\mathbf{U}}^T \underline{\mathbf{D}}_1^T \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{zz} \underline{\dot{\mathbf{U}}} + \\ &\quad \frac{1}{2} \underline{\dot{\mathbf{U}}}^T \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{zz} \underline{\dot{\mathbf{U}}} - \frac{1}{2} \rho \omega^2 \underline{\mathbf{U}}^T \underline{\mathbf{U}}\end{aligned}\quad (15)$$

The Lagrange functional (13) has to be stationary for the admissible solution $\underline{\mathbf{U}}$ so that this VF holds:

$$\int_{\Omega} \delta L(\underline{\mathbf{U}}, \underline{\dot{\mathbf{U}}}) \, d\Omega - \int_{\Gamma_G} \delta \underline{\mathbf{U}}^T \underline{\mathbf{G}} \, d\Gamma = 0 \quad (16)$$

The construction of the Hamiltonian *partial-mixed* VF corresponding to Eq. (16) requires first to determine the dual, or conjugate, variable to $\underline{\dot{\mathbf{U}}}$ (i.e. the generalized momentum $\underline{\mathbf{P}}$). This is achieved from Eq. (15) as follows:

$$\underline{\mathbf{P}} = \frac{\partial L}{\partial \underline{\dot{\mathbf{U}}}} = \frac{\partial L}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{S}}_z} \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{S}}_z}{\partial \underline{\dot{\mathbf{U}}}} = \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{pz}^T \underline{\mathbf{S}}_p + \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{zz} \underline{\mathbf{S}}_z \equiv \underline{\mathbf{T}}_z \quad (17)$$

Then, substituting Eq.(10) into Eq.(17) allows to eliminate $\underline{\dot{\mathbf{U}}}$ according to:

$$\underline{\dot{\mathbf{U}}} = \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{zz}^{-1} \underline{\mathbf{T}}_z - \underline{\mathbf{D}}_1 \underline{\mathbf{U}} - \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{zz}^{-1} \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{pz}^T \underline{\mathbf{D}}_2 \underline{\mathbf{U}} \quad (18)$$

The Lagrange functional density (15) thus writes as:

$$L(\underline{\mathbf{U}}, \underline{\mathbf{T}}_z) = \frac{1}{2} \underline{\mathbf{U}}^T \underline{\mathbf{D}}_2^T (\underline{\mathbf{C}}_{pp} - \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{pz} \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{zz}^{-1} \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{pz}^T) \underline{\mathbf{D}}_2 \underline{\mathbf{U}} + \frac{1}{2} \underline{\mathbf{T}}_z^T \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{zz}^{-1} \underline{\mathbf{T}}_z - \frac{1}{2} \rho \omega^2 \underline{\mathbf{U}}^T \underline{\mathbf{U}} \quad (19)$$

Now, the Hamiltonian energy density is now introduced via this Legendre transform:

$$H(\underline{\mathbf{U}}, \underline{\mathbf{T}}_z) = \underline{\mathbf{T}}_z^T \underline{\dot{\mathbf{U}}} - L(\underline{\mathbf{U}}, \underline{\mathbf{T}}_z) \quad (20)$$

Where, $\underline{\dot{\mathbf{U}}}$ is here also expressed in terms of $(\underline{\mathbf{U}}, \underline{\mathbf{T}}_z)$ according to Eq.(18). The following *Hamiltonian functional* is then obtained:

$$\mathcal{H}(\underline{\mathbf{U}}, \underline{\mathbf{T}}_z) = \int_{\Omega} [\underline{\mathbf{T}}_z^T \underline{\dot{\mathbf{U}}} - H(\underline{\mathbf{U}}, \underline{\mathbf{T}}_z)] d\Omega - \int_{\Gamma_G} \underline{\mathbf{U}}^T \underline{\mathbf{G}} d\Gamma \quad (21)$$

By taking the variations of the Hamiltonian functional (21) and grouping together the terms relative to the same virtual variable, the following variational equation holds:

$$\int_{\Omega} \delta \underline{\mathbf{U}}^T \left(-\underline{\dot{\mathbf{T}}}_z - \frac{\partial H}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{U}}} \right) d\Omega + \int_{\Omega} \delta \underline{\mathbf{T}}_z^T \left(\underline{\dot{\mathbf{U}}} - \frac{\partial H}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{T}}_z} \right) d\Omega + \int_{\Gamma_G} \delta \underline{\mathbf{U}}^T (\underline{\mathbf{T}}_z - \underline{\mathbf{G}}) d\Gamma = 0, \quad \forall \delta \underline{\mathbf{U}} / \delta \underline{\mathbf{U}}_{\Gamma_U} = \underline{\mathbf{0}} \quad (23)$$

Finally, by using Eqs. (19) and (20), the *Hamiltonian partial-mixed VF* writes as:

$$\int_{\Omega} \delta \underline{\mathbf{U}}^T \left(-\underline{\dot{\mathbf{T}}}_z + \left(\underline{\mathbf{D}}_2^T \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{pp}^* \underline{\mathbf{D}}_2 - \rho \omega^2 \right) \underline{\mathbf{U}} + \underline{\mathbf{D}}_1^T \underline{\mathbf{T}}_z + \underline{\mathbf{D}}_2^T \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{pz}^* \underline{\mathbf{T}}_z \right) d\Omega + \int_{\Omega} \delta \underline{\mathbf{T}}_z^T \left(\underline{\dot{\mathbf{U}}} - \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{zz}^* \underline{\mathbf{T}}_z + \underline{\mathbf{D}}_1 \underline{\mathbf{U}} + \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{pz}^{*T} \underline{\mathbf{D}}_2 \underline{\mathbf{U}} \right) d\Omega = 0 \quad (24)$$

$$\forall \underline{\mathbf{U}} / \underline{\mathbf{U}} = \underline{\tilde{\mathbf{U}}}(\Gamma_U) ; \quad \forall \underline{\mathbf{T}}_z / \underline{\mathbf{T}}_z = \underline{\mathbf{G}}(\Gamma_G) ; \quad (\Gamma_G) \quad \forall \delta \underline{\mathbf{U}} / \delta \underline{\mathbf{U}} = \underline{\mathbf{0}}(\Gamma_U) ; \quad \forall \delta \underline{\mathbf{T}}_z / \delta \underline{\mathbf{T}}_z = \underline{\mathbf{0}}(\Gamma_G)$$

in which the starred matrices are defined as:

$$\underline{\mathbf{C}}_{zz}^* = \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{zz}^{-1} ; \quad \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{pp}^* = \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{pp} - \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{pz} \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{zz}^{-1} \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{pz}^T ; \quad \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{pz}^* = \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{pz} \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{zz}^{-1} \quad (25)$$

2.2 Spectral FE discretization

In order to derive the general solution of the vibration problem in hand, the case of a *single-layer* piezoelectric plate is considered in a first step, for which the finite element (FE) in-plane discretization of the previous Hamiltonian partial-mixed VF is introduced. In a second step, this single-layer solution is extended to the *multilayer* case thanks to its dynamic stiffness (DS) formulation as described in the next section. The single-layer domain is thus decomposed into its in-plane area Σ and its thickness h . Let's then suppose that the primary variables $(\underline{\mathbf{U}}, \underline{\mathbf{T}}_z)$ at any point of the domain have the following separable discretization:

$$\underline{\mathbf{U}}(x, y, z) = \underline{\mathbf{N}}(x, y) \underline{\mathbf{U}}^*(\zeta) ; \quad \underline{\mathbf{T}}_z(x, y, z) = \underline{\mathbf{N}}(x, y) \underline{\mathbf{T}}_z^*(\zeta) \quad (26)$$

Where, $\underline{\mathbf{N}}(x, y)$ is the interpolation matrix containing the FE shape functions and ζ refers to the local thickness coordinate relative to the layer, whereas z denotes the global thickness coordinate. Substituting Eq. (26) into the VF (24) leads to its following discretized form:

$$\int_0^h \delta \underline{\mathbf{U}}^{*T} \left(-\underline{\tilde{\mathbf{N}}}_z \underline{\dot{\mathbf{T}}}_z^* + \underline{\tilde{\mathbf{B}}}_z \underline{\mathbf{U}}^* + \underline{\tilde{\mathbf{A}}}_z^T \underline{\mathbf{T}}_z^* \right) d\zeta + \int_0^h \delta \underline{\mathbf{T}}_z^{*T} \left(\underline{\tilde{\mathbf{N}}}_z \underline{\dot{\mathbf{U}}}^* + \underline{\tilde{\mathbf{A}}}_z \underline{\mathbf{U}}^* - \underline{\tilde{\mathbf{D}}}_z \underline{\mathbf{T}}_z^* \right) d\zeta = 0 \quad (27)$$

Where,

$$\begin{aligned}\underline{\underline{\tilde{\mathbf{N}}}} &= \int_{\Sigma} \underline{\underline{\mathbf{N}}}^T \underline{\underline{\mathbf{N}}} d\Sigma & \underline{\underline{\tilde{\mathbf{A}}}} &= \int_{\Sigma} \underline{\underline{\mathbf{N}}}^T \left(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{D}}}_1 + \underline{\underline{\mathbf{C}}}_{pz}^{*T} \underline{\underline{\mathbf{D}}}_2 \right) \underline{\underline{\mathbf{N}}} d\Sigma \\ \underline{\underline{\tilde{\mathbf{D}}}} &= \int_{\Sigma} \underline{\underline{\mathbf{N}}}^T \underline{\underline{\mathbf{C}}}_{zz}^{*T} \underline{\underline{\mathbf{N}}} d\Sigma & \underline{\underline{\tilde{\mathbf{B}}}} &= \int_{\Sigma} \underline{\underline{\mathbf{N}}}^T \left(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{D}}}_2^T \underline{\underline{\mathbf{C}}}_{pp}^{*T} \underline{\underline{\mathbf{D}}}_2 - \rho \omega^2 \mathbf{I} \right) \underline{\underline{\mathbf{N}}} d\Sigma\end{aligned}\quad (28)$$

and \mathbf{I} states for the identity matrix and Σ is the in-plane surface of the layer.

By invoking the arbitrariness of $\delta \underline{\underline{\mathbf{U}}}^{*T}$ and $\delta \underline{\underline{\mathbf{T}}}_z^{*T}$, Eq.(27) allows to reach this first-order differential system:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \underline{\underline{\dot{\mathbf{U}}}}^* \\ \underline{\underline{\dot{\mathbf{T}}}}_z^* \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -\underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}} & \underline{\underline{\mathbf{D}}} \\ \underline{\underline{\mathbf{B}}} & \underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}}^T \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \underline{\underline{\mathbf{U}}}}^* \\ \underline{\underline{\mathbf{T}}}_z^* \end{Bmatrix}\quad (29)$$

together with these BC at the bottom (b) and top (t) surfaces of the layer:

$$\begin{aligned}\underline{\underline{\mathbf{T}}}_z^{*b} &= -\underline{\underline{\mathbf{G}}}_b^* & (\Gamma_G^b) \\ \underline{\underline{\mathbf{T}}}_z^{*t} &= \underline{\underline{\mathbf{G}}}_t^* & (\Gamma_G^t)\end{aligned}\quad (30)$$

Where, the bloc matrices are defined by:

$$\underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}} = \underline{\underline{\tilde{\mathbf{N}}}}^{-1} \underline{\underline{\tilde{\mathbf{A}}}} ; \quad \underline{\underline{\mathbf{D}}} = \underline{\underline{\tilde{\mathbf{N}}}}^{-1} \underline{\underline{\tilde{\mathbf{D}}}} \quad \underline{\underline{\mathbf{B}}} = \underline{\underline{\tilde{\mathbf{N}}}}^{-1} \underline{\underline{\tilde{\mathbf{B}}}}\quad (31)$$

High-order spectral FE [6] are used in this approach, so that the matrix $\underline{\underline{\tilde{\mathbf{N}}}}$ can be identified with the identity matrix. The governing equations (29) are solved analytically and the corresponding DS matrix is now derived. Equation (29), relative to a given k -layer, can be rewritten in this condensed form:

$$\underline{\underline{\dot{\Psi}}}^k = \underline{\underline{\mathbf{H}}}^k \underline{\underline{\Psi}}^k\quad (32)$$

Its general solution expresses as $\underline{\underline{\Psi}}_{(z)}^k = \underline{\underline{\mathbf{e}}}^{\underline{\underline{\mathbf{H}}}^k z} \underline{\underline{\mathbf{c}}}^k$, where the classical Taylor series expansion is employed to evaluate the matrix exponential function so that $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{e}}}^{\underline{\underline{\mathbf{H}}}^k h_k} = \underline{\underline{\mathbf{Z}}}_k$. The integration constant vector $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{c}}}^k$ is moreover determined with the help of BC (30). On the one hand, the matrix exponential at the bottom surface $z_b = 0$ reduces to the identity matrix and $\underline{\underline{\Psi}}_{(z_b)}^k \equiv \underline{\underline{\mathbf{c}}}^k$ so that BC (30) gives:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \underline{\underline{\mathbf{U}}}_{(k)}^{b*} \\ -\underline{\underline{\mathbf{G}}}_{(k)}^{b*} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \underline{\underline{\mathbf{c}}}_1^k \\ \underline{\underline{\mathbf{c}}}_2^k \end{Bmatrix}\quad (33)$$

On the other hand, $\underline{\underline{\Psi}}_{(h_k)}^k \equiv \underline{\underline{\mathbf{Z}}}_k \underline{\underline{\mathbf{c}}}^k$ on the top surface $z_t = h_k$ of the layer so that BC (30) implies:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \underline{\underline{\mathbf{U}}}_{(k)}^{*t} \\ \underline{\underline{\mathbf{G}}}_{(k)}^{*t} \end{Bmatrix} = \underline{\underline{\mathbf{Z}}}_k \begin{Bmatrix} \underline{\underline{\mathbf{c}}}_1^k \\ \underline{\underline{\mathbf{c}}}_2^k \end{Bmatrix}\quad (34)$$

Further, Eqs. (33) and (34) allow to eliminate the constant $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{c}}}^k$ so that the DS problem of the k -th layer writes:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \underline{\underline{\mathbf{G}}}_{(k)}^{*b} \\ \underline{\underline{\mathbf{G}}}_{(k)}^{*t} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \underline{\underline{\mathbf{K}}}_k^{11} & \underline{\underline{\mathbf{K}}}_k^{12} \\ \underline{\underline{\mathbf{K}}}_k^{21} & \underline{\underline{\mathbf{K}}}_k^{22} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \underline{\underline{\mathbf{U}}}_{(k)}^{*b} \\ \underline{\underline{\mathbf{U}}}_{(k)}^{*t} \end{Bmatrix}\quad (35)$$

with:

$$\begin{aligned}\underline{\underline{\mathbf{K}}}_k^{11} &= \left[\underline{\underline{\mathbf{Z}}}_k^{12} \right]^{-1} \underline{\underline{\mathbf{Z}}}_k^{11} & ; & \quad \underline{\underline{\mathbf{K}}}_k^{12} = \left[\underline{\underline{\mathbf{Z}}}_k^{12} \right]^{-1} \\ \underline{\underline{\mathbf{K}}}_k^{21} &= \underline{\underline{\mathbf{Z}}}_k^{21} - \underline{\underline{\mathbf{Z}}}_k^{22} \left[\underline{\underline{\mathbf{Z}}}_k^{12} \right]^{-1} \underline{\underline{\mathbf{Z}}}_k^{11} & ; & \quad \underline{\underline{\mathbf{K}}}_k^{22} = \underline{\underline{\mathbf{Z}}}_k^{22} \left[\underline{\underline{\mathbf{Z}}}_k^{12} \right]^{-1}\end{aligned}\quad (36)$$

3 SOLUTION PROCEDURE

The analytical integration of the set of two-point boundary value problem (35) allows us to obtain the DS of a given layer in terms of its bottom and top surfaces variables. A procedure is now required to assemble this layer DS into a global one by enforcing ICC as well as the plate's edges BC. With the global DS at hand, the unknown circular frequencies are finally evaluated by solving a transcendental algebraic system, which is done with the help of W-W algorithm [4].

3.1 Application of the plate's BC

In the context of piezoelectric multilayer structure modelling, the issue of enforcement of the ICC is a difficult task. Straightforward fulfilment of the transverse stresses and electrical displacement variables ICC at the laminate interfaces is usually done in the framework of mixed VF. Therefore, thanks to a partial Legendre transformation, a four-field partial-mixed VF has been established in the previous section so that it inherits the algebraic properties of Hamiltonian matrices, facilitating the numerical implementation of ICC. However, the detailed inspection of this partial-mixed VF shows that it suffers from inconsistencies when dealing with arbitrary BC of the plate's edges. Namely, one can show that for BC other than the simply supported one, there is not anymore a one to one correspondence between the primary and conjugate nodal variables; the application of BC thus makes the final matrix rectangular so that the problem turns to be unsolvable. Here, in order to handle arbitrary BC i.e. any combination of simply supported, clamped and free BC, the boundary nodal variables have to be split into prescribed and unknown ones. This is formally equivalent to consider given BC and reactions at the plate's edges. The crux point of the proposed approach is that the identification of these two types of variables is done before integrating the equations along the thickness direction. The elimination of the prescribed degrees of freedom (DOF) is then performed by bearing in mind that the final resulting matrix must be square.

3.2 Dynamic stiffness computation and Wittrick-Williams algorithm's implementation

The problem is correctly formulated whatever the plate's edges BC as soon as the final equations write in the form of a first-order differential system equation with a square underlying coefficients matrix. The well-known W-W algorithm [4] can now be applied to compute the natural circular frequencies ω of the multilayered plate once the DS of the whole plate is formulated as before. The algorithm basically allows to compute the number of modes when ω is lower than a given trial radial frequency ω^* . The W-W algorithm originates from the Sturm sequence property for constrained systems and it states that the eigenvalue count $\mathbf{J}(\omega^*)$ is given by:

$$\mathbf{J}(\omega^*) = \mathbf{J}_0(\omega^*) + s \{ \underline{\mathbf{K}}(\omega^*) \} \quad (37)$$

Where, $\underline{\mathbf{K}}(\omega^*)$ is the DS of the whole plate and $s \{ \underline{\mathbf{K}}(\omega^*) \}$ is the signature of $\underline{\mathbf{K}}(\omega^*)$; that is, the number of its negative diagonal elements after an upper triangularization. Moreover, $\mathbf{J}_0(\omega^*)$ is given by:

$$\mathbf{J}_0(\omega^*) = \sum_{k=1}^N \mathbf{J}_0^k(\omega^*) \quad (38)$$

Where, $\mathbf{J}_0^k(\omega^*)$ refers to the number of eigenvalues in the frequency range $[0, \omega^*]$ when the upper and lower surfaces of the plate's k -th layer are clamped. The evaluation of $\mathbf{J}_0^k(\omega^*)$ is a crucial point to be fixed for applying the method. An explicit formulation of $\mathbf{J}_0^k(\omega^*)$ is actually out of reach in general, except for very basic systems with few DOF. Thus, a numerical evaluation of $\mathbf{J}_0^k(\omega^*)$ is adopted here. For this, we consider that a given plate's k -layer is made of a certain number of M sufficiently *thin numerical sublayers* so that no vibrations occur inside any of these s -th thin sublayer when its external faces are clamped. Under this hypothesis, we can state that:

$$\mathbf{J}_0^{k,s}(\omega^*) = 0, \quad \forall s = 1:M \quad (39)$$

$\mathbf{J}_0^k(\omega^*)$ is then computed *recursively* by assembling each thin sublayer's DS $\underline{\mathbf{K}}_k^s$ into an overall DS $\underline{\mathbf{K}}_k(\omega^*)$ for the k -th layer. $\mathbf{J}_0(\omega^*)$ is next calculated thanks to Eq.(38) and $\mathbf{J}(\omega^*)$ is evaluated with the help of Eq. (37) after assembling each layer's DS $\underline{\mathbf{K}}_k(\omega^*)$ into an overall one $\underline{\mathbf{K}}(\omega^*)$.

Now the eigenvalues count $\mathbf{J}(\omega^*)$ for a given radial frequency range $[0, \omega^*]$ is known, the well-established bisection method can be implemented to determine all circular frequencies within this range without missing any.

4 NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

In this section, some numerical tests are presented to assess the performance of the proposed new Hamiltonian semi-analytical approach for vibration analysis of piezoelectric multilayered plate. For this, two test cases are considered: in order to show the convergence and accuracy of the present approach, the vibration analysis of a homogenous cantilever piezoelectric plate is first performed [7]; then, the test case of a fully clamped piezoelectric multilayer cross-ply plate is analyzed [8]. The numerical tests are performed with a fixed 2x2 high-order spectral FE mesh with variable number N (up to 8x8 per element) of Gauss-Legendre-Lobatto grid points.

4.1 Single layer piezoelectric cantilever rectangular plate

Consider a single layer piezoceramic cantilever plate having these e-form electromechanical properties: $C_{11} = 107.6$ GPa, $C_{12} = 63.12$ GPa, $C_{13} = 63.85$ GPa, $C_{33} = 100.4$ GPa, $C_{44} = 19.62$ GPa, $C_{66} = 22.24$ GPa, $e_{31} = -9.6$ N/Vm, $e_{33} = 15.1$ N/Vm, $e_{15} = 12$ N/Vm, $\varepsilon_{11}/\varepsilon_0 = 1110$, $\varepsilon_{33}/\varepsilon_0 = 852$, $\varepsilon_0 = 8.85 \cdot 10^{-12}$ F/m, $\rho = 7760$ kg/m³. The plate has a rectangular shape and its dimensions along x , y , z are $a=20$ mm, $b=40$ mm and $h=1.5$ mm. The electric BCs are short-circuit ones; that is, $\varphi=0$ on the upper and lower plate's surfaces. A comparison is made with experimental and 3D ABAQUS FEM results [7]. Table 1 lists the results obtained with increasing orders of spectral elements; the numbers between brackets show the errors defined as: Error (%) = (Present-FEM)/FEM. As one can see, a good agreement is observed in comparison with 3D FEM results. The table shows also that 6th order spectral element is sufficient to compute the third mode. Moreover, convergence is achieved with a 4th order element when computing the first two modes. This confirms the good performance of the present semi-analytical approach in conjunction with W-W algorithm to compute the natural frequencies of a vibrating piezoelectric plate.

Table 1: Convergence analysis for a cantilever single layer rectangular piezoelectric plate (Hz)

Mode	[7]		Present			
	Exp.	FEM	2x2	4x4	6x6	8x8
1	2940	2905	2910 (0.17)	2909 (0.14)	2907 (0.06)	2908 (0.1)
2	3270	3233	3321 (2.72)	3238 (0.15)	3235 (0.06)	3235 (0.06)
3	7320	7243	7448 (2.83)	7291 (0.67)	7250 (0.1)	7250 (0.1)

4.2 Five layers cross-ply piezoelectric fully clamped square plate

A fully clamped (CCCC) square piezoelectric laminate of thickness $h = 0.01$ m and side length a is now analyzed. The plate's lay-up consists of a (0°/90°/0°) Graphite-Epoxy sublaminar bonded by two PZT-4 outer layers. Each piezoelectric layer has a thickness of $0.1 h$ whereas each elastic composite layer has a thickness of $0.267 h$. Three geometric configurations with side-to-thickness ratios $a/h = 4, 10$ and 50 are analyzed. The relevant materials properties are: $E_1 = E_2 = 81.3$ GPa, $E_3 = 64.5$ GPa, $\nu_{12} = 0.329$, $\nu_{13} = \nu_{23} = 0.432$, $G_{12} = 30.6$ GPa, $G_{13} = G_{23} = 25.6$ GPa, $e_{31} = e_{32} = -5.20$ Cm⁻², $e_{33} = 15.08$ Cm⁻², $e_{15} = e_{24} = 12.72$ Cm⁻², $\varepsilon_{11}/\varepsilon_0 = \varepsilon_{22}/\varepsilon_0 = 1475$, $\varepsilon_{33}/\varepsilon_0 = 1300$ for PZT-4 and $E_1 = 132.38$ GPa, $E_2 = E_3 = 10.756$, $\nu_{12} = \nu_{13} = 0.24$, $\nu_{23} = 0.49$, $G_{12} = G_{13} = 5.654$ GPa, $G_{23} = 3.606$ GPa, $\varepsilon_{11}/\varepsilon_0 = 3.5$, $\varepsilon_{22}/\varepsilon_0 = \varepsilon_{33}/\varepsilon_0 = 3.0$ for Graphite-Epoxy. The electric potential at all edges around the plate is specified to zero; the plate's upper and lower surfaces are also grounded. However, the inner surfaces of the piezoelectric layers are assumed non-electroded so that the electric potential and transverse electric displacement are continuous at the interfaces. Table 2 compares the fundamental radial frequency (in rad/s) computed by the present approach with those of [8], obtained by a spline finite strip method. It is observed that the converged results for the herein proposed approach are in close agreement with the reference ones. Moreover, thanks to the analytic integration of Eq. (32) along the thickness direction, the present approach does not exhibit the shear locking phenomena for high side-to-thickness ratio. Figures 1 and 2 provide the through-thickness distributions of some primary variables to show the ability of the present approach to satisfy the ICC without any post-processing.

Table 2: Fundamental Circular frequency (rad/s) of a CCCC piezoelectric square cross-ply $[0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ]$ plate

Method	$\omega/100$ in rad/s		
	a/h=4	a/h=10	a/h=50
[8]	69.804	19.924	1110.5
Present (8x8)	69.895	19.906	1111.7
Error (%)	0.13	-0.09	0.11

Figure 1: Fundamental mode cross-thickness distributions of $u(\frac{a}{2}, \frac{b}{2}, z)$ and $\varphi(\frac{a}{2}, \frac{b}{2}, z)$, $\frac{a}{h} = 4$ for a five plies multilayered CCCC square plate.

Figure 2: Fundamental mode cross-thickness distributions of $\sigma_{yz}(\frac{a}{2}, \frac{b}{2}, z)$ and $D_z(\frac{a}{2}, \frac{b}{2}, z)$, $\frac{a}{h} = 4$ for five-ply multilayered CCCC square plate..

5 CONCLUSIONS

This work presents a new approach for the vibration analysis of piezoelectric multilayered plates. The formulation leads to a partially-mixed Hamiltonian VF. The in-plane dimensions are discretized with 2D High-

Order FEM whereas the solution along the thickness is expressed analytically using a matrix exponential function. W-W algorithm is then implemented to compute the natural frequencies of the piezoelectric composite plate. A comparison with reference solutions from the literature highlights the accuracy and fast convergence of the proposed approach.

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CONTINUUM MODELING AND FINITE ELEMENT SIMULATION OF INCOMPRESSIBLE DIELECTRIC VISCOELASTIC ACTUATORS AT FINITE STRAINS

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Abstract. Dielectric elastomers, known for their ability to undergo large deformations exceeding 100%, are widely used as actuators in adaptive structures and soft robotics. Within the current contribution, we present a continuum material model that captures the incompressibility and viscous behavior of these polymers under finite strain and electric actuation. To address large deformations, we use a multiplicative decomposition of the deformation gradient to separate elastic and viscous effects. The elastic response is represented by a Yeoh potential, which is well suited to describe the material behavior under large strains. The evolution of internal strains is modeled using a dissipation function. Electric field and dielectric displacement are modeled in spatial configuration, leading to an electromechanically coupled problem. We propose a mixed finite element formulation within a variational framework based on the above thermodynamic principles. We introduce a novel approach using volume-preserving tensor-valued elements for internal strains, where we make use of matrix exponential functions to achieve incompressibility exactly. As an example, we consider an experimental setup of a three-dimensional circular actuator. We provide material parameters for VHB4910 for the proposed model, and compare our results to experimental data from a different work.

Keywords: electromechanical coupling, electro-active polymers, viscoelasticity

1 INTRODUCTION

Due to their ability to undergo significant deformations exceeding 100%, dielectric elastomers are frequently used as actuators in adaptive structures or soft robotics applications. In this contribution, we provide a phenomenological continuum material model respecting the nearly incompressible nature of these polymers as well as their viscous characteristics at finite strain in a coupled electro-mechanic setting. Regarding applications there is a great need in the field of soft robotics but also in the area of sensor development. We cite Guo [5] and O'Halloran [12], both of which provide a comprehensive overview concerning the application of such dielectric elastomers. As mentioned in Wissler [13], it is of high interest to predict the behavior of such dielectric elastomers. In many cases only analytic models using linear or non-linear elastic characteristics have been proposed for strongly simplified problem setups, often neglecting three-dimensional effects or the viscoelastic behavior.

For the basic concepts of modeling such large-deformation electro-elastic materials, we cite the comprehensive monograph by Maugin [8] and the more recent review article by Dorfmann and Ogden [4]. Ask et al. [1] provide a phenomenological material model for electrostrictive viscoelastic polymers at finite strain. Kunzemann et al. [7] developed a similar thermodynamically consistent model

for incompressible viscoelastic polymers, which is suitable for finite element discretization. Within this framework, we develop a phenomenological material model for nearly incompressible, dielectric, viscoelastic polymers. To address large deformations, we apply a multiplicative decomposition of the deformation gradient to differentiate between elastic and viscous effects (cf. [1]). The elastic response is modeled using a Yeoh potential. Various intermediate configurations represent the subsystems of a classical linear Wiechert model in the current setting of finite strains. Viscoelastic dissipation is captured through a dedicated dissipation function, which ensures that the Clausius-Duhem inequality is respected locally. Thus, the material model is considered thermodynamically consistent. Electric quantities and electrostatic field equations must be considered with respect to the actual spatial configuration of the body, which results in an electromechanically coupled problem.

We introduce a mixed finite element formulation that incorporates these aspects within a variational framework. In many finite element methods, elastic deformation is modeled using classical or advanced linear or quadratic elements, while viscous strains are represented at integration points. We propose a different approach that employs independent tensor-valued elements for internal strains. Discretizing these internal strains is challenging due to their volume-preserving nature. We use matrix exponential functions to achieve an exactly volume-preserving representation of these strains in our finite element method.

As an example, we consider a three-dimensional model of a circular actuator that was first described in [13]. The acrylic elastomer VHB4910 is used as base material, where the necessary material parameters were determined in the original reference [13]. A comparison to measurements and simulation results provided there is established.

2 CONSTITUTIVE MODEL FOR DIELECTRIC VISCOELASTIC SOLIDS

In this present work a body \mathcal{B} made of viscoelastic and dielectric material is considered. In the undeformed reference configuration, let \mathbf{X} be the coordinates of any material point \mathcal{P} . Under deformation, we denote \mathbf{x} as the spatial coordinates of \mathcal{P} , and $\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{x} - \mathbf{X}$ as the displacement field. The deformation gradient is defined in the standard way as $\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{I} + \text{Grad } \mathbf{u} = \mathbf{I} + \partial \mathbf{u} / \partial \mathbf{X}$. Here and in the following, uppercase differential operators such as the gradient Grad, rotation Curl and divergence Div indicate derivation with respect to material coordinates \mathbf{X} , whereas lowercase operators, like grad, curl, and div describe derivatives with respect to spatial coordinates \mathbf{x} . The Jacobi determinant $J = \det \mathbf{F}$ represents the change of volume during deformation.

It is common to split the deformation gradient into its volumetric and isochoric parts, especially for incompressible or nearly incompressible materials. In this context, isochoric quantities will be labeled with a hat symbol, $\mathbf{F} = J^{1/3} \hat{\mathbf{F}}$. To form the constitutive equations we additionally need the right Cauchy-Green tensor \mathbf{C} and its isochoric part $\hat{\mathbf{C}}$, defined by,

$$\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{F}^\top \cdot \mathbf{F}, \quad \hat{\mathbf{C}} = \hat{\mathbf{F}}^\top \cdot \hat{\mathbf{F}} = J^{-2/3} \mathbf{C}. \quad (1)$$

Similar to the work of [1], we decompose the isochoric deformation gradient multiplicatively into an elastic part $\hat{\mathbf{F}}_{e,i}$ and a viscoelastic part $\mathbf{F}_{v,i}$,

$$\hat{\mathbf{F}} = \hat{\mathbf{F}}_{e,i} \cdot \mathbf{F}_{v,i}, \text{ for } i \in \{1, \dots, N\}. \quad (2)$$

With this extension to the classical linear Wiechert model, we have to deal with N independent stress-free, volume-preserving *intermediate* configurations, see e.g. [7]. In our model, the viscoelastic part of

the deformation gradient is assumed to be volume preserving, which implies the kinematic constraint $\det \mathbf{F}_{v,i} \equiv 1$. According to (2), the i^{th} elastic isochoric part of the deformation gradient is given by $\hat{\mathbf{F}}_{e,i} = \hat{\mathbf{F}} \cdot \mathbf{F}_{v,i}^{-1}$ and the corresponding elastic and viscoelastic Cauchy-Green tensors are defined as,

$$\hat{\mathbf{C}}_{e,i} = \hat{\mathbf{F}}_{e,i}^\top \cdot \hat{\mathbf{F}}_{e,i} = \mathbf{F}_{v,i}^{-\top} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{C}} \cdot \mathbf{F}_{v,i}^{-1}, \quad \mathbf{C}_{v,i} = \mathbf{F}_{v,i}^\top \cdot \mathbf{F}_{v,i}. \quad (3)$$

Regarding the actuation, we assume that modeling in electrostatic regime is justified. Here, the electric field \mathbf{e} and the dielectric displacement \mathbf{d} are of interest, which are both regarded as fields in spatial configuration. From Faraday's law, $\text{curl } \mathbf{e} = 0$, we deduce that the electric field \mathbf{e} is a gradient field, meaning that it can be expressed as the negative gradient of the electric potential field ϕ , $\mathbf{e} = -\text{grad } \phi$. Gauss' law implies that the dielectric displacement field \mathbf{d} must be divergence-free in the spatial configuration for non-conducting materials (no free charges), $\text{div } \mathbf{d} = 0$. As a simplification, which can be justified for thin, electroded dielectric structures, the electric field is modeled only in the material, effects from the surrounding air or vacuum are not taken into account, [4]. To transform the above fields from the spatial to the material configuration, we introduce the pull-back of the electric field \mathbf{e} and dielectric displacement \mathbf{d} to their material counterparts, denoted by capital letters,

$$\mathbf{E} = \mathbf{F}^\top \cdot \mathbf{e} = -\text{Grad } \phi, \quad \mathbf{D} = \mathbf{J}\mathbf{F}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{d}. \quad (4)$$

We now develop a thermodynamically consistent model for electroactive viscoelastic materials. Therefore, we define the free energy density Ψ for independent Cauchy-Green tensor \mathbf{C} , viscoelastic tensors $\mathbf{C}_{v,i}$, which will serve as internal variables, and electric field \mathbf{E} . The free energy density is defined additively through several independent potentials: a hyperelastic potential Ψ_∞ describing the long term behavior, viscoelastic energy densities $\Psi_{v,i}$ and a dielectric potential Ψ_{el}^{aug} , which is augmented to include the effect of vacuum permittivity,

$$\Psi(\mathbf{C}, \mathbf{C}_{v,i}, \mathbf{E}) = \Psi_\infty(\mathbf{C}) + \sum_{i=1}^N \Psi_{v,i}(\hat{\mathbf{C}}, \mathbf{C}_{v,i}) + \Psi_{el}^{aug}(\mathbf{C}, \mathbf{E}). \quad (5)$$

We describe the specific choices for the energy densities that make up the augmented free energy Ψ . In this study, the elastic component of the free energy Ψ_∞ will be defined by a nearly incompressible Yeoh hyperelastic potential,

$$\Psi_\infty(\mathbf{C}) = C_{10}^\infty (\text{tr } \mathbf{C} - 3) + C_{20}^\infty (\text{tr } \mathbf{C} - 3)^2 + C_{30}^\infty (\text{tr } \mathbf{C} - 3)^3 + \frac{1}{D_1} (J - 1)^2, \quad (6)$$

with C_{10}^∞ , C_{20}^∞ and C_{30}^∞ being the Yeoh parameters describing the long term behavior and D_1 denoting the compressibility parameter. Concerning the i^{th} multiplicative decomposition, an incompressible Yeoh hyperelastic potential models the elastic energy for $\hat{\mathbf{C}}_{e,i}$ instead. As $\text{tr } \hat{\mathbf{C}}_{e,i} = \hat{\mathbf{C}} : \mathbf{C}_{v,i}^{-1}$, we use the representation,

$$\Psi_{v,i}(\hat{\mathbf{C}}, \mathbf{C}_{v,i}) = C_{10}^{v,i} \left(\hat{\mathbf{C}} : \mathbf{C}_{v,i}^{-1} - 3 \right) + C_{20}^{v,i} \left(\hat{\mathbf{C}} : \mathbf{C}_{v,i}^{-1} - 3 \right)^2 + C_{30}^{v,i} \left(\hat{\mathbf{C}} : \mathbf{C}_{v,i}^{-1} - 3 \right)^3, \quad (7)$$

with $C_{10}^{v,i}$, $C_{20}^{v,i}$ and $C_{30}^{v,i}$ being the Yeoh parameters describing the viscoelastic behavior.

Last, the dielectric potential, represented by Ψ_{el}^{aug} , describes the behavior of polarization within the material. In an isotropic linear dielectric material, this contribution is described by the materials relative electric susceptibility χ . We define Ψ_{el}^{aug} by,

$$\Psi_{el}^{aug}(\mathbf{C}, \mathbf{E}) = -\frac{1}{2} \epsilon_0 (\chi + J) \mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{C}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{E}, \quad (8)$$

see also [6]. In this context, ϵ_0 is the permittivity of vacuum.

In order to define the constitutive equations, we use the framework of the Clausius-Duhem inequality, which states the non-negativity of dissipation \mathcal{D} . In the current setting, \mathcal{D} can be described by,

$$\mathcal{D} = \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{T} : \dot{\mathbf{C}} - \mathbf{D} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{E}} - \dot{\Psi} \geq 0. \quad (9)$$

In this context, \mathbf{T} is the total second Piola-Kirchhoff stress, \mathbf{D} the material dielectric displacement. Again, $\dot{\mathbf{C}}$, $\dot{\mathbf{E}}$, $\dot{\Psi}$ are each the rate of the right Cauchy-Green tensor, of the electric field and of the augmented free energy. By computing $\dot{\Psi}$ explicitly, equation (9) becomes,

$$\mathcal{D} = - \left(\frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \mathbf{C}} - \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{T} \right) : \dot{\mathbf{C}} - \left(\frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \mathbf{E}} + \mathbf{D} \right) : \dot{\mathbf{E}} - \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \mathbf{C}_{v,i}} : \dot{\mathbf{C}}_{v,i} \geq 0. \quad (10)$$

Dissipation \mathcal{D} is explicitly defined through the choice of a dissipation function Φ ,

$$\mathcal{D} = \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial \dot{\mathbf{C}}_{v,i}} : \dot{\mathbf{C}}_{v,i} \geq 0. \quad (11)$$

This implicitly defines the rate of the viscoelastic Cauchy-Green tensor $\dot{\mathbf{C}}_{v,i}$ by using the Clausius-Duhem inequality of equation (10). The dissipation function Φ is also composed additively from contributions due to the N internal variables $\mathbf{C}_{v,i}$. To be specific, we use,

$$\Phi = \sum_{i=1}^N \Phi_i(\mathbf{C}_{v,i}, \dot{\mathbf{C}}_{v,i}), \quad \text{with} \quad \Phi_i(\mathbf{C}_{v,i}, \dot{\mathbf{C}}_{v,i}) = \frac{1}{12} \sum_{i=1}^N \eta_i (\mathbf{C}_{v,i}^{-1} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{C}}_{v,i}) : (\mathbf{C}_{v,i}^{-1} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{C}}_{v,i}). \quad (12)$$

In the work of Wissler [13], two sets of material parameters are provided. Both contain the Yeoh parameters, C_{10} , C_{20} , C_{30} , defining the instantaneous response, and Prony parameters g_i , τ_i for $N = 4$. Since we base the material characterization on the longterm parameters, these still have to be converted accordingly, same applies to the viscoelastic parts,

$$C_{j0}^\infty = C_{j0} \left(1 - \sum_{i=1}^N g_i \right), \quad C_{j0}^{v,i} = C_{j0} g_i, \quad \text{for } i \in \{1, \dots, N\}, j \in \{1, 2, 3\}. \quad (13)$$

Since there is no further information on the compression parameter D_1 , we define it by Poisson's ratio ν , resulting in,

$$D_1 = \frac{1 - 2\nu}{2C_{10}\nu}. \quad (14)$$

In the dissipation function, each of the terms is governed by a viscosity parameter η_i , which is given by,

$$\eta_i = 6g_i\tau_i C_{10}, \quad \text{for } i \in \{1, \dots, N\}. \quad (15)$$

3 INCREMENTAL MINIMIZATION PRINCIPLE AND FINITE ELEMENTS

In this section, we aim at developing a finite element formulation for viscoelastic solids using an incremental variational formulation. The approach follows a minimization principle, which has been widely employed in the modeling of dissipative processes, including viscoelasticity, as presented by Miehe et al. (cf. [9, 10, 11]). Since the following example can be seen as quasi-static, we do not take the kinetic part into account, also no effects due to gravity will be governed.

For a finite time step $[t_0, t_0 + \Delta t]$ with known initial conditions at time t_0 , we define the *incremental potential* over the time step as:

$$\Pi_t^{t+\Delta t} = \int_{t_0}^{t_0+\Delta t} (\dot{\Psi} + \Phi) dt, \quad (16)$$

where the different terms represent the following energy contributions:

$$\Pi_t^{t+\Delta t} = \underbrace{\Psi_{t_0+\Delta t} - \Psi_{t_0}}_{\text{stored}} + \underbrace{\int_{t_0}^{t_0+\Delta t} \Phi dt}_{\text{dissipated}}. \quad (17)$$

The incremental potential $\Pi_{t_0}^{t_0+\Delta t}$ is then minimized with respect to all admissible displacements and viscoelastic internal variables, while being maximized with respect to the electric field. For a time step size Δt approaching zero, we arrive at,

$$\dot{\Psi} + \Phi \rightarrow \min_{\dot{\mathbf{u}}} \min_{\dot{\mathbf{C}}_{v,i}} \max_{\dot{\mathbf{E}}}. \quad (18)$$

We can now rewrite equation (18) for the specific choice of the free energy Ψ , resulting in,

$$\frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \mathbf{C}} : \dot{\mathbf{C}} + \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \mathbf{C}_{v,i}} : \dot{\mathbf{C}}_{v,i} + \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \mathbf{E}} \cdot \delta \dot{\mathbf{E}} + \Phi \rightarrow \min_{\dot{\mathbf{u}}} \min_{\dot{\mathbf{C}}_{v,i}} \max_{\dot{\mathbf{E}}}. \quad (19)$$

Variation of the optimization problem (19) yields, for kinematically admissible virtual displacements $\delta \mathbf{u}$, $\delta \mathbf{C}_{v,i}$ and $\delta \mathbf{E}$,

$$\int_{\mathcal{B}} \left(\frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \mathbf{C}} : \delta \mathbf{C} + \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \mathbf{C}_{v,i}} : \delta \mathbf{C}_{v,i} + \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \mathbf{E}} \cdot \delta \mathbf{E} \right) dV + \int_{\mathcal{B}} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial \dot{\mathbf{C}}_{v,i}} : \delta \dot{\mathbf{C}}_{v,i} dV = 0. \quad (20)$$

With regard to spatial discretization, we assume $\mathcal{T} = \{T\}$ to be a prismatic triangular finite element mesh of the section of \mathcal{B} . The displacement \mathbf{u} is represented by continuous basis functions $\mathbf{N}_i^{(u)}$ with the approximation order k . The electric potential is also discretized by a continuous basis function with the same order,

$$\mathbf{u} = \sum_{i=1}^{n_u} q_i^{(u)} \mathbf{N}_i^{(u)}, \quad \phi = \sum_{i=1}^{n_\phi} q_i^{(\phi)} \mathbf{N}_i^{(\phi)}. \quad (21)$$

Moreover, kinematic boundary conditions $\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{0}$ on boundary part Γ_{fix} and also $\phi = \phi_0$ on the electroded boundary Γ_{el} have to be satisfied.

The approximation of the viscoelastic internal variables $\mathbf{C}_{v,i}$ can be achieved by using the viscoelastic strain tensor $\mathbf{S}_{v,i}$ containing the independent viscoelastic strains $s_{i,xx}$, $s_{i,yy}$, $s_{i,xy}$, $s_{i,xz}$ and $s_{i,yz}$. This can be challenging due to their volume-preserving nature. To address this, we use matrix exponential functions to achieve an exact representation of these strains,

$$\mathbf{S}_{v,i} = \begin{bmatrix} s_{i,xx} & s_{i,xy} & s_{i,xz} \\ s_{i,xy} & s_{i,yy} & s_{i,yz} \\ s_{i,xz} & s_{i,yz} & -s_{i,xx} - s_{i,yy} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{C}_{v,i} = \exp(2\mathbf{S}_{v,i}). \quad (22)$$

The viscoelastic strains $s_{i,\alpha\beta}$ are discretized by piecewise polynomials of approximation order $k - 1$, one order less than displacement and electric potential.

Concerning the evaluation of the matrix exponential function, we use a high-order Taylor approximation,

$$\mathbf{C}_{v,i} = \exp(2\mathbf{S}_{v,i}) \simeq \mathbf{I} + 2\mathbf{S}_{v,i} + 2\mathbf{S}_{v,i}^2 + \dots + \frac{2^n}{n!} \mathbf{S}_{v,i}^n, \quad (23)$$

with n the order of the series expansion. In order to handle the occurrence of high viscoelastic strains in the simulation, choosing a high order is necessary. The choice $n = 30$ will prove sufficient in the numerical example. Since the example is considered quasi-static, the rate of the viscoelastic strains is approximated in a backward Euler time-stepping scheme

$$\dot{s}_{i,\alpha\beta} = \frac{1}{\Delta t} (s_{i,\alpha\beta}(t + \Delta t) - s_{i,\alpha\beta}(t)). \quad (24)$$

With the rate of the viscoelastic strains $\dot{s}_{i,\alpha\beta}$, the rate of the strain tensor $\dot{\mathbf{S}}_{v,i}$ is provided. The rate of the viscoelastic Cauchy-Green tensor then follows as,

$$\dot{\mathbf{C}}_{v,i} = \text{Sym} \left(2\dot{\mathbf{S}}_{v,i} \exp(2\mathbf{S}_{v,i}) \right). \quad (25)$$

4 COMPUTATIONAL IMPLEMENTATION AND RESULTS

We test our formulation against the measurements provided in the work of Wissler [13]. There, the authors aimed at creating a corresponding model for the acrylic elastomer VHB4910 in a Yeoh and Prony series representation, and to verifying this model for a circular actuator. The characterization was done by performing relaxation and tensile tests with a rectangular specimen with a thickness of 1 mm. For the actuator, a circular specimen was pre-stretched radially up to a radial strain of $s_{pre} = 308\%$, resulting in an outer radius of $R = 75$ mm and a thickness of $t = 0.06$ mm, as seen in Figure 1. This configuration is held in a frame for 1 hour, after which a circular area with $r_0 = 22$ mm is coated with beaten gold on the upper and lower surface to form electrodes. Within 5 seconds, a voltage is applied linearly up to a limit value of 3.5 kV. This voltage is then held constant for a another 175 seconds, which causes the coated surface to expand, as indicated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Circular actuator

Table 1: fitted material parameters.

Parameter	Unit	Wissler [13]	current
C_{10}	MPa	0.0693	0.0693
C_{20}	MPa	-9.88×10^{-4}	-9.88×10^{-4}
C_{30}	MPa	16.7×10^{-6}	16.7×10^{-6}
g_1	-	0.547	0.493
g_2	-	0.198	0.250
g_3	-	0.110	0.0929
g_4	-	0.0384	0.0628
t_1	s	0.135	2.980
t_2	s	0.382	49.462
t_3	s	37.1	299.679
t_4	s	217	5564.668

First, we tried to use the parameters directly in our formulation, and reproduce the measurements from the relaxation tests. As expected, the results did not agree perfectly; in the original work [13] the large deformation viscoelastic model is formulated in a different manner as proposed here. Instead, we used the relaxation test data for the largest nominal strain of 500 % and fitted the viscoelastic parameters g_i and τ_i for our model, while keeping the instantaneous hyperelastic response as characterized though the Yeoh parameters the same. Optimization using a non-linear bounded least squares algorithm leads to the results depicted in Figure 2. The green markers represent the measurements, the orange dashed curve shows the simulation with the original parameters from [13], and the blue curve displays the simulation with the new fitted parameters, which are shown in Table 1 as *current*. The implemented geometry for the finite element analysis can be seen in Figure 3. Due to symmetries, the geometry can be simplified with corresponding boundary conditions on the two faces. The in-plane displacements u_x and u_y are set to zero on these surfaces, respectively. Vertical displacement $u_z = 0$ is prohibited on the bottom circumferential edge, as the sample becomes significantly thinner, whereas the radial displacement is prescribed matching the pre-strain on the circumferential face. To achieve the given pre-stretch $s_{pre} = 3.08$, the initial radius was set to $R_0 = R/(1 + s_{pre})$ resulting in $R_0 = 18.38$ mm. The finite element mesh consists of 212 prismatic triangular elements. Due to the thin structure, two layers of third order prismatic elements are used to prevent locking. This leads to a total of 10731 degrees of freedom for the displacement, 1225 degrees of freedom for the electric field and 76320 degrees of freedom for the viscoelastic strains.

Figure 2: Relaxation experiment

The electrodes were defined circular on the upper and lower surfaces, with pre-stretched radius r_0 . To improve convergence, the electric field is only modeled in the section directly between the electrodes. This simplification is justified mainly due to the thin structure, shown in Figure 4, as no significant electric field is expected in the outer region. In [13], the given electric susceptibility χ is expected to be $\chi = 4.7$. However, in a more recent work [3], the susceptibility of VHB4910 was characterized in large strain regime around $\chi = 4.1$, which we use in our computations. Last, the compression parameter D_1 was defined by using equation (14), using a Poisson's ration of $\nu = 0.44$, which has been characterized by [2].

Figure 3: Circular actuator - Implementation

Figure 4: electric field distribution

To measure the effect of the electric field, the radial expansion at the transition between the electrode and the sample was used. The original radius after pre-stretching r_0 is set in relation to the current radius r_1 to calculate the nominal radial strain,

$$s_r = \frac{r_1}{r_0} - 1. \quad (26)$$

Figure 5: Measured and calculated nominal radial strain

Figure 5 represents the comparison of the nominal radial strain between simulation and measurements. The blue line indicates the numerical results, whereas the measurements are marked in green. The red curve shows the prescribed electric potential over time. The contours of the two results are similar, but there is a noticeable offset. In computations, we see sensitivity with respect to both the choice of the electric susceptibility χ and the Poisson ratio ν .

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MIXED SHELL ELEMENTS FOR INCOMPRESSIBLE VISCOELASTIC DIELECTRIC ELASTOMERS

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Abstract. The focus of this work lies on modeling and simulation of thin dielectric viscoelastic structures undergoing large deformations of 100% and beyond. A shell formulation is developed that incorporates the necessary kinematic and constitutive features to capture the structure’s characteristics under transient electric loads. This includes the incorporation of not only elastic and viscous membrane strains and curvature, but also thickness deformation and variation of the electric field through the thickness. A model based on the second principle of thermodynamics is presented, which is then discretized using low-regularity shell elements in a variational setting. Computational results prove the accuracy and efficiency of the proposed method.

Keywords: Dielectric shell; Viscoelasticity; Mixed formulation.

1 INTRODUCTION

The usage of electro-active polymers in smart structures is increasing, not least due to their ability to undergo deformations beyond 100% under electric stimulation. However, accurate modeling of their behavior remains a significant challenge as it involves the interplay of mechanical, electrical and viscoelastic effects. Within this work, we focus on modeling the elastic and viscous characteristics of thin dielectric plates.

When designing a dielectric actuator, compliant electrodes are placed on the surfaces of a thin, often pre-stretched structure. Under application of an electric voltage, electrodes are pulled towards each other due to Maxwell stresses in the dielectric material; the structure contracts in thickness direction. For an incompressible elastomer, this change in thickness implies in-plane extension, which is used for actuation. Such concepts have been proposed and modeled e.g. by Klinkel et al. [1] or Kadapa and Hossain [2], see also the review on soft robotics by Gu et al. [3]. Often, these elastomers are modeled purely elastic. Several authors have proposed to include viscoelastic relaxation to obtain more accurate results; we cite Bishara and Jabareen [4] and Mehnert et al. [5].

When discretizing thin structures using a volumetric finite element mesh, continuum mechanics material models can be transferred to the computational method directly. However, locking effects are expected in computations in view of the thin-walled nature of structures. Several authors have proposed techniques to alleviate or circumvent these problems; see e.g. solid shell elements proposed by Klinkel et al. [1], solid elements developed by Kadapa and Hossain [2] or mixed solid elements introduced by Pechstein [6]. As an alternative, structural elements based on plate or shell formulations have been developed. We cite non-exhaustively isogeometric shell elements proposed by Kiendl et

al. [7] or Duong et al. [8], and large deformation plate elements by Staudigl et al. [9]. In the context of dimensional reduction, a proper transition from three-dimensional continuum modeling to a structural formulation is crucial. None of the relevant aspects, which in this case include through-the-thickness distributions of thickness strains and electric field, can be neglected, as has been analyzed recently by Pechstein and Krommer [10].

In the current contribution, we develop a shell formulation that incorporates the necessary kinematic and constitutive features to capture the behavior of thin viscoelastic dielectric structures under transient electric loads. We develop a thermodynamically consistent model based on the free energy density and a dissipation function imposing the kinematic assumptions of Kirchhoff-Love shells, which integrates the viscoelastic constitutive model with electrostatic field equations, based on prior work addressing elastic incompressible dielectric shells [10].

A mixed shell element implementing this formulation is proposed, which extends the element proposed in [10] adding viscoelastic internal strains. The element originally introduced in [11] for St. Venant-Kirchhoff materials has been shown to be very versatile; only nodal degrees of freedom for the displacement field are necessary, such that standard shape functions can be used, and there are no restrictions on the structure of the underlying finite element mesh. Moments and curvatures enter the formulation as additional unknowns. Element-local degrees of freedom for thickness deformation and the through-the-thickness distribution of the electric field have proven to be necessary to mimic the behavior of dielectric shells correctly.

The proposed elements are validated through a benchmark problem [12] and compared against three-dimensional results. Our findings highlight the capability of the mixed shell elements to simulate the complex behavior of the electro-viscoelastically coupled material in thin shell-like structures.

The remainder of this work is organized as follows: in Section 2, a continuum model of dielectric viscoelastic materials is presented. Section 3 is dedicated to the definition of a non-according shell formulation and finite element discretization. Finally, computational results are presented in Section 4.

2 MODELING OF INCOMPRESSIBLE VISCOELASTIC DIELECTRIC MATERIALS

When modeling electroelastic materials, it is standard practice to account for the significant difference between the speed of sound and the speed of light. This large disparity justifies limiting the formulation to the electrostatic regime. Within this work, we further assume that all material velocities are sufficiently low, such that inertial forces and dynamic effects can be neglected, thereby simplifying the analysis to a quasi-static framework.

Consider a material body \mathcal{B} , for which we distinguish between its position in the reference configuration, denoted by the position vector \mathbf{X} , and its position in the current or deformed configuration, represented by the position vector \mathbf{x} . Using standard notation for all kinematic quantities, the displacement field is defined as $\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{x} - \mathbf{X}$. With the displacement field defined, we can introduce the deformation gradient tensor \mathbf{F} , a fundamental quantity in continuum mechanics that relates the differential change in position from the reference to the current configuration, as $\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{I} + \text{Grad } \mathbf{u}$. The deformation gradient tensor does not only describe the deformation of a material body but also serves as the foundation for defining various strain measures. One important strain measure is the right Cauchy-Green tensor, denoted as \mathbf{C} , which is defined as $\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{F}^T \cdot \mathbf{F}$. Moreover, let $J = \det \mathbf{F}$ denote the Jacobi determinant, which describes the change of volume under deformation. For incompressible

materials, we require $J \equiv 1$ throughout \mathcal{B} .

Faraday's law ensures the existence of an electric potential Φ , such that the spatial electric field $\mathbf{e} = -\nabla_{\mathbf{x}}\Phi$ is its negative spatial gradient. With respect to the reference configuration, we define the material electric field $\boldsymbol{\mathcal{E}} = -\nabla_{\mathbf{X}}\Phi = \mathbf{F}^{-T} \cdot \mathbf{e}$.

In order to describe viscoelastic behavior, the so called generalized Maxwell model as described in [13] is used, see also Figure 1.

Figure 1: Generalized Maxwell model.

To characterize the material's properties, we use the *long term modulus* E_∞ , as well as modulus E_1 and viscosity η_1 of the Maxwell element. The instantaneous modulus of the material is then given as $E_0 = E_\infty + E_1$. As we are dealing with incompressible polymers only, Poisson's ratio is at the limit of $\nu = 0.5$, and the respective shear moduli are given by $\mu_\infty = E_\infty/3$ and $\mu_1 = E_1/3$.

In order to derive a large-deformation formulation, we use a multiplicative split in terms of the deformation gradient tensor, where we follow Ask et al. [14]. The deformation gradient tensor is split into its volumetric and isochoric part, which are defined as $J^{1/3}\mathbf{I}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{F}} = J^{-1/3}\mathbf{F}$, respectively. Accordingly, we define the isochoric part of the right Cauchy-Green tensor as $\hat{\mathbf{C}} = J^{-2/3}\mathbf{C}$.

Following Ask et al. [14], the isochoric part of the deformation gradient tensor is further decomposed into its elastic and viscoelastic part, where the viscoelastic part \mathbf{F}_V is modeled to be volume preserving,

$$\hat{\mathbf{F}} = \hat{\mathbf{F}}_e \cdot \mathbf{F}_V, \quad \text{with } \det \mathbf{F}_V \equiv 1. \quad (1)$$

This decomposition is now used in terms of the right Cauchy-Green tensor, which leads to

$$\mathbf{C}_V = \mathbf{F}_V^T \cdot \mathbf{F}_V, \quad \hat{\mathbf{C}}_e = \hat{\mathbf{F}}_e^T \cdot \hat{\mathbf{F}}_e = \mathbf{F}_V^{-T} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{C}} \cdot \mathbf{F}_V^{-1}. \quad (2)$$

We propose to use an energy-based formulation to get a thermodynamically consistent model where the free energy density Ψ is decomposed additively into three parts – the hyperelastic potential Ψ_∞ , the viscoelastic potential Ψ_1 and dielectric contributions Ψ_{diel} ,

$$\Psi = \Psi_\infty + \Psi_1 + \Psi_{diel}. \quad (3)$$

The hyperelastic potential is based on a Neo-Hookean potential including an independent pressure p , which acts as a Lagrangian multiplier for the incompressibility constraint. The viscoelastic potential Ψ_1 is also of Neo-Hooke type. The dielectric contribution, often denoted as Helmholtz free energy (augmented by vacuum contributions), is characterized through the material's electric permittivity ϵ . We list our formal choices for the different contributions,

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi_\infty &= \frac{\mu_\infty}{2} (\text{tr } \mathbf{C} - 3) - \mu_\infty \log J + p \log J \\ \Psi_1 &= \frac{\mu_1}{2} (\text{tr } \hat{\mathbf{C}}_e - 3) = \frac{\mu_1}{2} (\hat{\mathbf{C}} : \mathbf{C}_V^{-1} - 3), \\ \Psi_{diel} &= -\frac{1}{2}\epsilon \mathbf{e} \cdot \mathbf{e} = -\frac{1}{2}\epsilon \boldsymbol{\mathcal{E}} \cdot \mathbf{C}^{-1} \cdot \boldsymbol{\mathcal{E}}, \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

More detailed motivation for the definition of these potentials is presented by Kunzemann et al. [15] concerning the viscoelastic modeling and Pechstein et al. [10] concerning the dielectric contribution.

The Clausius-Duhem inequality states that dissipation \mathcal{D} is non-negative (cf. [16]),

$$\mathcal{D} = \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{T} : \dot{\mathbf{C}} - \mathcal{D} \cdot \dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} - \dot{\Psi} \geq 0, \quad (5)$$

where \mathbf{T} are the second Piola-Kirchhoff stresses, defined by $\mathbf{T} = 2 \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \mathbf{C}}$, and $\mathcal{D} = -\frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}$ is the material dielectric displacement vector. We use a dissipation function to define dissipation in terms of the viscoelastic strain and its rate,

$$\mathcal{D} = \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial \dot{\mathbf{C}}_V} : \dot{\mathbf{C}}_V \quad \text{with } \phi = \frac{1}{12} \eta_1 \left((\mathbf{C}_V^{-1} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{C}}_V) : (\mathbf{C}_V^{-1} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{C}}_V) \right). \quad (6)$$

For details on material modeling using dissipation functions, we refer interested readers to [17]; the present choice for ϕ is discussed in [15]. With these considerations, we can write the principle of virtual work for the multiplicative decomposition of the deformation gradient tensor as

$$\int_{\mathcal{B}} \left(\frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \mathbf{C}} : \delta \mathbf{C} + \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \mathbf{C}_V} : \delta \mathbf{C}_V + \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial p} \delta p + \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} : \delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \right) dV + \int_{\mathcal{B}} \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial \dot{\mathbf{C}}_V} : \delta \dot{\mathbf{C}}_V dV = \delta W_{ext}. \quad (7)$$

Above, the first integral collects the virtual work of internal forces, while the second term on the left hand side corresponds to the dissipated work. Using common notation, δW_{ext} collects all virtual work contributions from external loads.

3 Shell formulation

The approach outlined above for describing the behavior of viscoelastic dielectric materials will now be applied to shells and plates, assuming the principles of the Kirchhoff-Love shell theory. Following the notation of Vetyukov [18], we denote the shell's midsurface as \mathcal{S} in the reference configuration with its normal vector \mathbf{N} and t as the shell's thickness. The volumetric shell domain is defined as $\Omega_{\mathcal{S}} = \{\mathbf{R} + \zeta \mathbf{N} : \mathbf{R} \in \mathcal{S} \text{ and } \zeta \in (-t/2, t/2)\}$. Using the normal vector \mathbf{N} , we can define the first metric tensor as $\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{I} - \mathbf{N}\mathbf{N}$ and the second metric tensor as $\mathbf{B} = -\nabla_{\mathcal{S}} \mathbf{N}$, where $\nabla_{\mathcal{S}}$ denotes the surface nabla operator. These metric tensors are essential for describing the shell's geometry and deformation. Within this contribution, we restrict the derivations to the case of initially plane structures, where $\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{0}$.

Introducing the midsurface displacement as $\mathbf{u}_{\mathcal{S}}$, such that $\mathbf{r} := \mathbf{R} + \mathbf{u}_{\mathcal{S}}$ represents the position of the midsurface of the shell after deformation, we can define the surface deformation gradient as $\mathbf{F}_{\mathcal{S}} = (\nabla_{\mathcal{S}} \mathbf{r})^T = \mathbf{A} + (\nabla_{\mathcal{S}} \mathbf{u}_{\mathcal{S}})^T$. It should be noted that this tensor is not invertible, as it is only of rank two.

Following [11], the normal vector of the deformed midsurface can be expressed by using the well-defined cofactor tensor of $\mathbf{F}_{\mathcal{S}}$, which leads to

$$\mathbf{n} = \frac{\text{Cof } \mathbf{F}_{\mathcal{S}} \cdot \mathbf{N}}{|\text{Cof } \mathbf{F}_{\mathcal{S}} \cdot \mathbf{N}|}. \quad (8)$$

The two metric tensors can be defined not only for the reference configuration but also for the deformed configuration, as $\mathbf{a} = \mathbf{I} - \mathbf{n}\mathbf{n}$ and $\mathbf{F}_{\mathcal{S}}^T \cdot \mathbf{b} = -\nabla_{\mathcal{S}} \mathbf{n}$. We once again follow the work of [18] to

introduce the two Green strain measures of the shell surface, the symmetric membrane strain $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ and the symmetric curvature tensor $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$,

$$\begin{aligned}\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} &= \frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{F}_S^T \cdot \mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{F}_S - \mathbf{A}), \\ \boldsymbol{\kappa} &= - (\mathbf{F}_S^T \cdot \mathbf{b} \cdot \mathbf{F}_S - \mathbf{B}) = \mathbf{F}_S^T \cdot \nabla_S \mathbf{n} - \nabla_S \mathbf{N}.\end{aligned}\tag{9}$$

Following the assumptions from Pechstein et al. [10], the deformation kinematics are assumed to be free of shear, but including thickness strains. An according mapping of material to spatial point can be formulated using not only the midsurface displacement \mathbf{u}_S , but also the thickness coordinate z ,

$$\mathbf{R} + \zeta \mathbf{N} \mapsto \mathbf{R} + \mathbf{u}_S + z(\zeta) \mathbf{n}.\tag{10}$$

When neglecting higher order contributions through the thickness, the right Cauchy-Green tensor of such a deformation is found as

$$\mathbf{C}_3 = \mathbf{C}_2 + C_{NN} \mathbf{N} \mathbf{N}, \quad \text{with } \mathbf{C}_2 = \mathbf{A} + 2(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} + z \boldsymbol{\kappa}) \text{ and } C_{NN} = \left(\frac{\partial z}{\partial \zeta} \right)^2.\tag{11}$$

A similar approach is chosen to discretize the viscoelastic tensor \mathbf{C}_V in terms of viscoelastic membrane strains $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_V$ and viscoelastic curvature tensor $\boldsymbol{\kappa}_V$. The kinematic incompressibility constraint determines the thickness contribution $C_{V,NN}$ directly,

$$\mathbf{C}_{V,3} = \mathbf{C}_{V,2} + C_{V,NN} \mathbf{N} \mathbf{N}, \quad \text{with } \mathbf{C}_{V,2} = \mathbf{A} + 2(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_V + \zeta \boldsymbol{\kappa}_V) \text{ and } C_{V,NN} = \frac{1}{\mathbf{N} \cdot \text{Cof } \mathbf{C}_{V,2} \cdot \mathbf{N}}\tag{12}$$

These tensor fields \mathbf{C}_3 and $\mathbf{C}_{V,3}$ are then used in the hyperelastic and dielectric potentials. Note that the Jacobi determinant is computed as $J = \sqrt{\det \mathbf{C}_3}$. As proposed in [10], we adopt a linear approximation for both the independent pressure $p(\zeta)$ and independent stretch $z'(\zeta) = \frac{\partial z(\zeta)}{\partial \zeta}$, ensuring that both quantities maintain the same approximation order.

Concerning the electric field, it is implicitly assumed that the structure is electroded at the both surfaces, and an external voltage V is applied. The material electric field $\boldsymbol{\mathcal{E}}$ is then oriented in direction of the surface normal \mathbf{N} , its nominal value computed as $\mathcal{E}_0 = V/t$. In the studies presented in [10], it was shown that a linear variation of the electric field has to be included in the model to capture the electromechanic interactions correctly; in the shell formulation, the electric field is finally described as

$$\boldsymbol{\mathcal{E}} = \mathcal{E}_0 (1 + \zeta \kappa_{\mathcal{E}}) \mathbf{N}.\tag{13}$$

We can now use these definitions to introduce the hyperelastic potential for the shell structure. Similar to the approach for dielectric elastomer plates as used by [9], we formulate the thermodynamic potential by using through-the-thickness integration as

$$\Psi_S(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}, \boldsymbol{\kappa}, z, p, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_V, \boldsymbol{\kappa}_V, \kappa_{\mathcal{E}}) = \int_{-t/2}^{t/2} \Psi d\zeta.\tag{14}$$

We also apply integration over the thickness for the dissipation function, which results in the following relationship

$$\phi_S(\dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_V, \dot{\boldsymbol{\kappa}}_V, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_V, \boldsymbol{\kappa}_V) = \int_{-t/2}^{t/2} \phi \, d\zeta. \quad (15)$$

Based on the assumptions and derivations outlined above, it is now possible to propose the principle of virtual work analogous to the one previously developed for the continuum model above, as

$$\int_S \underbrace{\left(\frac{\partial \Psi_S}{\partial \mathbf{C}_3} : \delta \mathbf{C}_3 + \frac{\partial \Psi_S}{\partial \mathbf{C}_{V,3}} : \delta \mathbf{C}_{V,3} + \frac{\partial \Psi_S}{\partial p} \delta p + \frac{\partial \Psi_S}{\partial \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} : \delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \right)}_{\delta \Psi_S} dS + \int_S \frac{\partial \phi_S}{\partial \dot{\mathbf{C}}_{V,3}} : \delta \dot{\mathbf{C}}_{V,3} dS = \delta W_{ext}. \quad (16)$$

However, we refer to [11], where they suggested a different approach. They propose introducing the moment tensor as an additional unknown, which acts as a Lagrangian multiplier in the defining relation of the curvature tensor. Additionally, the curvature tensor itself is discretized separately, a method recently presented by [19], which is similar to the well-known Hellinger-Reissner mixed formulation in continuum mechanics. As discussed in [10], this formulation can be extended to nonlinear hyperelasticity and electromechanically coupled problems. The resulting formulation amounts to

$$\int_S \left(\delta \Psi_S + \frac{\partial \phi_S}{\partial \dot{\mathbf{C}}_{V,3}} : \delta \dot{\mathbf{C}}_{V,3} \right) dS + \int_S \delta \left(\left(\mathbf{F}_S^T \cdot (\nabla_S \mathbf{n})^T - \nabla_S \mathbf{N} - \boldsymbol{\kappa} \right) : \mathbf{m} \right) dS = \delta W_{ext}. \quad (17)$$

Without going into the details of the implementation of the presented theory in the context of the finite element method, we refer to [10], which contains the basic ideas and properties of the finite element discretization and the shell elements used for the analysis.

4 NUMERICAL EXAMPLE

A geometrically simple example from the literature (cf. [12]), a dielectric membrane, is used to validate the present formulation. As described in [12], the membrane is analyzed without pre-stretching. The circular membrane has a thickness of H and radius A .

As shown in Figure 2, the lateral boundary is simply supported. In the shell model, this means that the displacements of the midsurface are constrained to zero in all three spatial directions. In contrast, in the continuum model, the displacements are constrained along the centerline of the lateral surface, as indicated and the mean value of the displacement in Z -direction on the lateral surface is constrained to zero.

Figure 2: Initial state of the dielectric membrane.

Within this numerical example, we assume the material to be perfectly isotropic and incompressible with $\mu_\infty = \mu_1 = 1 \text{ N/mm}^2$ and $\eta_1 = E_1 \tau_1 = 3\mu_1 \tau_1$ with $\tau_1 = 5 \text{ ms}$. Additionally we use $\epsilon = 5\epsilon_0$ as the material's permittivity.

Two different external loads are considered in the analysis. First, the membrane is subjected to an external pressure. Second, an electrical voltage is applied across its thickness direction as shown in Figure 3. As shown in [12], beyond a critical pressure $p_{ext} = p_{crit}$, no equilibrium condition can be found. This critical pressure is calculated as $p_{crit} = 2\mu_\infty \frac{H}{A}$. A characteristic electric voltage is also used for the electrical loading, which is defined as $V^* = H \left(\frac{2\mu_\infty}{\epsilon} \right)^{1/2}$. For comparison, the vertical displacement of the midpoint is expressed in a dimensionless form as u_Z/A and the time is presented dimensionless as t/τ_1 .

Figure 3: Deformed state of the dielectric membrane.

The computational results for the proposed elements are presented and compared to the solution of the corresponding fully coupled continuum problem. In addition to this comparison, the results obtained using our formulation are evaluated against existing results reported in the literature. This comprehensive comparison serves to validate the accuracy and applicability of the proposed method.

As shown below, the evolution of the vertical displacement of the the membrane's midpoint u_Z is used for a first comparison. The external loads were both applied in 5 steps. We are using the data of [12] as reference for the proposed formulation.

Figure 4: Evolution of u_Z under several different voltages, while $p_{ext} = 0.5p_{crit}$ is kept constant.

As shown in Figure 4 above, the results are in good agreement with the reference values from [12]. For 10% and 20% of V^* , both, the continuum model and the shell model, align almost perfectly with the reference values. As the voltage increases, the membrane becomes unstable and no equilibrium state can be found, which was also discussed in [12]. The numerical results exhibit exactly this behaviour, showing that the shell model is more robust in the direction of instability. Unlike the continuum model, it is unable to find an equilibrium position at later times. For 30% of V^* , the continuum model fails at $7.9\tau_1$, whereas the shell models reaches $21.5\tau_1$. For 40% of V^* , although the time difference is smaller, it remains significant: the continuum model fails at $1.5\tau_1$, whereas the shell model reaches $2.8\tau_1$.

The evolution of the membrane's shape for two different electrical voltages is shown in Figure 5. Obviously, the numerical results from the shell model were employed for this analysis as the continuum model fails to achieve an equilibrium state at 30% of V^* , even before $t/\tau_1 = 10$. These results once again show good agreement with the reference values from the original work already mentioned several times [12].

Figure 5: Evolution of the membrane's shape at two different voltages (top: $V = 0.2V^*$ and bottom: $V = 0.3V^*$).

For the special choice of geometric properties with $A = 10$ mm and $H = 0.2$ mm, the mesh of the full three-dimensional problem comprises 1331 third-order elements, with two elements across the thickness, which leads to 29679 coupling degrees of freedom in total. In comparison, the surface mesh used for the shell model consists of 55 third-order triangular elements, resulting in 2421 coupling degrees of freedom in total.

The shell's mesh illustrating an exemplary result is shown below in Figure 6. The 55 third-order elements of this very coarse mesh are clearly recognizable, yet it delivers highly accurate results consistent with those found in the literature. The efficiency of this coarse mesh highlights the potential of the presented shell elements to reduce computational effort without sacrificing the accuracy of the numerical solution.

Figure 6: Numerical result for 20% of V^* , illustrated $|\epsilon_V|$ on the undeformed mesh (left) in the x-y-plane and on the deformed mesh (right) in the x-z-plane.

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DAMAGE IDENTIFICATION AND APPLICATION OF PRESTRESSED CONCRETE BEAMS BASED ON HILBERT-HUANG TRANSFORM

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Abstract. In this paper, through the analysis of numerical and experimental studies with and without noise, the vibration characteristics of the prestressed concrete beam during failure process were studied. Runge-Kutta method was used to solve the partial differential equations of controlling vibration to obtain dynamic response under hammer excitation. The vibration characteristics of the test beam under different damage conditions were researched by Hilbert-Huang Transformation (HHT) time-frequency analysis method. Concrete strain, deflection and crack development, etc. were recorded during failure process, and dynamic testing of five key working conditions was made. The acceleration signals were obtained from each key condition and HHT was used to get instantaneous frequency-acceleration amplitude curve during each damage stage. The results showed that instantaneous frequency-acceleration amplitude curve obtained by the HHT can clearly reflect the degree of damage, the change of damage characteristic frequency display the extent of damage in the failure process.

Keywords: Prestressed concrete beam; Vibration analysis; Damage identification; Hilbert-huang transform; Experimental study

1. INTRODUCTION

Medium and Short span prestressed concrete bridge occupies a large proportion in Chinese highway Bridges. With the increase of traffic load and adverse effect of environment, there will be various forms of damage in the service, resulting in reduction of load carrying capacity of bridges. Therefore, it is of great practical significance to study the damage identification of medium and short span prestressed concrete structures.

The occurrence of structural damage will inevitably lead to the change of dynamic parameters of the structures, and the analysis of the signals obtained by the dynamic response of the structures is related to the accurate identification of the structure state [1]. Many scholars have successively carried out researches on damage identification of concrete beam structures by vibration test methods [2-8].

The traditional Fourier transform is to transform the signal from the time domain to information in the frequency domain, but it does not simultaneously possess the time-frequency resolution ability. The time-domain information will be lost in the transformation process. Wavelet transform is a signal processing method which has both time and frequency domain resolution. Wavelet analysis for engineering application problems exists in the choice of wavelet base. Analysis of the same question may produce different results by different wavelet base [9].

Hilbert-Huang Transform [10] (HHT) is a new time-frequency analysis method with self-adaptation, which can analyze both steady and non-stationary signals. This method firstly used the empirical mode decomposition (EMD) method to decompose the given signal adaptively step by step into the basic intrinsic mode function (IMF). The introduction of the decomposition method of signal local characteristics makes the concept of instantaneous frequency signal to become the real physical significance.

In this paper, the prestressed concrete hollow beam was taken as the research object, which had served for 11 years. It focused on the measurement of acceleration signals of constant prestressed concrete hollow beams with

different damage degrees under dynamic loads, as well as the signal processing and analysis of the changes of instantaneous frequency and acceleration amplitude of the hollow beam under time domain by using Hilbert-Huang transform, and explored the beam structural damage status and frequency changes of the damaged hollow beam after different static loads loading level.

2 HILBERT-HUANG TRANSFORMATION

Hilbert-Huang Transformation (HHT) consists of Huang transform and Hilbert spectrum analysis. The key of Huang transformation is empirical mode decomposition (EMD). EMD decomposes the signal into a sum of finite intrinsic mode functions (IMF). Any time series $x(t)$ can be expressed as the sum of n -order natural modal function (c_1, c_2, c_3, \dots) and a residual r_n after EMD decomposition.

$$x(t) = \sum_{i=1}^n c_i + r_n \quad (1)$$

Every order component is a vibration modal with different amplitude and frequency, the first order modal function has the highest frequency. With the increase of the order number of modal its cycle become longer until close to a linear function of time. Hilbert transform gains the analytic signal of the signal through Hilbert transform to obtain the instantaneous frequency. All order modal functions $c_i(t)$ obtained by EMD decomposition were performed by Hilbert transformation, i. e. :

$$c_i(t) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int \frac{c_i(\tau)}{t - \tau} d\tau \quad (2)$$

The analytic signal $z_i(t)$ corresponding to $x(t)$ is:

$$z_i(t) = c_i(t) + jH[c_i(t)] = a_i(t) \exp[j\phi_i(t)] \quad (3)$$

Where: $a_i(t)$ and $\phi_i(t)$ is the amplitude function and phase function of the signal, respectively, as following formula.

$$a_i(t) = \sqrt{c_i^2(t) + H^2[c_i(t)]} \quad (4)$$

$$\phi_i(t) = \arctan\left(\frac{H[c_i(t)]}{c_i(t)}\right) \quad (5)$$

Further, the instantaneous frequency can be obtained:

$$\omega_i(t) = \frac{d\phi_i(t)}{dt} \quad (6)$$

$$f_i(t) = \frac{\omega_i(t)}{2\pi} = \frac{1}{2\pi} \frac{d\phi_i(t)}{dt} \quad (7)$$

3 EXPERIMENT BACKGROUND

3.1 Dimensions and materials of test beam

Mid-span cross section and plan view of the PC experimental beam is shown in figure 1. The length of beam is 19.96 m, and calculation span is 19.30 m, ordinary reinforced configuration is $\Phi 8$, which adopts R235 hot rolled round steel bar. The prestressed steel strand is a high strength and low relaxation strand wire with standard strength 1860 MPa. The layout of steel strands is $8\Phi^{j15.24} + 8\Phi^{j15.24}$ with tension on both ends. The strength grade of concrete is C50.

Figure 1: Dimensions of the experimental beam

3.2 Test loading and test scheme

This test loading device select four sets of JAW-500A electro-hydraulic servo test system (500 kN). The two symmetrical loads are exerting on one-third points of the beam span determined by the calculation(As shown in figure 2). The live loading photo is shown in figure 3.

Figure 2: Loading diagram of the test beam (unit: cm)

Figure 3: The live loading photo

The deflection measurement points are arranged at the bottom of the beam in $L/4$, $L/2$ and $3L/4$ cross-sections of beam span and two sides of the two temporary supports respectively to measure the settlement or deflection in two end supports. At the same time, the deflection data are checked by steel ruler and wire-drawing displacement meter. Digital strain gauges along the top and bottom of the beam and sides web in the $L/4$, $L/2$, $3L/4$ cross-sections in longitudinal direction are arranged, steel strain gauges in the bottom bar area of the mid-span cross section of the beam are pasted to measure steel strains. The dynamic measurement adopts the acceleration sensors installed on the test beam gain correspond signal, as shown in the figure 4. vibration of the beam is stimulated by the test force hammer.

Figure 4: Layout of acceleration sensors

4 NUMERICAL CALCULATION OF VIBRATION CHARACTERISTICS OF TEST BEAM

4.1 Vibration partial differential equation of test beam

Figure 5 is a simply supported beam, and assume that the bending stiffness of the beam is $EI(x)$ and the mass of per beam length is $m(x)$, it can vary at any location x along the span L . The vertical load above the beam is $p(x,t)$, it can also vary with arbitrary location and time. The vertical displacement response of the beam is $v(x,t)$.

Considering the balance of all vertical forces:

$$V(x, t) + p(x, t)dx - [V(x, t) + \frac{\partial V(x, t)}{\partial x} dx] - m(x) \frac{\partial^2 v(x, t)}{\partial t^2} dx - c(x) \frac{\partial v(x, t)}{\partial t} dx = 0 \quad (8)$$

Where $V(x, t)$ is the vertical force acting on the section, $m(x)dx \frac{\partial^2 v(x, t)}{\partial t^2}$ is the resultant forces of transverse inertial forces acted on the micro segment, $c(x) \frac{\partial v(x, t)}{\partial t} dx$ is damping force acted on the micro segment, $c(x)$ is damping factor. The equation is divided by dx , we can get:

$$\frac{\partial V(x, t)}{\partial x} = p(x, t) - m(x) \frac{\partial^2 v(x, t)}{\partial t^2} - c(x) \frac{\partial v(x, t)}{\partial t} \quad (9)$$

The second equilibrium equation can be obtained by summing the moment at the point on the elastic axis. When ignoring the second order moment term containing the inertial force and the applied load [11], we can get

$$M(x, t) + V(x, t)dx - [M(x, t) + \frac{\partial M(x, t)}{\partial x} dx] = 0 \quad (10)$$

Due to ignoring the moment of inertia, so have

$$\frac{\partial M(x, t)}{\partial x} = V(x, t) \quad (11)$$

Take the derivative of the above equation with respect to x , and replace it into Eq.(9)

$$\frac{\partial M^2(x, t)}{\partial x^2} + m(x) \frac{\partial^2 v(x, t)}{\partial t^2} + c(x) \frac{\partial v(x, t)}{\partial t} = p(x, t) \quad (12)$$

The relationship between bending moment and curvature of beam is introduced

$$M(x, t) = EI(x) \left[\frac{\partial^2 v(x, t)}{\partial x^2} \right] \quad (13)$$

Substitute Eq. (13) into Eq. (12), we can get:

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \left\{ EI(x) \left[\frac{\partial^2 v(x, t)}{\partial x^2} \right] \right\} + m(x) \frac{\partial^2 v(x, t)}{\partial t^2} + c(x) \frac{\partial v(x, t)}{\partial t} = p(x, t) \quad (14)$$

Figure 5: Simply supported beam under dynamic loads

It is worth noting that the differential equation given by the Eq. (8) to Eq. (14) only shows the physical parameters such as the mass distribution, damping and bending stiffness of the beam that affect the vibration of a beam under an ideal perfect elastic body and the corresponding vibration displacement equation, which does not consider the influence of prestressing force within the beam. The cracking behavior of prestressed concrete beams under different static loads is only simply expressed by stiffness reduction. The dynamic signal obtained in the actual beam test has included the influence of the relevant physical parameters (such as the damage, cracking degree and the damping etc. of the beam). Theoretically, the magnitude of prestressing does have a certain influence on the vibration of the beam body, how to consider the effect of prestressing in vibration equation of the beam needs to be further studied and perfected in the future study. In this test process, it is assumed that the prestressing variation of the beam body is small and can be ignored.

4.2 Numerical calculation of dynamic response of test beam

In order to explore the feasibility of damage identification after the dynamic test signal of the test beam is decomposed into some basic intrinsic mode functions (IMF) by EMD, the displacement response signal of the concrete beam in actual constant prestressing is solved by numerical method, and then the relevant signal transformation is analyzed. When the stiffness, calculation span, mass and damping factor etc. parameters of test beam are substituted into the partial differential equation (14), taking the impact exciting load acted on the beam as 10 kN and the sampling frequency as 1000 Hz, the time-dependent displacement response of the beam can be calculated and gained during the 4s. The displacement response point is selected at the mid-span of the beam. As the damage of the structure will lead to the reduction of the beam bending stiffness, here the bending stiffness reduction of 5%, 10% and 15% for the beam is respectively defined to simulate the different damage cases of the beam. The dynamic response results at the mid-span point of test beam obtained by Runge-kutta method and Matlab programming according to Eq. (14) is shown in the figure 6.

The signal is decomposed by EMD, as shown in the figure 7. In order to eliminate the influence of endpoint effect when is decomposed by EMD, the intermediate data are selected for analysis, and the time-dependent curves of displacement amplitude and frequency are obtained, as shown in the figure 8.

Figure 6: Displacement response in the mid-span of test beam

Figure 9 shows the relationship curve of the instantaneous frequency-time of the test beam in different degrees of damage. As you can see, the instantaneous frequency beam fluctuates up and down near the base frequency. With deepening of the damage degree, the instantaneous frequency range becomes lower, which can reflect the extent of the damage. It shows that the index is an effective indicator to measure the damage degree of structure.

Figure 7: EMD of mid-span displacement response

Figure 8: Time-dependent curve of instantaneous amplitude and frequency

Figure 9: Instantaneous frequency-time relation curves in different damage states

5 TEST CONTENT AND DATA ANALYSIS

5.1 Test process

The whole static loading process of the test beam is divided into 18 stages, mainly including loading before cracking, stage after cracking, stage near 90% ultimate load and the failure stage of the test beam. The holding time of each stage remains around 15mins after loading. After the displacement meter reading and crack development are basically stable, the crack development of the beam is observed and recorded. After collecting the displacement meter and strain gauge readings, unload to zero. The experiment shows that when the test load is up to 200 kN, the concrete on the top of the beam flange crushes, and the crack width of the beam increases obviously. The crack distribution in the limit state of the structure is shown in the figure 10. The crack development in the key stages of the whole test process is listed in table 1.

The corresponding dynamic response is also tested in five key stages by the hammer exciting load acted on at the mid-span of the beam, which mainly include the Condition I : the initial state of beam; Condition II : unloading after the load reaches 90 kN (test beam is just cracking); Condition III: unloading after the load reaches 155 kN (ordinary steel bar has begun to yield); Condition IV: unloading after the load reaches 185 kN (crack width is more than 1 mm); Condition V : loading up to the ultimate load of test beam(200 kN).

Figure 10: Crack diagram of test beam in ultimate state

Table 1. Crack development in the key stages of the whole test process

Load value (kN)	Maximum crack width (mm)	Fracture depth extension (depth of beam $h=90\text{cm}$)	Crack development description
0	0	0	No cracks
90	0.02	0.01h	The width of cracks is small for the bottom plate near the mid-span
125	0.2	0.5h	The cracks extend to half beam depth, and transverse cracks appear on the bottom plate
155	0.3	0.65h	Cracks appear in the whole area from the quarter point to the middle of the span, and the cracks continue to develop
185	1.0	0.85h	The crack depth extends to the lower edge of top slab of test beam, and the crack width is more than 1mm
200	2.8	h	Several cracks near the mid-span section is more than 2.5mm wide, the maximum is up to 2.8mm. The concrete in top flange of the beam near mid-span is crushed

5.2 Test data analysis

The actual measurement of the acceleration signal will inevitably encounter noise interference. Before loading, the acceleration response in mid-span measured by the test is shown in figure 11. The response signal is decomposed by EMD, and the results are shown in figure 12.

Figure 11: Acceleration response in the mid-span of the test beam

Figure 12: Results of the acceleration response decomposed by EMD

When acceleration signal gained in the different conditions is transformed by HHT, we can get instantaneous frequency-time curves and acceleration amplitude-time curves. After removing the effect of endpoints, the instantaneous frequency-time curves and acceleration amplitude-time curves are analyzed within the range of 1.0~3.0s.

The instantaneous frequency and amplitude are one by one corresponding through the time scale, the instantaneous frequency-acceleration amplitude curves are made in the different conditions, as shown in figure 13. The loss rate of base characteristic frequency of damaged beam is corresponding to the applied load, as drawn in figure 14.

Figure 13: The instantaneous frequency-acceleration amplitude curve of the test beam in each damaged state

Figure 14: Loss rate of base frequencies of damaged beam corresponding to different loading levels

It is found that from figure 14, the loss rate of base characteristic frequency of the beam reflects the damage degree and corresponded to the loading level. At the same time, it reflects the change of base frequency of damaged beam in different damage conditions. HHT transformation can clearly display the damage degree of test beam.

6 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, vibration characteristics of existing prestressed concrete beams with and without noise are respectively analyzed by the numerical calculation and experimentally investigated. The following conclusions are drawn:

- The vibration partial differential equation of test beam solved by the Runge-kutta method is proposed. The dynamic response signal of simulated beam obtained under the hammer excitation force is analyzed by HHT in time-frequency domain. The vibration characteristics of the test beam are described in different damage conditions. The results show that the time history of instantaneous frequency variation obtained by HHT can reflect the occurrence and degree of damage in the structural system.
- In terms of the acceleration signal obtained by the HHT transformation in different cases, the instantaneous frequency-acceleration amplitude curves of the beam have been obtained during the damage process. It is found that the loss rate of characteristic frequency of damaged beam reflects the damage degree and corresponds to the loading level. It also reflects the change of damage characteristic frequency under in different damage conditions. HHT transformation can clearly display and predict the damage degree of test beam.

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EFFECT OF STRAIN FIELDS ON FREQUENCY BAND GAPS OF PERIODIC LATTICE-BASED METAMATERIALS

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Abstract. Lattice-based metamaterials, known for their ability to deliver unique acoustic properties such as wave band gaps and direction-dependent phase velocities, are considered promising for noise filtering and acoustic sensor applications. Lattice-based metamaterials' unique acoustic abilities arise from their periodic porous structures, allowing them to be realized even when the lattices are made from isotropic materials. The properties of lattice metamaterials are primarily determined by their inner microstructure (i.e., topology and morphology). Consequently, by designing their inner microstructure, it is possible to tune their properties to filter or detect specific frequencies. Varying the topology of lattice metamaterials has been shown to affect their acoustic properties significantly. However, this work focuses on the effect of morphological changes, particularly stretching, on their acoustic properties. Stretching can be achieved by mechanically deforming lattice metamaterials using external forces or by constructing them from active constituents such as piezoelectric materials. The overall goal of this work is to assist in developing lattice metamaterial that can deliver deformation-tunable acoustic properties. This work computationally investigates the effect of stretching strain fields on a hexagonal lattice-based metamaterial. In particular, it examines the effects of small and large strain fields on the frequency band gaps between 100kHz and 1000kHz. Different strain levels are used to determine the sensitivity of frequency band gaps to stretching strains. The results show that the frequency band gaps are insensitive to small strains at low frequencies (~100kHz) but are sensitive to small strains at higher frequencies (~1000kHz). Conversely, large strains significantly affect the frequency band gaps, resulting in the shift, creation, or cancelation of band gaps. The findings demonstrate that actuating lattice-based metamaterial can effectively tune their frequency band gaps.

Keywords: Smart materials; Band gaps; Tunable properties; Finite element analysis; Lattice materials.

1 INTRODUCTION

Lattice-based metamaterials, known for their ability to deliver unique acoustic properties such as wave band gaps and direction-dependent phase velocities, are considered promising for applications in noise filtering and acoustic sensors [1, 2], wave attenuators [3], and wave propagation switchers [4]. The unique acoustic abilities of Lattice-based metamaterials arise from their periodic porous structures, which allow lattices to exhibit unique acoustic properties even when their struts or cell walls are made from isotropic materials. As a result, the acoustic properties of lattice metamaterials are primarily determined by their inner microstructure (i.e., topology and morphology). Consequently, by designing their inner microstructure, it is possible to tune their properties to filter or detect specific frequencies [5, 6]. While the acoustic behavior is also influenced by the constituent material, the dependence on topology is stronger and more easily engineered.

Due to the strong influence of topology on lattices' acoustic properties, multiple efforts have investigated the coupling between acoustic properties and different topologies such as hexagonal [7], Bravais [8], Auxetic [3, 9–11], Kagome [12, 13], core-embedded periodic patterns [14], and perturbed honeycombs [15–17]. These efforts

proved that frequency band gaps with different values and widths can be created or eliminated by changing lattices' topology. This observation motivated the development of lattices with designed topology to provide user-predetermined band gaps. Fulfilling this motivation was realized by utilizing artificial intelligence (AI) tools to establish a relationship between topological features and frequency band gaps [15, 17, 18]. The AI-based models were shown to be effective in selecting the geometric features needed to deliver a specific band gap. The potential for designing lattice materials with specific band gaps motivated the development of lattices with tunable properties. These lattices can potentially change their acoustic properties due to their interaction with their environments, such as interacting with electric, voltage, force, or thermal fields. The working principle of these materials is based on external excitation inducing a morphological change in the lattice structure, which subsequently alters their acoustic properties. Accordingly, the sensitivity of band gaps in lattice materials to morphological changes caused by deformations triggered by external stimuli such as uniform loading, buckling instabilities, or thermal and electrical fields has been explored. [4–6, 19–22]. Results demonstrated that frequency band gaps could be activated or deactivated by deformations that significantly morph lattice materials. These findings supported the hypothesis that the band gaps of lattice materials can be tailored by adjusting their inner structure [15]. However, advancing this approach requires a deeper understanding of the limitations of tunability through morphing. Although a broader range of morphing is linked to more tunable responses, excessive morphing can significantly alter the lattice's shape, potentially causing overstress and damage. Therefore, it is essential to define the tunable range of lattices when using morphing. This involves assessing the impact of small to relatively large shape changes on the acoustic properties of the lattices. Understanding these limitations will aid in designing the mechanisms that drive morphing. For instance, knowing the deformable limits of a lattice can assist in selecting its constituent material (e.g., active materials), trigger mechanisms, and the desired tunable frequency band gap range.

This work focuses on investigating the effect of morphological changes on the acoustic properties of lattices. These changes are modeled by uniform stretching fields, which represent uniform axial strains. Such strains can be generated or triggered by external forces [5] or by external electric fields when the lattices are composed of active materials, such as piezoelectric constituents. The effect of these stretching strain fields on the band gaps of hexagonal and triangular lattice-based metamaterials is analyzed using computational techniques. Specifically, this study examines the impact of both small and large strain fields on the frequency band gaps of the lattices in the 100 kHz to 1000 kHz range. Various strain levels are applied to assess the sensitivity of the frequency band gaps to stretching strains (i.e., morphing). The overall aim of this work is to support the development of lattice metamaterials with deformation-tunable acoustic properties.

2 METHODOLOGY

The effect of stretching-induced morphing is investigated in a hexagonal honeycomb lattice. This lattice is chosen due to its widespread use as cores in composite sandwich structures, making it industrially relevant. Additionally, it represents the class of lattices in which the underlying deformation mechanism of their cell walls is bending. The hexagonal lattice is comprised of identical cell walls in terms of material property and thickness. Thus, this cell follows the single-sided cell wall classification. The lattice is assumed to be made of aluminum with Young's modulus of 70 GPa, Poisson's ratio of 0.33, and a density of 2700 kg/m³. The lattice is 10 mm in size. Size is defined as the distance from one corner of the hexagon to the opposing corner. Accordingly, the circle passing through the six corners of the hexagon is 10 mm in diameter. Multiple relative densities are considered, namely 5%, 10%, 15%, 20%, 25%, and 30%, to explore the effect of relative densities. Larger relative densities are not considered as highly porous materials exhibit richer frequency band gap behavior in terms of frequency level and bandwidth. In addition, larger relative densities will correlate to higher mass and less flexible structures. The methodology investigated the response in an infinite material, which is represented using the unit cell approach. The unit cell used to represent the honeycomb lattice is shown in Figure 1. Two levels of stretching are used, namely 3% and 12%. The former represents a relatively small morphing strain, while the latter represents a considerable morphing strain. Although morphing in applications can comprise deformations in multiple directions, one one-directional stretching is considered to facilitate focusing on the interaction of strain and frequency band gaps. Similar studies can subsequently be used to investigate other morphing strain directions or the effect of combined strains.

The determination of the frequency band gaps for both the regular and stretched hexagonal lattices is conducted using finite element analysis in conjunction with Bloch wave theory. While the complete

methodology is detailed in the literature [17], it is briefly summarized here to provide readers with sufficient background without unnecessary repetition. The approach starts by defining the physical lattice directions ($\mathbf{e}_1, \mathbf{e}_2$) and their reciprocal directions ($\mathbf{b}_1, \mathbf{b}_2$). The physical lattice directions are shown in Figure 2 for the unstretched lattice. For the stretched lattice, they will rotate slightly upward.

Figure 1: Schematic of the hexagonal honeycomb lattice and its unit cell, showing the configuration before and after stretching

The reciprocal vectors are computed from the physical vectors using the definition $\mathbf{b}_i \cdot \mathbf{e}_j = \delta_{ij}$, where δ_{ij} is the Kronecker delta. The two reciprocal lattice vectors are used to define the 1st Brillouin zone. This zone for the unstretched lattice is shown in Figure 2. The 1st Brillouin zone for the stretched lattice would change slightly since both its physical and reciprocal lattice vectors would be altered.

Figure 2: The lattice vectors and 1st Brillouin zone for the unstretched hexagonal lattice.

Applying the Bloch wave theory on the unit cell results in the periodic boundary conditions that describe the propagation of a harmonic wave with specific attenuation and dispersion properties in the periodic lattice. The periodic boundary conditions for both the unstretched and stretched lattices are given by

$$\text{and} \tag{1}$$

such that $\mathbf{u}_0, \mathbf{u}_1, \mathbf{u}_2$ represent the degrees of freedom at the nodes 0, 1, and 2 shown in Figure 2, respectively. and k_2 represent the dispersive properties along the reciprocal directions, which are defined using

$$\tag{2}$$

The range of admissible values of k_1 and k_2 is defined by the 1st Brillouin zone [17]. The periodic boundary conditions defined by Equation (1) are applied to the unit cell shown in Figure 2 using the finite element software ABAQUS. The walls of the unit cell were modeled using Timoshenko beam elements. Each wall was discretized using at least 50 elements. This number was determined after conducting a mesh sensitivity analysis, which identified 50 as the conservative number to ensure that the results are independent of the mesh size. The periodic boundary conditions were applied using the Equation command in ABAQUS. The default

eigenfrequency solver in ABAQUS, the Lanczos solver, was used to calculate the eigenfrequencies of the models, which consisted of a unit cell and periodic boundary conditions. Only eigenfrequencies below 1000 kHz were determined. The solution process requires assuming the k_1 and k_2 values before solving the systems to find their eigenvalues. The values of k_1 and k_2 are defined by tracing the polygon marked by the points OABCO in Figure 2. Each line of the polygon was divided into 20 segments. Each point on the segments belonging to the polygon OABCO defines a set of k_1 and k_2 . So, for each point on the polygon OABCO, the system was solved, and the eigenfrequencies were determined. The eigenfrequencies were plotted against the position on the polygon OABCO. This plot defines the band gap structure, with the gaps representing the frequency band gaps.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The described approach was used to determine the frequency band gaps in the unstretched, 3% stretched, and 12% stretched lattices at the relative densities of 5%, 10%, 15%, 20%, 25%, and 30%. Results are shown in Figure 3. In this figure, each frequency band gap detected is presented as a bar whose lower level and upper level correspond to the boundaries of the frequency band gap. The figure is color-coded to represent the frequency band gap level in kHz. Results show that the unstretched lattice had two to three frequency band gaps at almost every relative density tested, except at the highest relative density. At increased relative density, the porosity decreases, and so do the band gaps. However, stretching the lattice by 3%, which is reasonably low, affected the frequency band gaps at the lowest densities most. The stretching caused two gaps to vanish at 5% relative density. Additionally, it caused one band to disappear at each of the relative densities: 10%, 15%, 25%, and 30%.

Figure 3: The frequency band gaps of the unstretched, 3% stretched, and 12% stretched lattices.

Higher stretch, i.e., 12% strain, resulted in a more pronounced effect. It eliminated all the band gaps at the relative densities of 5%, 15%, 25%, and 30%. It also reduced the width of the frequency band gaps. Conversely, it generated two new band gaps at 10% relative density. Moreover, the lowest band, at 20% relative density, was shifted downward. Accordingly, the results demonstrate a significant change in the frequency band gap characteristics due to the application of stretching or morphing strain.

Results indicate that frequency band gaps nonlinearly depend on relative density. Both the width and level of the band gaps varied with relative density, but the lowest number of band gaps was observed at the highest relative density used. From an application perspective, e.g., sensing or filtering, small morphing-induced strains can make the lattice sensitivity to a few frequencies. Those are the frequency band gaps that were eliminated by

the small strain, such as the ~ 580 kHz at 5% relative density. Frequencies around this range would be blocked by the original lattice, but they will be allowed to pass by the 3% deformed lattice. Accordingly, a 3% strain can be considered an on/off switch to pass frequencies around ~ 580 kHz. The on-off switching is more effective at the 12% strain. This strain can close all the gates at 5%, 15%, 25%, and 30%. But even at 10% and 20%, the 12% strain decreased the width of the frequency band gaps and decreased their functionality; they can just pass a very narrow range of frequencies. So, the 12% strain can be practically used to block the propagation of all frequencies below 1000 kHz. Accordingly, strains between 3% and 12% are significant enough to alter the acoustic properties of the hexagonal lattice and change its frequency band gaps. The strains achieve this effect by changing the inner structure of the lattice. This change in inner structure stems from the linear transformation associated with stretching the lattice, which can be achieved in practical applications by applying an external force. Of course, other approaches can be used to deform and stretch the lattice, such as utilizing active or shape memory materials and subsequently triggering the lattice deformation using a thermal, electrical, or magnetic external field. The mechanism of deforming the lattice is not within the scope of this work. Here, we are focused on finding the level of deformation (i.e., morphing) that can effectively lead to significant changes in the acoustic properties of the lattice material. So, the results suggest that strains beyond 12% are not needed.

4 CONCLUSIONS

- This work's main objective was to explore the effect of applying morphing strain fields on the frequency band gaps of a common lattice (i.e., Hexagonal honeycomb lattice) over a range of porosity or relative density levels. Small (3%) and large (12%) strain fields were used to represent actuating-induced strains.
- Frequency band gaps showed nonlinear dependence on porosity or relative density level. However, smaller porosities exhibited narrower and lesser frequency band gaps.
- Both applied strains affected the frequency band gaps of the lattice. The small strain, 3%, effectively eliminated multiple frequency band gaps. On the other hand, The large strain, 12%, eliminated all band gaps at 5%, 15%, 25%, and 30% relative densities. It also narrowed all remaining frequency band gaps at the 10% and 20 % relative densities. Accordingly, the large strain altered the behavior of the lattice to block approximately most frequencies below 1000 kHz.
- Results confirm that strains between 3% and 12% can be used effectively to switch the frequency band gaps of the hexagonal lattice on and off. Accordingly, from an application perspective, to utilize this lattice as a frequency switch or sensor, it should be morphed by strains within the 12% range. This morphing strain can be generated by an external force or by the use of active constitutes.

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LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT OF PIEZOELECTRIC MATERIALS USED FOR ENERGY HARVESTING SYSTEMS: PZT VERSUS KNN

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ABSTRACT

Over the past decade, piezoelectric materials have been extensively used in various engineering areas, particularly for energy harvesting, due to their efficient electromechanical conversion. Several scientific researches reported in the literature have performed modeling, prototyping, and experimentation to improve the performance of harvesters. Piezoelectric transducers, especially those used for energy harvesting, could have significant environmental impacts. Few studies have emphasized the environmental issue of harvesters in their life cycle. This paper aims to study the environmental impacts of piezoelectric energy harvesters obtained with screen-printing process by performing a life cycle assessment (LCA). Firstly, a comprehensive overview of piezoelectric materials and their implementation in the context of micro electromechanical systems is first presented. Secondly, the environmental impacts of these materials are briefly discussed based on previous studies. Here the aim is to present a comparative analysis of the environmental consequences of energy harvesters based on different piezoelectric materials, from cradle to gate. The harvester based on lead zirconate titanate $\text{Pb}(\text{Zr},\text{Ti})\text{O}_3$ (PZT) is taken as a reference. The impact assessment is conducted by evaluating the selected impact categories using ILCD 2011 method. Results highlight the most impactful components of energy harvesters referring to the unique scores calculated for different impact categories at the Midpoint. They highlight also the importance of LCA and offer technical guidance and crucial recommendations for eco-design.

Keywords: Life cycle assessment, ecodesign, sustainability, energy harvesting, piezoelectric materials

1 Introduction

Piezoelectric materials have been widely investigated across various engineering fields over the past years, especially for self-powered sensing systems through energy harvesting techniques [1, 2, 3]. Zhang et al. [4] developed an energy harvester that captures rotational energy from machinery using an arc-shaped piezoelectric sheet placed between an outer race and the pedestal of the bearing. In addition to powering sensors, it can detect bearing faults. Its performance was successfully tested on a rotor test rig, demonstrating both fault detection and self-powered wireless sensing capabilities. Khazaei et al. [5] developed a self-powered condition monitoring system for rotating machines that generates energy from machine vibrations. Using a voltage multiplier, the system captures and stores energy to power a microcontroller and radiofrequency transmitter for real-time monitoring. By estimating the piezoelectric harvester output and refining the system with an electromechanical model, it was successfully tested on a water pump, where it autonomously detected faults. Hazeri et al. [6] explored the use of piezoelectric materials in tires to capture energy from

tire deformations, generating 2.31 W from 56 piezoelectric patches. Energy harvesting becomes more efficient as vehicle speed and weight increase, particularly when the elements are placed on the outer surface of the tire. However, the technology slightly increases the environmental impact, hence further research is required to assess its durability and longevity. Zheng et al. [7] reviewed advancements in piezoelectric wind energy harvesters, focusing on micro electromechanical systems (MEMS). They discussed piezoelectric material classifications and operational principles by exploring research from various perspectives. The review highlighted existing literature and future development directions by offering valuable insights for industry innovation.

The most commonly used piezoceramic for energy harvesting is lead zirconate titanate $\text{Pb}(\text{Zr,Ti})\text{O}_3$ (PZT), due to its high electromechanical conversion efficiency [8, 9]. Fernandes et al. [10, 11] introduced a piezoelectromagnetic energy harvester, which is manufactured using PZT screen-printing technology and featuring a centrally-supported meandering structure. Experimental tests on a fabricated harvester, which had a thick PZT layer printed on a stainless steel substrate, confirmed the accuracy of frequency response functions predicted through a finite elements model. The proposed design demonstrates a higher normalized power density compared to other MEMS-based piezoelectromagnetic devices and exhibits significant potential when compared to larger devices that utilize bulk or thin-film piezoelectrics. Tabora et al. [11] have developed a printed mechanical energy harvester for powering autonomous systems, especially micro-electromechanical systems. The resonant harvester consisted of a multilayer structure formed by a screen-printed PZT layer between two screen-printed gold electrodes and a stainless steel substrate. Santawitee et al. [12] introduced a cost-effective technology utilizing screen-printing to fabricate PZT-based microdisks with sacrificial layers. The study investigated the influence of different electrode materials, including Au and Ag/Pd, on the release behavior. A comparison of PZT particle sizes showed that microdisks made from nanometric PZT particles, combined with Ag/Pd electrodes, exhibited high electromechanical coupling efficiency. Despite the wide application of lead-based materials its use is limited by regulations aimed at environmental protection. Bell et al. [13] review the toxic effects of lead and outline existing regulations aimed at mitigating its environmental impact. Additionally, their research seeks to assess the risks linked to the production, utilization, and disposal of lead-based piezoelectric materials. The study highlights that the piezoelectric industry is contributing an increasing portion, around 0.1%, to electronic waste while intensifying the demand for lead-free alternatives. As a result, ongoing research has focused on developing lead-free piezoelectric materials that demonstrate promising performance.

Significant progress has been made over the last few years in developing lead-free piezoceramics to replace PZT in electromechanical devices. Rödel et al. [14] outlined guidelines for developing lead-free piezoelectric ceramics by focusing on selecting chemical elements based on cost, toxicity, and ionic polarizability. It discusses various crystal structures and phase diagrams with good piezoelectric properties and uses insights from density functional theory to refine these concepts. Moreover, several studies focus on the environmental assessment of lead- and lead-free piezoceramics based on their life cycle flowchart, as shown in Figure 1. Ibn-Mohammed et al. [15] highlighted the environmental advantages of potassium sodium niobate $(\text{K,Na})\text{NbO}_3$ (KNN), which is considered a less hazardous piezoelectric material compared to PZT, primarily due to its ~60 wt% Nb_2O_5 content. This makes it significantly less toxic to humans than lead oxide in piezoelectric applications. As a result, KNN and sodium bismuth titanate (NBT) have been proposed as alternatives to replace PZT in various electronic components due to its toxicity. Da Silva Lima et al. [16] performed a life cycle assessment to quantify the environmental impacts at the production of both FeNb and Nb_2O_5 , by using production data provided by the niobium manufacturer responsible for roughly 75% of the global market. Ibn-Mohammed et al. [17] conducted an environmental assessment comparing NBT, KNN and PZT for their potential transition from lab to market. The study found that NBT has a more favorable environmental profile than both KNN and PZT, primarily due to its lower energy consumption during synthesis and production. However, when comparing NBT to PZT specifically, Bi_2O_3 (used in NBT) has a greater environmental impact than PbO (used in PZT) in certain areas including climate change. Wu et al. [18] conducted a life cycle assessment comparing PZT and KNN-based ceramics with a volume of 0.001 m^3 from cradle to gate. The study found that PZT has a greater environmental impact than KNN ceramics, mainly due to the extraction and processing of lead. KNN ceramics account for only 28% of PZT's overall environmental impact in areas such as toxicity and resource use, making them a more eco-friendly option. However, KNN production still requires improvements to reduce energy consumption and emissions, particularly during Nb_2O_5 extraction. The study offers important insights into material sustainability.

This paper concentrates on assessing the environmental impact of a piezoelectric energy harvester produced through the screen-printing process detailed in these works [10, 11]. It marks an initial step towards adopting an eco-design approach aimed at replacing PZT with KNN, while preserving similar performance levels. Cradle-to-gate life cycle assessment will be performed using an appropriate method to calculate the

Figure 1: The flowchart of life cycle assessment of piezoceramics [18].

unique score for impact categories. This paper begins with a brief introduction highlighting advancements in energy harvesting using piezoelectric materials and the environmental need for lead-free alternatives in piezoceramics. The following sections cover specific topics: Section 2 introduces the methodology for conducting a life cycle assessment on a piezoelectric energy harvester, detailing the life cycle inventory (LCI), which includes identifying materials, estimating their weights, and assigning manufacturing processes to understand the sensor's structure. Section 3 presents the results and discussion, incorporating a life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) for selected environmental impact categories, along with initial interpretations. Section 4 concludes with technical recommendations for design improvements and sustainability.

2 Methodology

The case study involves conducting a LCA on a zigzag piezoelectric energy harvester, as described in the [10, 11] research study. The harvester is sized for a first resonance frequency of 60 Hz which corresponds to the resonance frequency of the power grid. The harvester is excited by an electromagnetic device with a permanent magnet mounted at its free end and a conductive wire is placed under the magnet with a well-defined spacing. The latter is supplied by an alternating current from the power supplier system. Consequently, a Lorentz-type excitation force is created which causes the harvester to vibrate. Figure 2 presents the real harvester along with a drawing illustrating its geometric dimensions. As mentioned in the introduction, the environmental impacts of this harvester will be assessed throughout its life cycle for both PZT and KNN piezoceramics.

Figure 2: The piezoelectric screen-printed energy harvester: (a) the physical harvester with an enlarged view, and (b) the design drawing with geometric dimensions [10, 11].

The LCA study aligns with the ISO 14040 and ISO 14044 standards, which outline the principles and specific requirements as well as offer guidelines for conducting LCA. The overall methodological structure of LCA is divided into four key stages [19]: (1) goal and scope definition, (2) inventory analysis, (3) impact assessment, and (4) interpretation.

2.1 Scope and goal

Conducting a LCA for the zig-zag piezoelectric harvesters involves several key steps. The objectives of the study are outlined below:

- Identify the components and stages that contribute most significantly to the overall environmental impact.
- Assess the environmental impacts associated with the harvester from the production phase through to its use phase.

The harvesters adhere to the same functional unit, possess identical lifespans, and operate under similar assumptions regarding transportation and usage until the end of their service life. Table 1 outlines the key elements of the LCA, including the functional unit, lifespan, system boundaries, and evaluation method. It offers a clear and concise overview of the essential aspects of the LCA by ensuring a thorough understanding of the assessment's parameters and objectives.

Table 1: The scope of the LCA of the piezoelectric energy harvester.

LCA Keys	Descriptions
Functional unit	Piezoelectric energy harvester converts the vibration into electrical signal during its lifespan.
Lifespan	It is assumed to be 3 years.
System Boundaries	Cradle-to-gate: From raw material extraction to use stage
Method/Normalization/Ponderation	European, ILCD 2011 Midpoint+/EC-JRC Global, Equal weighting
Environmental impact categories	16 indicators of Midpoint

2.2 Life cycle inventory analysis

Life cycle inventory (LCI) involves the collection and compilation of data within a defined system boundary by leading to the subsequent phase of life cycle impact assessment (LCIA). Based on laboratory estimates and literature reviews, LCI gathers detailed information on raw materials, energy use, product outputs, and environmental emissions throughout the life cycle of piezoelectric harvesters. As the second phase of life cycle assessment, LCI focuses on collecting and organizing data on processes according to the established system boundaries.

The characteristics of the harvester under examination are detailed in Table 2, outlining key attributes that contribute to its operational efficiency and durability. These specific features are not only integral to the harvester's ability to carry out its functional unit but also play a crucial role in its long-term performance and sustainability.

Table 2: Characteristics of piezoelectric energy harvester.

PEH architecture	Zig-zag
Layer materials	Stainless Steel (SS)/Au/PZT/Au
Technology	All layers are screen-printed on Stainless Steel substrate and co-fired
Area dimensions	11.5 mmx12.7 mm
Au thickness	$\sim 10\mu m$
PZT thickness	$\sim 50\mu m$
Energy harvesting test	Piezoelectric-magnetic principle

Throughout its lifespan, these core attributes ensure the harvester remains reliable and capable of meeting the demands of various operational conditions. Therefore, any design modifications or optimizations must take these characteristics into careful consideration. Preserving or enhancing these features is essential to maintaining the harvester’s functionality while adhering to the fundamental principles of ecodesign. This approach ensures that design improvements do not compromise environmental impact objectives, such as resource efficiency, reduced emissions, and minimal ecological footprint, which are central to sustainable product development.

In this study, lead zirconate titanate (PZT) and potassium sodium niobate (KNN) piezoceramics undergo similar preparation processes including weighing, ball milling, drying, calcination, re-milling, screen printing, layer pressing, and sintering. Electrical energy consumption for each of the manufacturing processes is calculated as follows:

$$E = \frac{P \times t}{1000} \quad (1)$$

where E is the electrical energy required (kWh), P is the electrical power (W), and t denotes the process time (h).

The electrical energy consumption inputted into our LCA model is taken from the study of Wu et al. [18], which provides the data necessary for the production of $0.001m^3$ of PZT and KNN. To determine the weight percentage of PZT chemical compositions, we used energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDXS), which provides detailed elemental and chemical analysis. Figure 3 shows the EDXS spectrum of the PZT powder with sintering aid, obtained under controlled experimental conditions with a 15 kV accelerating voltage and 4 μ -seconds sampling time. A preset time of 60 seconds was used to gather enough X-ray counts for accurate and reliable results.

Figure 3: The energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy spectra with microphotograph for PZT powder with sintering aid.

Our LCA study focuses on evaluating the stratified piezoelectric harvester composed of a linear-elastic substrate, a piezoceramic layer, and high electrical conductivity electrodes, as shown in Figure 4. The thin substrate is fabricated from stainless steel SS301, and the electrodes are printed from the commercial gold ink ESL8836 developed by ElectroScience. The piezoceramic layer is composed of 97%wt of Pz 26 powder, produced by Ferroperm Piezoceramics [20], and 3%wt of a sintering aid LBCu (0.8% Li_2CO_3 , 1.2% Bi_2O_3 , and 1% CuO by weight). The percentage of the chemical composition measured by weight of the PZT powder is given in the pie chart in Figure 4. The study involves analyzing resource use and environmental impacts. This includes aspects such as materials, energy inputs, transportation, manufacturing processes, and other relevant factors. The collected data of these different processes are then inputted into the LCA model which is powered by the Ecoinvent 3 database.

The study incorporates several assumptions regarding transportation and manufacturing locations, as well as the use scenarios. It is assumed that all components of the harvester are produced in France, with the supply chain confined to French territories within a maximum path of 1074 km. Additionally, electrical energy consumption for certain manufacturing processes is estimated based on data from similar previous

Figure 4: Piezoelectric energy harvester breakdown structure with the weight percentage of the chemical composition of the piezoceramic powder obtained with EDXS.

research studies. The comprehensive list of impact indicators based on elementary flows presents the output of LCI, which serves as input for the LCIA phase.

3 Results and discussion

Figure 5 presents a comparison of the environmental impact of PZT and KNN material extraction and processing across the 16 midpoint impact categories. The total impact score for PZT is 2.878, while for KNN it is 0.717, indicating that PZT’s environmental impact is approximately four times greater than that of KNN. For PZT, the most significantly impacted environmental aspects are mineral, fossil, and renewable resource depletion, freshwater ecotoxicity, and human toxicity (both cancer and non-cancer effects). Impact categories with unique scores less than 0.0039 Pt are assumed to be less impacted, which are grayed-out in the legend: climate change, ozone depletion, ... etc. Furthermore, water resource depletion and land use have the least environmental impact. For KNN, the most significantly impacted environmental aspects are the depletion of mineral, fossil, and renewable resources, as well as freshwater ecotoxicity and human toxicity (both carcinogenic and non-carcinogenic effects). However, the overall impact scores for these aspects are lower than those of PZT. The least impacted aspects of KNN are ozone depletion and land use. Ionizing radiation E (intermediate) is assessed as unaffected, and its unique score is zero for both PZT and KNN.

Figure 5: The unique score versus the piezoceramic materials (PZT and KNN) of the harvester for the 16 impact categories of Midpoint: The grayed-out impact categories are assumed to be unimpacted.

The environmental profiles of PZT and KNN are compared across the impact categories in Figure 6, providing a detailed assessment of their ecological footprints. These materials are evaluated based on their

respective ratios in the six impact categories mentioned above. KNN exhibits notable environmental burdens across all categories by reflecting its broad impact on the environment. In contrast, PZT shows a much higher ratio in certain categories, specifically in human toxicity, both carcinogenic and non-carcinogenic effects, ozone layer depletion, ionizing radiation, freshwater eutrophication, and freshwater ecotoxicity. These categories suggest that PZT's environmental cost is particularly severe in areas related to chemical toxicity and radiation exposure. Conversely, KNN's environmental impact is more concentrated in categories associated with atmospheric and land-related effects, such as particulate matter formation. The higher impacts in these areas are largely attributable to the initial stages of KNN's life cycle, notably during raw material extraction and purification processes. This highlights the significance of upstream activities in shaping KNN's environmental profile. While KNN's overall environmental burden may be lower than that of PZT in certain categories, its contributions to specific environmental stressors, particularly those linked to atmospheric and land-use impacts, remain significant. The comparison underscores the complex trade-offs involved in selecting materials, as neither PZT nor KNN can be considered universally superior in terms of environmental sustainability. Each material carries distinct ecological risks that must be weighed according to the application and environmental priorities.

Figure 6: The environmental profile of piezoceramic materials (PZT and KNN) of the harvester with the six considered impact categories.

Figure 7 presents the unique environmental score in Points (Pt) for the primary components of the harvester analyzed in LCA study. The unique score is derived from 16 selected impact categories at the Midpoint level, as previously described. Impact categories with unique scores below 0.0039 Pt are considered less significant and are shown in gray in the legend. According to the results, the most environmentally impactful component is the electrodes, with a unique score of 7.57, followed by the piezoceramic layer (PZT), which has a score of 2.88, and the stainless steel substrate SS301, with a score of 0.77. For the electrodes, the dominant impact categories include human toxicity (non-cancer effects), freshwater ecotoxicity, and human toxicity (cancer effects), signifying the considerable contribution of the electrodes to toxicological impacts on both human health and ecosystems. Specifically, the electrodes and the PZT layer demonstrate notably higher levels of human toxicity without carcinogenic effects, indicating potential risks to human health due to their material composition and production processes. Meanwhile, the substrate is most affected by climate change and ionizing radiation, particularly highlighting its contribution to global warming potential and human health risks from radiation exposure. Notably, ionizing radiation emerges as a significant concern across all components of the harvester. This can be attributed to the energy mix utilized in the LCA, which reflects the characteristics of French high-voltage nuclear electricity production, which is known for its radiation-related impacts due to nuclear power dependency. These findings emphasize the importance of material selection and energy sourcing in minimizing environmental and health impacts in the production and operation of the harvester.

Figure 7: The unique score versus the different part of the harvester for the 16 impact categories of Midpoint: The grayed-out impact categories are assumed to be unimpacted.

4 Conclusions

This research compares the environmental impacts of PZT and KNN materials by highlighting that PZT has a significantly higher total environmental impact, about four times greater than KNN, particularly in areas like resource depletion, toxicity, and ecotoxicity. However, KNN also has its environmental burdens, especially in categories related to atmospheric and land effects, such as climate change and acidification, largely driven by its early life cycle processes like raw material extraction. Both materials show trade-offs in their environmental profiles. While PZT is particularly harmful in toxicity and radiation-related categories, KNN has notable impacts on land use and atmospheric emissions. Neither material can be considered universally better in terms of sustainability; the selection between them should depend on the specific application and environmental priorities. Additionally, the study of the harvester's components shows that environmental impact of electrodes are determined the most significant, which is followed by the PZT layer with significant contributions to human toxicity and ecotoxicity. The precise chemical composition of Au ink, along with thorough environmental assessment, is necessary for optimization and could be a focus of our study. The stainless-steel substrate has a lesser but still notable impact, especially in climate change and ionizing radiation. The importance of energy sourcing, particularly from nuclear power in France, is emphasized due to its contribution to radiation-related environmental impacts.

Acknowledgments

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NUMERICAL ANALYSIS OF MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR USING BIO-COMPATIBLE MATERIAL FOR DENTAL PROSTHESIS

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Abstract. Recent technological advancement has revolutionized the field biomedical engineering and has significantly enhanced the well being of human life. From the design and manufacturing of bio-compatible materials to the development of software for computer-aided design (CAD) modeling and simulation, biotechnology plays a crucial role in creating safe and effective dental implants. Finite element analysis has been accustomed to simulating the stresses and strains on implants helping to optimize the design and insertion process. This study aims to compare the stress profiles of Polyetheretherketone (PEEK) and Titanium alloy dental implants during different stages of implant insertion depths. The study builds bone-blood interface CAD models and performs numerical simulations. The results indicate that PEEK is potentially capable of replacing Titanium alloy as a suitable material for dental implants. Additionally, the study evaluates von Mises stresses in cortical and cancellous bone and considers the impact of torque and insertion depth on stress profiles, as well as strain and deformation calculations. The results provide an insight into the usage of biocompatible materials in dental implants.

Keywords: Dental prosthesis, finite element analysis, insertion torque, biocompatible materials.

1 INTRODUCTION

Dental implants are prosthetic devices that are used to replace missing or damaged teeth. They are typically made of biocompatible materials like titanium or ceramic and are surgically inserted into the jawbone. The use of dental implants has emerged as increasingly popular in recent years due to their many benefits over traditional dentures or bridges. The global market for dental implants is projected to reach 6.81 billion by 2024, according to Grand View Research, Inc.[7]. The contemporary dental implant is a safe medically approved prosthesis that is placed through surgery through the mandible to restore one or more missing teeth usually made of titanium. If the screws are properly manufactured and implemented there is a high success rate of more than 95% maintenance over a five-year period [1] [2] [3].

Experts in implant dentistry strongly believe that a substantial percentage of the 5% of fails are due to imprecise insertion techniques. The use of finite element method for the placement of dental implants aims to increase the predictability and credibility of the process. Implant failure could be lessened by analyzing the stress distribution within the surrounding bone tissue during insertion. [4]. Evaluating stress profiles in the cortical and cancellous bone besides considering the outcomes of the experiment

of elements like implant design, material qualities, and surgical method are all included in the scope of FEM analysis in dental implantation. According to various studies that have examined the external geometry of implants, those with conical or tapered designs displayed greater initial mechanical anchorage and compared to those with an oblique shape, primary stability. [6]. Sugiura et al. proposed considering the height of the cortical bone crest can have a substantial impact on the maximum level of various clinical and experimental research.[7] Pure titanium or titanium alloys make up most of the dental implant systems that are now used in clinical procedures, including Straumann, Nobel Biocare, Dentsply Sirona, Zimmer Biomet, and BioHorizons. Despite their satisfactory short-term outcomes with a success rate of 90% after five years, their long term results are not entirely satisfactory, with a failure rate of up to 35% after ten years. Recent studies have demonstrated improved outcomes attributed to dental companies' contributions, with short-term failure rates reduced to 0.7-4% and over 95% of implants surviving for five years after implantation in most statistical cases [8].

According to according to Hannam et al. [9], to ensure the validity and accuracy of FEA studies, it is necessary to make comparisons with data obtained from other research or from the living subjects being modelled. Studies have shown that higher insertion torques can have an impact on the peri implant bone tissue, increasing tensile and compressive stresses [10]. Although Atieh et al. focused on stress distributions near immediately inserted implants with a wider diameter, they observed a similar pattern. FEA can be used in the medical industry to assess any structure or tissue's response to a certain stimulation and examine any biomechanical changes in the tissues. [11][12] [13].

The most well-known biomedical alloys for dental applications are Titanium (Ti) and Zirconia (Zr) [14]. Stainless steel, for bone structures and screws, 316L stainless steel was traditionally employed as an implant material but not been approved as a dental implant material. Cobalt-based alloys cast partial denture structures have been made for decades. And they are also used to framework hip prosthesis [15]. In a study, tantalum was used as a dental implant material. These implants showed a process of submerged healing that combines gradual osseointegration at the titanium interface with bone formation and differentiation inside of their permeable tantalum region. [16] [17]. In a study on rats, Webster et al. [18] investigated silicon nitride's biocompatibility and stability and discovered that it was even more bone responsive than titanium and polyether ether ketone.

PEEK, a semicrystalline linear polycyclic thermoplastic that has been proposed as a metal substitute in biomaterials and has FDA approval to be employed as an implantable material [19]. PEEK further exhibited high processability, manufacturing techniques such as injection molding and 3D printing were common [20]. PEEK slightly lessens Young's modulus in both porous and dense forms, and the addition of inorganic reinforcing phases is necessary, which has been extensively investigated. Carbon fiber is an essential reinforcing material that has been extensively employed in various fields, and carbon-fiber reinforced PEEK (CFR-PEEK) has proven to be advantageous as an implant material. Although the addition of a small amount of ZrO_2 nanoparticles was found to improve mechanical properties and reduce stress concentration at the carbon fiber interface. Hydroxyapatite, the primary component of natural bone, has great biocompatibility and is bioactive, making it the appropriate reinforcer phase in implantology. Several volume percentages of in the initial study of strengthened PEEK with HA [21].

The presiding objective referring this research work is to simulate a realistic implantation process using FEA. To achieve this, build a 3D representation of the implant. Subsequently, they construct models for the cortical and cancellous bone. The aim of present study is to focus on the torque exerted on the different steps of insertion dental implant with varying bio-compatible materials.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

FEA is a useful and effective method for analyzing complex biomechanical problems on a macro scale. This study employs two distinct types of models. The first model employs Ti-6Al-4V as the material for the dental implant, while the second model uses PEEK as the implant material. Models are kept consistent except for the material properties.

The implant, abutment, and screw are modeled as isotropic, homogeneous, and linear elastic. However, anisotropic materials comprises bone, cortical and cancellous bone as non-linear material, is incorporated in Table 1. It should be noted that the anisotropic modeling approach can lead to up to a 70% increase in stress and strain compared to isotropic models. To replicate a realistic implan-

Figure 1: Mesh Implant-Bone Model

tation process, the dental implant, cortical bone, and cancellous bone are produced as 3D models in CAD software. The 3D models of a dental implant embedded in cortical and cancellous bones along with blood interface and transient structural analysis is done. The implant features parallel 1 mm pitch threads and is cylindrical with a single threaded taper. The cortical bone, which encircles the cancellous bone, has a thickness of 1.31 mm. The intact height of the model with bone is 18 mm and the width of the bone is 14mm. The diameter of the dental implant is $\phi 3.5$ at the top and it extends to $\phi 4.5$ as threads start. The implants bottom diameter is $\phi 2.5$. Mesh creation is an essential step in finite element analysis. An intermediate size mesh is selected. The implant model, shown in figure 1, consists of brick elements 3262 and 12292 nodes. The jawbone section for the analysis, with an extent of 1.3mm for the cortical bone and 19878 brick elements and 10396 nodes, and 1460 block elements and 2454 nodes for the cancellous bone. In an entire implant placed, the total numbers of elements are 28265 and 57621 nodes for the intact implant and mandible model, respectively.

A blood-bone interface of 0.5mm is considered for contact of implant with tissue purpose. This study comprises fixed limits in the one direction displayed in and time-dependent torque imposed at the implant's top. One of the objectives on this subject research is to explore the impact of incorporating a PEEK composite material aimed at the fixture/implant on the dissipation of stress within the surrounding peri-implant bone. The study aims to evaluate the effects of the physical association that occurs amongst different interacting bodies during the exertion of torque to the peri-implant bone, through numerical analysis.

Table 1: Material properties used in the study

S/N	Material	Young's Modulus (GPa)	Modulus of Rigidity (GPa)	Modulus of Elasticity (GPa)	Poisson's Ratio	Density
1	Ti-6Al-4V	102			0.3	4.5
2	CFR-PEEK	18			0.39	1.32
3	Blood Interface	0.07			0.3	1.5
4	Cortical Bone		$G_x = 5$ $G_y = 7.4$ $G_z = 5.5$	$E_x = 12.7$ $E_y = 17.9$ $E_z = 22.8$	$\nu_x = 0.18$ $\nu_y = 0.21$ $\nu_z = 0.32$	1.5
5	Cancellous Bone		$G_x = 0.068$ $G_y = 0.434$ $G_z = 0.068$	$E_x = 0.21$ $E_y = 1.148$ $E_z = 1.148$	$\nu_x = 0.055$ $\nu_y = 0.31$ $\nu_z = 0.055$	1.5

3 STRESS PROFILES AT CORTICAL AND CANCELLOUS BONE

The intent of the analysis characterizes replicating the process of inserting a dental implant into the jawbone in a dynamic manner. However, due to modeling difficulties such as auto-remeshing, a simplified modeling approach is proposed to step-by-step simulate and recreate the implantation process, a few models using finite elements are designed. Each model represents a new implant placement depth, with a start from 0.5mm and increasing by 1 mm until the full 11 mm length the structure of the jawbone once the implant has been inserted.

Figure 2: Ti Stress Profile Cortical & Cancellous Bone (0.5mm-2mm)

The appropriate torque is applied during the first nine seconds of implant placement, exerted torque applied to the implant's upper portion abruptly changes from 0 to 450 N mm and stayed there for 23 seconds (8 mm depth), and then increased up to 1000 N mm during the final 14 sec of the process. The non-linear transient dynamic analysis considered the material non-linearity according to the stress strain graph.

Figure 3: CFR-PEEK Stress profile Cortical and Cancellous bone(0.5mm-1mm)

The stress magnitude varies by a maximum of 0.4 MPa during the time period between 0.5-2 sec. The results shows comparatively lowest stress in the cancellous bone since the implant does not come in immediate interaction with it. During this stage, the cancellous bone only experiences stress that is transmitted by ensuring its interaction with the cortical bone. From the time period of 2.5-5 sec, there is an immediate increase in the stress profile magnitude. The cancellous bone is in touch with the primary filament from the implant's bottom, and the cortical bone is interacting with the second thread. The stress pattern exhibits a minimal peak at 0.5 mm a consequence of the bottom thread's sole interaction with a cancellous bone at a single spot, resulting in a focus under stress. For detailed explanation of the methodology, and computational approach used in this study, refer to Ahmed Dogar, Ayesha (2023). Numerical analysis of mechanical behavior of bio-compatible materials for Dental Prosthesis-A Finite Element Analysis. Master's Thesis, National University of Science and Technology, Pakistan.

Since the exerted torque is constant across 8.5 and 26 sec, these steps are merged. As the amount of applied torque increases, the tension along the cortical bone increases. From 29.5 to 33 sec, the

stress profile exhibits a similar pattern to the previous stage from 26 to 29 sec, with a slight reduction in stress levels. The key factor causing the reduction in stress levels is the expanded surface area of contact among the implant and cancellous bone.

To promote healthy bone growth recommended a stress range in the cancellous bone of 1.72 to 2.76 MPa. A significant portion of the observed stress levels from 5.5 to 36 s lie between 2.72 and 3.76 MPa, and the stress level from 0.5 to 5 s is below 1.76 MPa. At the lower and upper thread levels, some stress peaks, though, are greater than 2.76 MPa. To reach the desired stress levels that would result in the best osseointegration, proper management of the time dependent torque is essential [11].

Figure 4: Deformation & Strain

For the time period of 0.5 to 2.5 sec, the maximal stress increases from the distance from the implant to 8 to 12 MPa. In contrast as, when the distance from the implant neck rises, the stress magnitude considerably declines to less than 2-4 MPa. During the time range between 2.5 and 5 sec the stress at the implant neck increases to an assortment of 12-22 MPa in comparison onto first stage. This is possibly due to the moment that is applied via the implant being aggregated amongst the cortical and cancellous bone, thereby step downing the stress in the contact of the implant thread. Consequently, the stress peak occurs 1 mm away from the implant. It ranges from 23-30 MPa stress profiles, occurs at the implant top, which is double as in the preceding stage.

Table 2: Results of the simulations performed at different depths of dental implant torque varying with respect to time

S/N	MATERIAL	DEPTH (mm)	STRESS		STRAIN	DEFORMATION (mm)
			Cortical	in MPa Cancellous		
1	Ti Alloy	0.5	11.709	0.9560	0.0506	0.0068
2		1	17.005	4.2639	0.00016	0.00012
3		2	25.52	3.4318	0.0155	0.00543
4		3-7	34.992	1.049	0.0077	0.00019
5		8	9.8149	3.9835	0.00540	0.00195
6		9	17.475	5.3693	0.00207	0.01130
7		10	23.776	5.2319	0.00247	0.0310
8		11	32.951	4.8446	0.0166	0.0105
9	CFR-PEEK	0.5	8.5862	0.8421	0.0021	0.00166
10		1	9.3958	2.2968	0.00535	0.00177
11		2	12.817	3.0908	0.00252	0.00118
12		3-7	21.583	1.6572	0.00118	0.00028
13		8	12.979	4.3138	0.00434	0.00241
14		9	17.568	4.6577	0.05638	0.0113
15		10	23.766	5.0936	0.03016	0.07575
16		11	32.951	4.8446	0.0166	0.01057

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This simulation describes stress profiles during different stages of dental implant insertion using material Titanium and CFR-PEEK. The results represents that as the depth of insertion of dental implant increases the value of applied torque also increases varying with respect to time evaluated in Table 2. When the implant encounter fluid (blood vessels) the strain dissipates in the three bodies two bones and blood interface.

To accurately simulate this process, frictional contact is used. For analysing the interaction that occurs between contacting bodies, the ANSYS Software offers a variety of settings, namely frictional, free of friction, rough, bonded, no separation, and additional. In cemented contact, the bodies are perfectly glued together, whereas sliding motion is allowed in frictional contact. For interaction between the cement layer and abutment, the abutment and fixture, and the cancellous bone and cortical bone, bonded contact is used.

The von Mises stresses are plotted at selected salient axes parallel the cancellous and cortical bones for every stage of implant insertion. The stress level increases with an increase in torque for all insertion depths. During the starting stage, the implant only comes in liaison with the cortical bone, resulting in adequately lessen stress in the cancellous bone. The stress magnitude decreases significantly as far as the implant is located. The stress reduction within the cancellous bone is expected due to the initial layer of interstitial blood and fragments of, which comes into proximity to the cortical bone. The top bottom segment of cancellous bone received greater stress levels. Maximum stress on the cortical bone was close towards the implant neck, and it grew with intervals and implantation depth. Since the implant is in having linear interaction therewith the cancellous bone at the implant's base

without any blood-bone interface, have high stress.

The stress distribution in the top portion of the implant is not significantly affected by friction coefficients that fluctuate between 0.1 to 0.4 sec. The highest stress values are observed in the cortical bone at the top bone-implant interaction, rather than in the cancellous bone. Cortical bone having high Young's modulus can absorb more torque than the cancellous bone. The findings suggest that no discernible change exists in stress distribution among the titanium alloy and PEEK studied. The cortical bone has both the greatest maximal and lowest minimal primary stresses.

As different models are simulated, the level of strains ascends 0.0035 mm. Specifically, the induced strain is found to be the highest when it comes to the PEEK implant. The maximum deformation in all the models is mostly around 0.01 due to the varied applied torque. All models have strains 0.001 to 0.021mm. Figure 4 shows the deformation and strain caused due to applied torque to the implant-bone model. In every model that is analyzed, it is observed that the implant-bone interface consistently experienced the greatest amount of strain.

However, these findings contradict the clinical observations that dental implants are highly successful. One possible explanation is considering the principles of "Frost's mechanostat theory", which accommodate long skeletal bones well and may not be applicable to alveolar bone. The study's findings will help dentists to carry out a patient specific implant procedure in an enhanced quality controlled way.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The research proposes an effective 3- dimensional modelling method to investigate stress distribution due to time-dependent torque during the implantation process, considering the biomechanical implant-jawbone relationship as well as realistic shape, material qualities, loading, and support requirements for the corresponding implant and the jawbone.

The study evaluates load transfer and stress distribution in peri-implant bone. The research identifies that the choice of contact type between occlusal surfaces can result in inaccurate stress distribution, and friction coefficients have minimal effect.

Future research will explore the impact of designing different screw geometries and complex bone structures. In accordance with on initial findings, more advanced methods could be used to fully simulate the dynamic implantation process.

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CURE MONITORING OF EPOXY STRUCTURAL ADHESION USING LAMB WAVES AND THE DISCRETE WAVELET TRANSFORM

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ABSTRACT

Epoxy adhesives have extensive applications in the aerospace industry. In this study, the curing behaviour of pre-impregnated epoxy adhesive was monitored using guided ultrasonic Lamb waves. These waves were excited and recorded using ultrasonic transducers. This study aims to analyze the recorded Lamb wave data using the discrete wavelet transform (DWT). A 5-level DWT was performed on the recorded ultrasonic signals. The approximation and detail coefficients of the signals were analyzed to extract the evolution of the degree of cure (DOC) as a function of time. The results were then validated using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). The results have shown that the DOC obtained from the DWT matches the one obtained using DSC. This method was able to detect the start time and end time of the curing process. The correlation between the two DOCs was found to be $R^2 = 0.68$ indicating that ultrasonic Lamb waves can be used as a real time monitoring method for the degree of cure of a material during the manufacturing process.

Keywords: Cure monitoring, Degree of cure, Lamb waves, Signal processing, Discrete Wavelet transform.

1 INTRODUCTION

Cure monitoring is the study of the curing reaction of a material in real-time. This process has been more frequently applied in industrial applications since it can guarantee the quality and the mechanical properties of the finished product. In polymer chemistry, curing refers to the toughening of a polymer solution by cross-linking its polymer chains at high temperatures. Cure monitoring can be done through various methods such as thermal imaging, differential scanning calorimetry, and ultrasonic methods. Cure monitoring through guided ultrasonic Lamb waves is a widely used method that assesses the group velocity of the waves propagating between the actuator and the sensor [1]. Named after the mathematician Horace Lamb, Lamb waves are elastic waves that travel on the surface of solid structures plates, rods, and shells. Since the 1990s, the understanding and utilization of Lamb waves have advanced significantly, especially in the field of non-destructive testing. These waves play a crucial role in assessing material integrity without causing damage. Lamb waves propagate through plate-like structures in two possible configurations: symmetric or the S_0 mode and antisymmetric or the A_0 mode. The propagation of the Lamb waves in an isotropic plate that is unbound in the x and y directions is described by the following set of simplified equations [2]:

$$\frac{\omega^4}{C_T^4} = 4k^2 q^2 \left[1 - \frac{p \tan \left(\frac{ph}{2} + \gamma \right)}{q \tan \left(\frac{ph}{2} + \gamma \right)} \right] \quad (1)$$

$$p^2 = \frac{\omega^2}{C_L^2} - k^2 \quad (2)$$

$$q^2 = \frac{\omega^2}{C_T^2} - k^2 \quad (3)$$

where γ represents the phase of the S and A wave modes for values of 0 and $\frac{\pi}{2}$, respectively, h is the plate's thickness, ω is the angular frequency and k is the wave number. C_L and C_T are respectively the longitudinal and

transverse velocities of the Lamb wave in the bulk material. Lamb waves are complex vibrational waves that propagate parallel to the test surface throughout the thickness of the material. Their propagation depends on the material properties, frequency, and thickness, making them valuable for various practical applications in material science.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Cure monitoring using ultrasonic Lamb waves

Ultrasonic testing using guided Lamb waves is an extensively researched tool in the field of composite materials. Applications of these waves include testing the structural integrity of the composite material and in-process cure monitoring of the composite during the manufacturing process. Lamb waves are used to identify various viscoelastic stages of the manufacturing process. As the material cures, it undergoes various transformations such as gelation, vitrification, and glass transition. Monitoring these changes is crucial to ensure the composite's quality and performance.

Mahfoud et al [1] studied the curing reaction of carbon fiber prepregs using guided ultrasonic Lamb waves. The prepregs were cured in the oven by ramping the temperature from 25°C to 70°C and then 120°C. The cure monitoring process was done by using two Teflon layers in which two piezoelectric sensors were sandwiched. This sensing system is placed directly in contact with the laminate as it can give a very good output signal of the Lamb wave propagation through the material. To excite the Lamb waves, a five-peak sinusoidal Hanning window was generated. The amplified signal to the actuator has a 160V peak-to-peak amplitude with a certain frequency of 70 kHz. The oscilloscope was used to collect the data at a sampling rate of 1 sample/10mins. The group velocity and the amplitude of the anti-symmetric mode A_0 was estimated from the distance between the transmitter and the sensor which is covered by the time of flight of the anti-symmetric Lamb wave mode. All three curing parameters: minimum viscosity, gelation, and vitrification were detected in both generated graphs. The results of the ultrasonic testing were validated against the dynamic mechanical analysis test where the curing parameters were also identified. This study has proved the potential of using a reusable Teflon film as a sensing medium for the in-situ cure monitoring of prepreg carbon fiber. It also proposed shortening the cure cycle of the tested prepreg by 1 hour. The carbon fiber prepreg with a shortened cure cycle was tested for its tensile strength using a universal testing machine. The experimental results showed that by reducing the cure cycle by 1 hour, the cure behavior of the prepreg is shifted by 1 hour without significant change in its mechanical properties.

2.2 Digital signal processing of ultrasonic Lamb waves

One of the major challenges in ultrasonic cure monitoring is relating the recorded signal to the actual physical changes happening during the curing [3]. To help interpret the complex signals obtained from Lamb waves, various signal processing methods have been implemented. Recent methods include Wavelet transforms, the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT), and the Hilbert transform (HT). Hilbert transform is used for the time domain processing, the Fourier transform is used for the frequency domain processing, and the Wavelet Transform is used to analyze both time and frequency domains simultaneously.

The Fast Fourier Transform (FFT)

The Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) is an algorithm that efficiently computes the Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) of a sequence or its inverse (IDFT). In this method, the observed Lamb wave amplitude-time recording is converted into recordings of the wave numbers at discrete frequencies [4]. The FFT has found application mostly in structural health monitoring (SHM) applications. For instance, Alem et.al [5] used the FFT and time of flight (TOF) techniques to estimate the size and location of damage instantaneously without the need for prior baseline signals. Regarding cure monitoring, the FFT is underrepresented in the literature. Such studies often favor other digital signal processing methods such as the Hilbert Transform and the Wavelet Transform.

The Hilbert Transform (HT)

The Hilbert transform is a valuable tool in Structural Health Monitoring (SHM). It aids in damage detection and localization by analyzing data from distributed sensors. The Hilbert-Huang transform (HHT) is one of the most

popular signal processing methods in SHM. This filter combines empirical mode decomposition with the Hilbert spectral transform, making it adaptive for analyzing stationary, non-stationary, and transient signals in SHM. Shahri et.al [6], used the HT to characterize the failure mechanisms in laminated composite materials. The HT method was applied to correlate acoustic emission signals with their corresponding failure modes. The experimental analysis focused on glass/epoxy laminated composites subjected to an end notch flexure test which simulates delamination. By analyzing the phase angle of the Hilbert transform, the frequency range associated with damage mechanisms occurring at different loading stages was identified. Additionally, scanning electron microscopy provided visual insights into the cracked surfaces. The results demonstrated the practical applicability of the proposed acoustic emission-based HT method for characterizing damage mechanisms in laminates, with strong agreement between the findings and microscopic images.

The HT finds valuable applications in field of cure monitoring of composite materials. It improves the process of cure monitoring by revealing valuable insights into the curing process and its effects on the quality of composite materials. In [3], the authors investigated the usage of the Hilbert transform for extracting the instantaneous features of the Lamb wave response. For this purpose, symmetric carbon fiber prepreg laminates were manufactured in a (0/90)_s stacking sequence. Two piezoelectric sensors were attached to the surface of the prepreg, which were operating in a pitch-catch mode. The input signal has the following characteristics: 185 kHz excitation frequency, 10V peak to peak amplitude and a 5-cycle sine pulse modulated by a Hanning window. The data acquisition was performed on an oscilloscope with 50 Ms/s (Mega samples/seconds). The recorded signals were decomposed and then filtered using the HT from which the frequency and amplitude of the signals were extracted. The results given by the HT exhibited two noise heavy regions and a structural region in which the characteristics of the signal reflect the physical changes in the curing reaction. The changes in the frequency and amplitude in the structural region are directly correlated with the change in the material viscosity. This allows for the identification of the major curing regions: minimum viscosity, gelation, and vitrification.

The Wavelet Transform

The usage of wavelet transform-based methods to analyze ultrasonic signals is rather popular. However, it is underutilized in cure monitoring studies that use ultrasonic-guided Lamb waves. The wavelet transform provides a method to analyze the time and frequency domains simultaneously [7]. A wavelet, $\psi(t)$, is a rapidly decaying, wave-like oscillation. It enables the representation of data across multiple scales, making it suitable for various applications in signal processing. Generally, it is a function characterized by its zero average, scale parameter s , and time shift u [8]:

$$\Psi_{us}(t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{s}} \psi\left(\frac{t-u}{s}\right) \quad (4)$$

The wavelet transform $Wf(u, s)$ of a signal $f(t)$ is computed by the inner product of $f(t)$ with a wavelet atom:

$$Wf(s, u) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} f(t) \psi^*\left(\frac{t-u}{s}\right) dt \quad (5)$$

Where ψ^* represents the complex conjugate of the wavelet atom. These wavelets, when combined with shifts of a real-valued low-pass scaling function $\phi(t)$, form an orthonormal basis expansion for the one-dimensional continuous time signal $f(t)$. This finite energy signal can be therefore decomposed into wavelets and scaling functions as follows [9]:

$$f(t) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} c(n) \phi(t-n) + \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} d(j, n) 2^{j/2} \psi(2^j t - n) \quad (6)$$

This decomposition is referred to as the Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT) of the continuous time signal $f(t)$. The scaling coefficients $c(n)$ and wavelet coefficients $d(j, n)$ are computed via the inner products:

$$c(n) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x(t) \phi(t-n) dt \quad (7)$$

$$d(j, n) = 2^{j/2} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x(t) \psi(2^j t - n) dt \quad (8)$$

Application of the Wavelet Transform and its variants in Lamb wave analysis

The wavelet transform has various applications in the non-destructive testing (NDT) field of material science. In particular, it had extensive utility in Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) and Cure Monitoring applications.

In SHM studies, the nature of the recorded signal allows the relaxation of the filter constraints. The filter does not need to be time invariant as the Lamb waves recorded in SHM studies do not change over time. This allows for the researcher to use any of the variants of the wavelet transform. For instance, recent damage detection studies have employed the continuous wavelet transform (CWT) as a tool to analyze Lamb wave signals. Saqib, Zheng, and Kaihong [10] estimated structural damage using the CWT. The ultrasonic sensing configuration consisted of PZT actuators and sensors mounted on a platelike structure. The plate was discretized into several points and the likelihood of damage at each grid point is directly determined by the coefficients of the CWT. By applying the CWT coefficients, which are based on the Gabor wavelet, to signals scattered by damage, an envelope was created for each actuator-sensor pair. The results have proven that, by using the CWT, damage can be detected and localized using only the signals detected from the damaged plate. This method eliminates the need to have a baseline or undamaged signal in damage detection studies. In a similar study, Zheng et al. [11] used the CWT to detect the damage in the plate based on the time of flight of the second harmonic Lamb wave. The bump wavelet functions were effectively used to detect the components of the second harmonic Lamb wave. The time of flight was then extracted from the signal using the Gabor wavelet function.

SHM studies can also employ the DWT to analyze Lamb wave signals. In [8], the DWT was used to extract the relevant features from noisy ultrasonic Lamb wave signals. The experimental setup consisted of a steel plate where artificial damage was created. Ultrasonic Lamb waves were generated at a frequency of 1.9 MHz received by a digitizing oscilloscope and amplified by a band-pass filter between 0.9 and 5.5MHz. Images of the artificial defects were generated based on the computed wavelet coefficients. The results showed that analyzing the real ultrasonic signals yielded more precise damage detection. Using the DWT method to analyze Lamb wave signals permits the extraction of the relevant features in the time-frequency domain without needing to return to the time domain. This is an advantage that the DWT has over more traditional methods of analysis, such as the Fourier transform.

The usage of the wavelet transform has not been extensively studied in cure monitoring applications. The study conducted by Koichi and Ogi [12] presented a method for evaluating the degree of cure of a carbon fiber prepreg based on the CWT. 10 layers of CFRP prepreg were laid up for the cure monitoring experiment. The ultrasonic testing setup consisted of 3 PZT sensors, where one acted as the actuator and the other acted as the receiver. The CFRP was cured in an electric oven by ramping the temperature from 25°C to 160°C at a rate of 2°C/min and then holding the temperature at 160°C for 5hrs. The CWT and HT were used to obtain the viscoelastic properties of the prepreg (gelation and vitrification) during its curing cycle. The group velocity and the attenuation of the Lamb waves relate to the degree of cure by the following equation:

$$\alpha(t) = \frac{1}{L_2 - L_1} \log \frac{A_1 \sqrt{L_1}}{A_2 \sqrt{L_2}} \quad (9)$$

Where L_1 , L_2 are the distances between the actuator and the first and second receivers, respectively. A_1 and A_2 represent the peaks of the CWT envelope for each sensor, respectively. The results of the ultrasonic method were validated experimentally using dynamic mechanical analysis. The material properties generated by this method were proven to be useful in modeling the curing process using numerical simulation.

In cure monitoring, the Lamb wave signals are affected by the evolution of the temperature as a function of time and material properties. Hence the filter applied in processing these signals needs to be time invariant and be able to detect features in higher dimensions. Therefore, the Dual-Tree Complex Wavelet transform (DTCWT) was proposed as a more suitable digital signal processing technique than the traditional DWT in this domain [13]. Holst et al. [13] monitored the curing process of a thin plate of CFRPs using guided Lamb waves. The prepreg was heated linearly to 160°C by increments of 2°C/min starting at room temperature. The piezoelectric actuators were excited by a single pulse square wave within the frequency interval of 150kHz to 400kHz with a frequency step size of 2kHz. The recorded signals were then analyzed using a variant of the DTCWT. This method is more robust in cure monitoring due to its almost time invariance by using two parallel wavelet transforms. This method allows estimation of the degree of cure of the prepreg by detecting the change in the resonance frequency, and the energy transmitted by the dominant wavelet. For instance, the vitrification of the prepreg was captured by noting the time at which the energy transmitted begins to increase. In addition, the attenuation of the energy transmitted is an indication of the final degree of cure which is indicated by the stop in change of the transmitted energy. The degree of cure was then determined by the energy of the dominant wavelet coefficient and its corresponding resonance

frequency. The multi-sensor Lamb wave approach ensures more homogeneous curing and facilitates the detection of defects using non-destructive methods.

This study aims to test the viability of the wavelet transform in the digital signal processing of Lamb wave signals. We are interested in the cure monitoring experiment of epoxy adhesives. The wavelet transform will be used to estimate the degree of cure of the adhesive as a function of time. These results will be validated against the experimental of the differential scanning calorimetry.

3 MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Experimental setup

In the cure monitoring experiment, 7 layers of epoxy adhesive film (XPREG-XA120) were stacked to form a plate with a thickness of 1 mm. The plate has the dimensions of $32 \times 35 \text{ cm}^2$. Figure 1 shows the uncured adhesive plate and the two PZTs glued directly on top of it. The actuator and the sensor are labeled as A and S, respectively. The PZTs are disc-shaped PZT-5J material type with 0.5 mm thickness, 7 mm diameter, and have 320°C Curie temperature. The PZT actuator is excited using a five-peak sinusoidal signal multiplied by a Hanning window. The PZT sensor feeds the data into an oscilloscope which is recording it every five minutes. The epoxy plate is cured by ramping from room temperature up to 120°C with a heating rate of $3^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$, then holding isothermal curing conditions for one hour at the said temperature, then cooling naturally.

Figure 1: Experimental setup of epoxy cure monitoring

3.2 Signal processing

The Lamb wave signals collected from the cure monitoring experiment will be analyzed using a variant of the Wavelet transform. Since Lamb waves transport kinetic energy, the degree of cure $\alpha(t)$ of the prepreg will be determined by the wavelet coefficients. The signal processing analysis was done using Python and the wavelet transform package Pywavelets [14].

Optimal wavelet selection

In wavelet transform analysis, the choice of the mother wavelet or the basis function determines the accuracy and efficiency of the results. By choosing the optimal mother wavelet, important features of a Lamb wave signal such as the time of flight can be extracted on both time and frequency domains. The selection of the mother wavelet is usually done using Shannon's entropy. Shannon's entropy is a measure of randomness in a closed system which also reflects the energy concentration of a signal along with the uncertainty associated with it. For a process $P = [p_1, p_2, \dots, p_n]$, the simplified Shannon's entropy is given by [15]:

$$S(P) = \sum_{i=1}^n p_i \ln p_i \quad (10)$$

A library L , containing Daubechies, Haar, and Symlet wavelets. The selection process starts by choosing a mother wavelet M ($M \in \{L\}$) and applying it to each of the 33 signal samples $x_i(t)$. The mother wavelet is selected to have the minimum entropy of all the ones in the library L . In practice, it is useful to calculate the energy-to-entropy ratio of the signal. The signal energy-to-entropy ratio (EER) is a measure that can be used to assess the quality or characteristics of a signal. EER is calculated according to the following equation:

$$EER[n] = \frac{\sum_{k=0}^l |x_k|^2}{S_p[n]} \quad (11)$$

Where n is the number of the signal samples ($0 \leq n \leq 33$) and l is the length of each signal ($0 \leq l \leq 2000$).

DWT

The 33 obtained Lamb wave signals were run through a 5-level DWT decomposition using the chosen mother wavelet. The input signal $x[n]$ is split equally and then passed through a low-pass filter $h_0[n]$ and a high pass filter $h_1[n]$. The output of the low pass branch is the approximation coefficients $A_1[n]$ while the output of the high pass branch is the detail coefficients $D_1[n]$. In a multilevel DWT analysis the approximation coefficients $A_i[n]$ are reintroduced to the low pass-high pass filter bank. In this study, a 5-level DWT analysis was performed, and the outputs of interest are A_5, D_1, D_2, D_3, D_4 and D_5 .

Signal energy analysis

Using the 33 Lamb wave signals recorded in the curing process, the energy of the wavelet detail $d(j, n)$ is calculated and scaled with respect to the first measurement taken. The energy of a wavelet detail $d(j, n)$ is then determined as follows:

$$E_n({}^s d_i) = \frac{1}{E_s({}^s d_1)} \sum_{k=0}^n |{}^s d_i[k]|^2 \quad (12)$$

in which i is the index of the current measurement. The degree of cure is then calculated using the following equation:

$$\alpha(t) = 1 - E_n({}^s d_i) \quad (13)$$

3.3 Validation

To validate the results, the curing behavior of the epoxy prepreg is investigated using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). Isothermal DSC scans were done by heating the epoxy sample using the curing cycle provided by the manufacturer. The samples were heated from 25°C up to a maximum temperature of 120°C. This temperature was held for 60 mins, after which the sample was cooled at different rates (5, 3°C/min) down to 25°C. The degree of cure $\alpha(t)$ is obtained by integrating the area under the heat flow graph obtained by DSC. The graph of the degree of cure α_{DSC} , obtained by differential scanning calorimetry, will be compared with the one generated by the wavelet transform α_{DWT} to validate this ultrasonic cure monitoring method.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Optimal mother wavelet selection

The tested wavelet library L , consisted of Daubechies (db), Haar, and Symlet (sym) wavelets. The notation using the wavelets library is given by the following equation:

$$L = [db1, db2, db3, sym4, sym20, haar] \quad (14)$$

Where $db1, db2$ and $db3$ represent the Daubechies wavelets with 1, 2 and 3 vanishing moments, respectively, $sym4$ and $sym20$ represent the Symlet wavelets with 4 and 20 vanishing moments, respectively and $haar$ represents the Haar wavelets. The collected Lamb wave signals were arranged in a 2000×33 matrix where each signal represents a sample n at time t . The average EER for each mother wavelet across all 33 signal samples is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Average signal energy-to-entropy ratio for the tested mother wavelets

Mother wavelet	EER
<i>db1</i>	21.5×10^3
<i>db2</i>	238×10^3
<i>db3</i>	1.17×10^6
<i>sym4</i>	1.6×10^6
<i>sym20</i>	5.9×10^6
<i>haar</i>	21.5×10^3

Furthermore, the variation of the EER across the sample number n is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Energy-to-entropy ratio as a function of the sample number n for each of the tested mother wavelets

From the results of Table 1, we can see that the "sym20" mother wavelet has the highest average EER of 5.9×10^6 . Therefore, this wavelet contains high amounts of energy per unit of Shannon's entropy. This translates into the mother wavelet's ability to concentrate energy effectively and to capture important features of the Lamb wave signal while minimizing noise.

4.2 DWT of the Lamb wave signal

Figure 3 shows the level 5 approximation and detail coefficients for the first Lamb wave signal recorded during the cure monitoring experiment. The detail coefficients reflect the main A_0 wavelet packet recorded in the main signal present at $400 \leq k \leq 800$ effectively by filtering out all the low-frequency components of the signal. Important features such as the energy carried by the A_0 waves can be extracted from the detailed coefficients of the DWT. Applying the 5-level DWT to a signal that appears to be holding little to no information resulted in a good localization of the A_0 wave packet as shown in Figure 4. In a typical Lamb wave analysis, the signal shown in Figure 4 is disregarded because it is too noisy, and thus no relevant features can be extracted from it.

Figure 3: Original signal, approximation coefficients, and detail coefficients of the signal captured at $n = 0$

Figure 4: Original signal, approximation coefficients, and detail coefficients of the signal captured at $n = 10$

4.3 Signal energy analysis

Figure 5 shows the degree of cure extracted from the signal energy of the detail coefficients for each signal sample. From this analysis, we can see that curing begins at $t = 30 \text{ mins}$ and ends at $t = 60 \text{ mins}$. The shape of the graph matches the typical degree of cure graphs found in the literature [13].

Figure 5: Degree of cure of the prepreg calculated from the ultrasonic Lamb wave signals

From Figure 5, we can see that the degree of cure is approximately 0 for the first 30 minutes of the experiment. Indicating that the curing reaction begins at $t = 30mins$. The degree of cure then reaches the value of 1 at $t = 70 mins$ signifying the end of the curing reactions.

4.4 Validation of the degree of cure

The results of the ultrasonic tests were validated against the analysis of the DSC test. Figure 6 shows the degree of cure of the prepreg obtained from the DSC test. The correlation between the degree of cure obtained from the ultrasonic test and the degree of cure obtained from DSC analysis was good with a correlation coefficient $R^2 = 0.68$.

Figure 6: Degree of cure of the prepreg calculated from differential scanning calorimetry

The start time and end time of the curing reaction were also validated. As shown in Figure 6, the curing reaction starts at $t = 30mins$ and ends at $t = 70mins$. These results agree with the start and end times found from the DWT analysis of the Lamb wave signals.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the application of the DWT in ultrasonic testing was studied. Lamb wave signals were recorded during the curing process of the 7-layer XPREG-XA120 prepreg epoxy adhesive film. A five-level DWT was applied to the 33 recorded signals. The results have shown that the DWT amplifies the desired features of the analyzed signal since it was able to condense and filter noisy Lamb wave signals. Furthermore, the energy of the wavelet's detail coefficients was used to calculate the degree of cure of the prepreg as a function of time. This analysis was then validated using differential scanning calorimetry. The results have shown the ability of ultrasonic Lamb waves to monitor the curing reaction. Future studies need to further explore the utility of DWT and its variants in cure monitoring applications. Real wavelets have been proven to have several disadvantages when processing a particular signal. Future work can tackle the usage of more complex variants of the DWT such as the DTCWT to measure the degree of cure of the prepreg during the manufacturing process.

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